

UNDERSTANDING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN INDIA: PATTERNS, INSTITUTIONAL RESPONSE AND GLOBAL LESSONS

Lubna Ludheen & Moumita Barman

WORKING PAPER

ISSUE-04 | OCTOBER-2025 | VOLUME-05

Road to People & Platforms: Let's Talk Accountability

DCS25 WEEKLY WEBINAR SERIES

Starting from October 08, 2025

- Theme I : **Governing Data, Governing Rights**
- Theme II : **Digital Justice and Citizenship**
- Theme III : **Truth in the Age of Disinformation**
- Theme IV : **Technology for Local Futures**
- Theme V : **Digital Artisans and Cultural Innovation**
- Theme VI : **Ethical AI for Social Good**

SCAN QR FOR DCS25 REGISTRATION

Organisers

Principal Partners

Associate Partners

Inclusion and Equity Partner

Knowledge Partners

14-15 November | T-HUB, Hyderabad

For more information, visit the CDPP website: www.cdpp.co.in

**Understanding Gender-Based Violence
in India: Patterns, Institutional Response,
and Global Lessons**

Moumita Barman & Lubna Ludheen

WORKING PAPER

ISSUE 04 | OCTOBER 2025 | VOLUME 05

Acknowledgement

The Centre for Development Policy and Practice (CDPP) is pleased to present this working paper as part of our ongoing effort to bridge research, policy, and practice in addressing pressing human rights challenges in India. We wish to acknowledge the many individuals whose contributions made it possible.

We are deeply grateful to Prof. Ipsita Sapra, Professor, School of Public Policy and Governance, TISS Hyderabad, Dr. Sheela Prasad, Professor (Retd.), University of Hyderabad, and Ms. Soma Wadhwa, Senior Research Fellow, CDPP and Associate Professor, School of Modern Media, UPES, Dehradun, for their valuable feedback, comments, and guidance, which greatly strengthened the quality, rigor, and clarity of this work.

We also extend our appreciation to our research interns — Ananya Ashutosh Kotwal, Emaan Chimote, Gayathri Lakshmi, Kavin Pillai, and Shraddha Pratapa — for their dedicated support in compiling data, reviewing literature, and assisting with analysis throughout the course of this study.

Finally, we would like to thank the CDPP team for their constant encouragement, collaborative spirit, and intellectual engagement, which made this working paper possible.

By consolidating evidence on the multidimensional nature of gender-based violence (GBV) in India and situating it within intersectional, legal, and historical frameworks, this paper reflects our commitment to fostering research-informed approaches that can guide inclusive, survivor-centred, and systemic interventions. We hope that this work contributes meaningfully to discussions on GBV, policy reform, and social transformation, providing both scholars and practitioners with insights to advance a violence-free and equitable future.

Table of Contents

Acknowledgement.....	5
Abstract	9
1 Research Question	1
1.1 Primary Research Question	1
1.2 Sub-Questions	1
1.3 Objectives.....	1
1.4 Methodology.....	2
1.5 Scope and Structure	2
2 The Historical Backdrop of GBV	3
2.1 The Roots of GBV in India	3
2.2 Colonial and Post Colonial Dimensions	4
2.3 Contemporary Persistence of Patriarchy	4
3 Typologies of Gender Based Violence in India	5
3.1 Domestic and Intimate Partner Violence.....	5
3.1.1 Domestic Violence in India.....	8
3.2 Sexual Harassment and Assault.....	9
3.2.1 Public Spaces	9
3.2.2 Workplace and Institutions	10
3.3 Caste, Tribal, and Religion Based GBV in India	12
3.3.1 Intersectional Vulnerabilities	12
3.3.2 Violence Against Dalit Women	12
3.3.3 Tribal Women and Structural Violence	12
3.3.4 Trafficking and Exploitation.....	13
3.3.5 Religion and Patterns of Violence	13
3.3.6 Symbolic Violence and Media Representation	14
3.4 Online Gender Based Violence	14
3.4.1 Forms and Manifestations.....	14
3.4.2 Political and Public Life	15
3.4.3 Intersectional Vulnerabilities	15
3.4.4 From Online to Offline Harm	15
3.4.5 Consequences.....	16
3.5 Trafficking and Exploitation.....	16
3.5.1 Defining Human Trafficking	16
3.5.2 Mechanisms of Exploitation	17
3.5.3 Cross-Border Trafficking	17
3.5.4 Data and Trends.....	17
3.5.5 Legal and Institutional Responses.....	18
3.5.6 Persistent Challenges.....	18
3.6 Honour Killings and Forced Marriages.....	19
3.6.1 Forced Marriage as a Human Rights Violation.....	19
3.6.2 Honour Based Violence and Its Social Roots.....	19
3.6.3 Contemporary Indian Context	20
3.6.4 State and Institutional Responses.....	20
3.7 Discrimination and Violence Against LGBTQI+ People.....	21
3.7.1 Global Perspectives	21
3.7.2 Indian Realities.....	22
3.7.3 Legal and Institutional Gaps.....	22

3.7.4 Vulnerability of Transgender People.....	23
3.7.5 Structural and Social Barriers.....	23
3.7.6 Towards Equality	23
3.8 Institutional Gender-Based Violence: Custody and Healthcare	24
4 Impact of GBV	26
4.1 Health Consequences of Gender-Based Violence.....	26
4.1.1 Sexual and Reproductive Health.....	26
4.1.2 Neurological and Stress-Related Health.....	27
4.1.3 Broader Physical Health.....	28
4.1.4 Mental Health Outcomes	28
4.1.5 Integrated Burden.....	29
4.2 Economic and Educational Consequences of Gender Based Violence.....	29
4.2.1 Macroeconomic Impacts	29
4.2.2 Everyday Economic Violence	30
4.2.3 Educational Access and School Related Violence.....	30
4.2.4 Empirical Evidence from Ethiopia	31
4.2.5 Educational Barriers and Intergenerational Impact.....	31
4.3 Intergenerational and Structural Impacts of Gender-Based Violence.....	32
4.3.1 Transmission Across Generations	32
4.3.2 Structural Burdens on Health and Social Systems.....	33
4.3.3 Economic Costs and National Development.....	34
4.3.4 Cycles of Harm and Systemic Response	35
4.4 Political and Civic Impact	35
4.4.1 Defining Violence Against Women in Political Life	35
4.4.2 Magnitude and Forms of Political Violence	36
4.4.3 Regional Dimensions and the Normalisation of Violence.....	36
4.4.4 Consequences for Individuals and Institutions.....	37
4.4.5 Policy Innovations and Democratic Safeguards	37
4.4.6 Democracy at Risk.....	38
5 Institutional Addressal in India	38
5.1 Legal and Policy Framework.....	38
5.1.1 Rape, Sexual Assault, Sexual Violence, Sexual Abuse, Coercion, Non-Consensual act (Section 375 IPC and Section 376 IPC)	38
5.1.2 Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956 (ITPA)(Sections 359–369 IPC and Sections 370–374 IPC).....	43
5.1.3 Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 (Amended 1986)(Sections 304B, 498, 498A IPC).....	47
5.1.4 Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986 (Section 354A, 354B, 354C, 354D, 509 IPC).....	50
5.1.5 Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971 (Amended 2021) (Sections 312, 313, 314 IPC)	55
5.1.6 Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987.....	59
5.1.7 Information Technology Act, 2000—Sections 67, 66C, 66D, 66E.....	62
5.1.8 Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 (PWDVA) ..	65
5.1.9 Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006 (PCMA)	68
5.1.10 Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012 (POCSO) ..	71
5.1.11 Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013	74

5.1.12 Acid Attacks (Section 326A & 326B IPC)	77
5.1.13 Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013 (POSH Act).....	80
5.1.14 Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019	83
5.1.15 Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023	86
5.2 Police and Judiciary	90
5.2.1 Specialised Police and Support Systems	90
5.2.2 Judicial Challenges	91
5.3 National and State Commissions	92
5.3.1 National and State Commissions for Women	92
5.3.2 Commission for Protection of Child Rights	92
5.3.3 National Council for Transgender Persons	92
5.3.4 Effectiveness and Gaps	93
5.4 Civil Society and Community-Based Mechanisms	93
5.4.1 Grassroots Justice Mechanisms and NGO Legal Aid.....	93
5.4.2 Helplines.....	94
5.5 Budget Allocations	94
5.5.1 Budget Utilisation: Gaps and Unspent Allocations	96
5.6 Challenges.....	98
6 Comparative Global Practices.....	100
6.1 Legal and Policy Reforms.....	100
6.2 Institutional and Service Delivery Models	101
6.3 Community-Based and Social Norms Transformation	103
6.4 Technological Interventions.....	104
6.5 Economic Empowerment Initiatives	105
6.6 Comparative Analysis: International Practices vs. India's Approach	106
6.6.1 Legal and Policy Landscape: A Tale of Two Realities	106
6.6.2 Institutional and Community Responses: Bridging the Gaps.....	107
7 Best Practices for India: Policy and Practice Recommendations.....	108
7.1 Prevention	108
7.2 Protection	109
7.3 Prosecution	110
7.4 Multi-stakeholder Collaboration	112
7.5 Technology Use	113
8 Conclusion	114
8.1 A Multidimensional Crisis of Gender-Based Violence.....	114
8.2 Reflections on Systemic Challenges and Emerging Opportunities.....	115
8.3 A Call for Integrated, Inclusive, and Context-Sensitive Interventions ..	115
9 Way Forward	116
Tables	118
References.....	165
About CDPP.....	177
Governing Council	178
Research Team	180
About CLES.....	182
CLES Advisory Board.....	183

Abstract

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) in India spans intersections of caste, class, religion, gender identity, and geography, making it a critical human rights concern. This paper synthesizes existing data, legal frameworks, and scholarship on GBV, to understand its forms, impacts, and institutional responses through both national and global lenses.

It situates GBV within India's sociocultural and historical contexts, from patriarchal and colonial legacies to present-day inequities, and expands its scope beyond intimate and sexual violence to include digital, caste- and religion-based, and state or community-inflicted harms.

Drawing on NCRB, NFHS, media, and legal data, the study highlights underreported violence and systemic barriers to justice. Incorporating insights from Sweden, Argentina, Rwanda, South Africa, and Bangladesh, it outlines effective practices such as preventive education, survivor-centred policing, and community justice. The paper concludes that eliminating GBV demands intersectional, systemic, and rights-based reforms for inclusive and sustainable change.

Authors:

Lubna Ludheen and Moumita Barman

Keywords: Gender-based violence (GBV), intersectionality, institutional frameworks, digital violence, policy recommendations.

1 Research Question

1.1 Primary Research Question

How is gender-based violence (GBV) manifested in India, and what lessons can be drawn from global literature to inform more inclusive and effective interventions?

1.2 Sub-Questions

- **Typologies of GBV:** What are the various forms of GBV in India and how does it intersect with the dimensions of caste, religion, class, and disability?
- **Impacts of GBV:** What are the documented physical, psychological, economic, social, and political impacts of GBV on individuals, families, and communities in India?
- **Institutional Responses:** How do Indian legal, policy, and institutional frameworks respond to GBV, and what gaps or challenges are highlighted in the literature?
- **Global Lessons:** What strategies, policies, and practices from international contexts (e.g., Sweden, Argentina, Rwanda, South Africa, and Bangladesh) are relevant or adaptable to the Indian context?
- **Policy Implications:** Based on the literature, what are the recommended interventions to strengthen prevention, protection, prosecution, and multi-stakeholder collaboration in India?

1.3 Objectives

This paper conducts a **comprehensive review of literature** on GBV in India within a comparative global framework. The objectives are to:

- **Synthesize** existing scholarship on the typologies and patterns of GBV in India, including its intersectional dimensions.
- **Consolidate** evidence on the physical, psychological, economic, and socio-political impacts of GBV.
- **Map** legal, institutional, and policy frameworks addressing GBV and identify documented strengths and limitations.
- **Incorporate** insights from global literature to identify promising approaches relevant to the Indian context.

- **Develop** policy-oriented recommendations based on the reviewed literature and international lessons.

1.4 Methodology

This study employs a **qualitative, exploratory, and integrative literature review**, combining academic research, policy documents, and secondary data to construct a comprehensive understanding of GBV and institutional responses in India.

- **Literature Review:** Academic publications, peer-reviewed articles, and reports from international agencies, government bodies, and civil society organisations were reviewed to trace conceptual frameworks, prevalence trends, and sociocultural contexts of GBV.
- **Policy and Legal Review:** Legal frameworks such as the IPC, BNS, Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (2005), POCSO Act (2012), and PoSH Act (2013), along with institutional mechanisms such as National Commission for Women (NCW), state commissions, helplines, and One-Stop Centres, were reviewed to map existing responses.
- **Secondary Data:** Quantitative data from NCRB, NFHS, and other official sources were reviewed to identify patterns and trends; qualitative insights were drawn from NGO and media reports.
- **Global Review:** Literature from countries such as Sweden, Argentina, Rwanda, South Africa, and Bangladesh was analysed to identify practices and strategies adaptable to India.

This approach synthesises literature, policy, and data to provide a cohesive picture of GBV and institutional mechanisms.

1.5 Scope and Structure

The review encompasses GBV in its physical, sexual, psychological, economic, and digital forms, with attention to intersectional dimensions shaped by caste, religion, class, gender identity, and disability.

The paper is structured as follows:

- **Section 2:** The Historical Backdrop of GBV in India.
- **Section 3:** Typologies and forms of GBV.

- **Section 4:** Impacts of GBV at individual, familial, structural, and political levels.
- **Section 5:** Institutional and policy responses in India.
- **Section 6:** Global literature and comparative lessons.
- **Section 7:** Policy recommendations and implications for India.
- **Section 8:** Conclusion and reflections.

2 The Historical Backdrop of GBV

Gender-based violence (GBV) is a pervasive phenomenon that cuts across social, economic, and geographic boundaries (Butalia & Bhasin, 2023). Rooted in unequal power relations between men and women, it is sustained by cultural traditions, social acceptance of harmful practices, and gaps in legal protections (Tsapalas et al., 2020).

2.1 The Roots of GBV in India

In India, the origins of GBV are deeply interwoven with historical, religious, and cultural frameworks. Ancient texts such as the Manusmriti (c. 2nd century BCE) portrayed women as inherently flawed, associating them with traits like dishonesty, idleness, and anger. Literary epics reinforced these ideas; for example, the Ramayana highlights Draupadi's public *vastraharana* (disrobing) and Sita's trial by fire, both of which portray women as morally suspect and bound to prove their purity. Similarly, the *Dharmashastras*, *Atharvaveda*, and *Tolkappiyam* endorsed early marriage for girls, often at or before puberty (Seshasayee, 2021).

Over time, these prescriptions were translated into entrenched practices. The dowry system, where families of brides provide material wealth to the groom's family, spread across caste, class, and religion, while *sati* demanded widows immolate themselves on their husbands' funeral pyres.

Such practices institutionalised women's subordination and reinforced patriarchal control. As Chakravarti (1993) argues, the ideology of *pativrata* (the chaste and devoted wife) became central to the patriarchal caste-class structure, positioning fidelity and chastity as women's highest virtues and binding them to familial honour.

These frameworks laid the foundation for a patrilineal system in which property and inheritance rights remained confined to men. Consequently, Indian women have historically faced not only the global patterns of sexual violence and domestic abuse but also specific forms of violence such as dowry deaths, honour killings, forced and child marriages, and caste or religion-based violence disproportionately targeting Dalit and minority women (Seshasayee, 2021).

2.2 Colonial and Post Colonial Dimensions

The colonial encounter further complicated women's status. According to Neelam Deo, a former Indian ambassador and board member of Breakthrough India, British colonialism "froze social structures and delayed progress on women's rights." Reform efforts such as the abolition of Sati during the Bengal Renaissance and the legalisation of widow remarriage emerged only after sustained social campaigns in Bengal and Maharashtra. While colonial reforms sought to curb extreme practices, they often reinforced patriarchal authority by positioning women primarily as symbols of cultural identity (Seshasayee, 2021).

2.3 Contemporary Persistence of Patriarchy

Despite globalisation and shifts in social attitudes, patriarchal values remain deeply embedded in South Asia. Niaz (2003) notes that rigid sociocultural practices continue to devalue women's roles and elevate the likelihood of violence. Practices such as arranged marriage, dowry, and restrictions on female mobility are often justified as preservers of family honour, even when they reproduce gender inequality. Although some communities practise these traditions without perceiving immediate harm, they perpetuate a patriarchal order that obstructs legal reform and social change (Bishwajit et al., 2016).

Ultimately, GBV in South Asia cannot be understood without recognising the interplay between historical texts, entrenched sociocultural norms, colonial legacies, and contemporary structures. In many communities, men are positioned as bearers of entitlement and authority, with domestic violence normalised as a "natural" element of marital life. This normalisation ensures that GBV remains underreported, underestimated, and, at times, overlooked as a social-economic, health, and cultural problem.

3 Typologies of Gender Based Violence in India

Gender based violence (GBV) in India takes multiple forms, from domestic violence and sexual assault to trafficking, online abuse, and institutional harm. Despite laws and constitutional safeguards, GBV remains deeply rooted in social norms, patriarchal structures, and unequal power relations. Women and girls are disproportionately affected, but queer communities and marginalised groups such as Dalits, Adivasis, and religious minorities also face heightened vulnerabilities. The persistence of GBV reflects not only individual acts of violence but also systemic failures within law enforcement, healthcare, and social institutions meant to provide protection. Understanding its varied dimensions is crucial for shaping effective interventions, strengthening accountability mechanisms, and ensuring the safety, dignity, and rights of all individuals in society.

Chart 1

Typologies of Gender Based Violence

3.1 Domestic and Intimate Partner Violence

Domestic violence (DV) and intimate partner violence (IPV) are among the most prevalent forms of gender-based violence worldwide. While the terms are often used interchangeably, they denote slightly

different scopes. Domestic violence refers broadly to abuse within a domestic setting, encompassing not only spousal or partner violence but also violence involving parents, siblings, or extended family members. In contrast, intimate partner violence specifically describes violence perpetrated by a current or former spouse, partner, or individual in a romantic or dating relationship (Women Against Abuse, n.d.).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021), nearly one in three women globally (about 30%) have experienced either physical and/or sexual violence by an intimate partner in their lifetime. The forms of IPV are multifaceted, ranging from physical assault (hitting, choking, burning), sexual coercion, psychological abuse (threats, intimidation, isolation), to economic control (withholding money, restricting employment or education).

IPV often begins early, with adolescents experiencing what is termed teen dating violence, and can persist throughout the course of life. The consequences are severe and wide, ranging from immediate injuries to chronic health issues such as cardiovascular disease, reproductive complications, and mental health conditions including depression and post-traumatic stress disorder (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2024).

WHO notes that women subjected to IPV are twice as likely to experience depression and almost twice as likely to develop alcohol use disorders. Beyond health impacts, IPV undermines educational attainment, employment opportunities, and social participation, perpetuating cycles of gender inequality (WHO, 2013).

While IPV disproportionately affects women, it also impacts men and individuals in LGBTQ+ relationships, particularly where structural inequalities intersect with stigma and marginalisation. Data further reveal that a significant proportion of femicides are committed by intimate partners, underscoring the lethal potential of IPV when unaddressed (Women Against Abuse, n.d.).

Violence against women also incurs significant costs to states, survivors, and communities. These costs are direct and indirect, tangible and intangible. For example, salaries of shelter workers are direct tangible costs, while lost productivity represents indirect costs. Everyone bears the burden—survivors, perpetrators, governments, and societies at large.

The economic toll is evident across contexts: according to UN Women (Puri 2016), the cost (public, private, and social) of violence against women worldwide amounts to USD 1.5 trillion. In Vietnam, violence represents 1.41% of GDP, with women survivors earning 35% less than those unaffected; in Egypt, over 500,000 workdays are lost annually due to marital violence, with health sector costs surpassing USD 14 million for just one-quarter of survivors; in Morocco, physical and sexual violence costs reach 2.85 billion dirhams annually (USD 308 million); and across the European Union, gender-based violence costs EUR 366 billion annually, of which EUR 289 billion (79%) is attributable specifically to violence against women (UN Women–Headquarters, 2024).

Efforts to promote gender equality and women’s economic empowerment are often viewed as essential strategies to reduce IPV. Yet, theoretical perspectives on the relationship between women’s empowerment and violence diverge. Household bargaining models suggest that when women improve their relative economic position—through income, education, or employment—they gain greater bargaining power within the household. This strengthens their “outside option,” or ability to exit an abusive relationship, thereby reducing the likelihood of violence (Bergvall, 2024).

Conversely, male backlash models posit that women’s increased economic independence can challenge traditional gender roles and established household power dynamics. In contexts where male dominance is socially expected, such shifts may provoke a violent reaction from men seeking to reassert control (Bergvall, 2024).

Empirically examining this relationship presents several challenges, particularly in terms of data availability and measurement. IPV and DMV are a deeply sensitive issue and often under-reported due to stigma, fear, or normalization of violence (Bergvall, 2024). Distinguishing whether changes in reported IPV reflect actual shifts in violence or differences in reporting behavior is therefore critical. Addressing these challenges is essential to developing evidence-based interventions that not only advance women’s economic empowerment but also safeguard their well-being and security.

3.1.1 Domestic Violence in India

The Latest National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB)'s *Crime in India 2023* report underscores the scale and persistence of domestic violence, particularly in the form of dowry deaths (Section 304B IPC) and cruelty by husband or his relatives (Section 498A IPC). In 2023, India registered 6156 dowry death cases (incidents) and over 1.3 lakh cases of cruelty by husbands or in-laws, making domestic violence one of the most prevalent crimes against women. Prevalence rates were especially high in states such as Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Bihar, and Rajasthan, while Telangana and Delhi recorded some of the highest relative rates of cruelty cases compared to population size. These statistics (Table 2) highlight how dowry practices, patriarchal norms, and weak enforcement of protective laws continue to make homes unsafe for many women (NCRB, 2023).

Analysis of dowry death cases from NCRB data of 2023 reveal a heavy backlog of dowry death trials. Of the 62,747 cases under trial, including 56,859 carried over from previous years and 5,888 newly sent for trial, only 4,522 were disposed of during the year, while 58,225 remained pending, indicating a pendency rate of 92.8 percent. Among the 4,284 cases in which trials were completed, only 1,501 resulted in conviction, yielding a conviction rate of 35 percent, with the remainder ending in discharge or acquittal. These figures underscore persistent challenges in securing timely justice for victims of dowry deaths and reflect both procedural delays and systemic inefficiencies in the prosecution of gender-based violence (NCRB, 2023).

It is important to note that large or low numbers in crime data do not necessarily reflect the true scale of incidents, as domestic violence cases in India are significantly underreported due to deep-rooted patriarchal norms, stigma, and fear of retaliation.

Complementing the NCRB's administrative data, a nationally representative study using NFHS-5 data (2019–2021) estimated that 31.2% of ever-married women in India experienced some form of domestic violence. Of these, 28.5% reported physical violence, 13.1% emotional violence, and 5.7% sexual violence. Karnataka reported the highest prevalence (47.3%), followed by Bihar (42.0%), Manipur (40.4%), and Telangana (40.2%), whereas states like Goa (9.8%) and Lakshadweep (0.8%) showed the lowest levels. The analysis further identified strong predictors of DV, including lower education levels, lower socioeconomic

status, alcohol use by husbands, and patriarchal household structures. Importantly, Muslim women were found to be more than twice as likely to face DV compared to women from other religions, while women from Scheduled Castes were also at greater risk compared to other caste groups (Mishra et al., 2024).

These patterns reveal that domestic violence is not only an issue of individual households but one deeply embedded in structural inequalities. Researchers have identified multiple factors that perpetuate DV, spanning cultural, political, economic, and legal domains. Cultural expectations of gender roles, dowry customs, and the acceptability of violence within intimate relationships normalise abuse. Politically, the under representation of women in decision-making, the framing of the family as a private sphere beyond state intervention, and the weak organisation of women as a political force hinder accountability. Economic dependence of women on men, discriminatory property laws, and limited access to education and employment further entrench vulnerability. Legally, the lesser status of women in both statutory provisions and practice, coupled with low legal literacy and insensitive treatment by police and judiciary, ensures that many survivors remain trapped in cycles of violence (Chaudhary, 2013).

Taken together, the NCRB's crime statistics, NFHS-based prevalence data, and the structural drivers identified by researchers reaffirm that domestic violence in India is a systemic issue. It is sustained by cultural norms, political neglect, economic inequalities, and legal shortcomings, demanding interventions that extend beyond legal reforms to transformative social and institutional change.

3.2 Sexual Harassment and Assault

3.2.1 Public Spaces

Research in India has consistently shown that sexual harassment in public spaces is both pervasive and normalised. Bharucha and Khatri (2018), in their study of Mumbai, demonstrate that women across socioeconomic strata regularly face harassment such as lewd comments, groping, and stalking. The study highlights enabling conditions like inadequate lighting, weak police presence, and non-functional helplines, which foster an unsafe environment. Importantly, many women themselves identified patriarchy, the easy access to pornography, and social tolerance of harassment as root causes. Even among urban, educated

women, internalised gender norms perpetuate the belief that women are inherently more vulnerable than men, reinforcing cycles of victimisation.

Bhattacharyya (2014) extends this discussion by linking domestic violence and sexual assault in public spaces. She argues that the dichotomy of “private” and “public” violence is misleading, as both are rooted in patriarchal socialisation. Her study found that over 80% of men who grew up in violent households normalised aggressive behaviour, carrying these attitudes into public life. Simultaneously, women socialised into acceptance of subordination often tolerate harassment in silence. This intersection illustrates how structural violence within the household reinforces spatial violence in the streets, parks, and workplaces.

A large scale quantitative study by Madan and Nalla (2016) conducted in Delhi after the Nirbhaya incident provides further evidence. Surveying over 1,300 respondents, the authors found that women not only reported higher rates of victimisation but also rated harassment as more serious than men did. Public transportation systems which includes buses, metros, bus stops, and roadsides, were identified as particularly unsafe. While women perceived taxis and auto-rickshaws as risky, actual victimisation was less frequent there compared to overcrowded public transport. The study also revealed that fewer women than men felt safe using public spaces, with harassment often occurring in broad daylight. Situational factors such as absence of surveillance (CCTV), ineffective policing, and overcrowding heightened vulnerability.

Taken together, these studies underline that sexual harassment in Indian public spaces is not incidental but embedded within broader patriarchal structures. It thrives in environments where weak institutional response converges with normalised gendered hierarchies. The result is both physical victimisation and the production of spatial exclusion, where women are denied equal and safe access to urban life (Bharucha & Khatri, 2018; Bhattacharyya, 2014; Madan & Nalla, 2016).

3.2.2 Workplace and Institutions

Workplace sexual harassment reflects broader structural inequalities within India’s labour market. Barman (2024) highlights that women in the workforce continue to encounter discrimination and harassment despite the existence of protective legislation. Gender stereotypes, unequal power hierarchies, and male-dominated work environments foster conditions where harassment is often trivialised or

normalised. Women are frequently reluctant to report incidents due to fear of retaliation, loss of employment opportunities, or stigmatisation within the workplace (Barman, 2024).

The persistence of sexual harassment at workplaces undermines women's participation in the labour force and reinforces economic marginalisation. Even with the enactment of the *Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013*, gaps remain in institutional enforcement and awareness. As Barman (2024) observes, many organisations fail to fully implement internal complaints mechanisms, limiting the Act's transformative potential. Thus, workplace harassment functions not only as an individual violation but also as a systemic barrier to gender equality and economic empowerment.

Sexual harassment within educational settings has also drawn increasing attention in recent years, both because of its prevalence and its damaging consequences for students and staff. Thomas (2015) emphasises that harassment in colleges and universities undermines the fundamental right to dignity, equality, and education. The study found that incidents often go unreported due to fear of disgrace, retaliation, or negative impacts on academic and career prospects. In many institutions, grievance redressal mechanisms mandated under the 2013 Act are absent or ineffective, leaving victims without adequate recourse (Thomas, 2015).

Women in educational institutions experience harassment in diverse forms, from verbal innuendo and sexually coloured remarks to quid pro quo situations involving faculty members. The consequences are profound—reduced academic confidence, social withdrawal, absenteeism, and in severe cases, dropping out of courses. Faculty and staff subjected to harassment report professional isolation, reputational damage, and job insecurity (Thomas, 2015).

Thomas (2015) argues that the fiduciary relationship between teachers and students intensifies the harm, as perpetrators often occupy positions of authority. Effective prevention and redressal require not only compliance with legal mandates but also cultural change within institutions. Awareness programmes, sensitisation workshops, and strong Internal Complaints Committees are identified as critical to creating safe educational spaces.

3.3 Caste, Tribal, and Religion Based GBV in India

3.3.1 Intersectional Vulnerabilities

Caste, tribe, and religion profoundly shape the dynamics of GBV in India, producing layered vulnerabilities that make women from marginalised communities disproportionately at risk. Dalit, Adivasi/tribal, and Muslim women experience violence not only because of their gender but also due to their caste, ethnic, and religious identities. These overlapping marginalisations create distinct and intersectional experiences of GBV, where structural hierarchies combine with patriarchal norms to reinforce subordination.

3.3.2 Violence Against Dalit Women

Dalit women, situated at the lowest levels of caste, class, and gender hierarchies, have historically been subjected to systemic sexual exploitation and abuse. Violence against them often functions as a collective tool of caste oppression, intended to discipline entire communities. As COFEM (2022) notes, rape and sexual harassment of Dalit women are frequently deployed as weapons to reinforce caste dominance, as tragically seen in the Hathras gang rape and murder of 2020. Despite constitutional protections and laws such as the *Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act*, Dalit women remain highly vulnerable due to institutional apathy, delayed justice processes, and entrenched caste prejudice. NFHS-5 data (2019–2021) confirms this reality, showing that 33.9% of Scheduled Caste women had experienced physical violence since age 15, with 26.6% reporting such violence in the 12 months before the survey.

3.3.3 Tribal Women and Structural Violence

Tribal women face similar, and in some cases heightened, risks shaped by geographic isolation, poverty, and systemic neglect in education, healthcare, and justice delivery. NFHS-5 (2019–2021) shows that 31% of Scheduled Tribe women reported physical violence since age 15, with 23.6% experiencing it in the year preceding the survey. Muthukkaruppan (2017) explains that caste and tribe related violence operates through visible violence (physical assault and killings), structural violence (normalised exclusion and humiliation), and symbolic violence (discourses that portray tribal communities as “primitive” and undeserving of protection). These layers often overlap, leaving tribal

women vulnerable to physical attacks during land disputes, everyday discrimination, and neglect by institutions (Halder, 2021).

The socioeconomic roots of such violence are argued to be closely tied to industrialisation and displacement. An insensitive state apparatus, often in collaboration with corporate actors and contractors, has contributed to the dispossession of tribal communities. Tribal women, in particular, suffer severe deprivation, sexual abuse, and harassment at the hands of state officials, traders, and middlemen (Dhal, 2018). They are also caught in the crossfire of armed conflict between the state and Maoist insurgents in Maoist-dominant areas of India, where they face violence from both security forces and insurgents.

3.3.4 Trafficking and Exploitation

Displacement and poverty have also heightened tribal women's vulnerability to trafficking. Organised groups often traffic young tribal girls to cities for domestic work, where they are subjected to exploitative labour, sexual harassment, and physical violence. Weak enforcement of anti-trafficking laws and the lack of valid identity documents or social protections exacerbate these hardships. Migrant tribal women face inhuman work conditions and are frequently deprived of basic rights, illustrating how economic marginalisation compounds gendered exploitation (Dhal, 2018).

3.3.5 Religion and Patterns of Violence

Religious affiliation also influences vulnerability to GBV. NFHS-5 (2019–2021) data shows that Hindu women reported 29.7% lifetime prevalence of physical violence, followed closely by Muslim women at 26.1%. Among Muslim women, 19.8% reported experiencing violence in the 12 months preceding the survey, reflecting their heightened exposure. Christian women (22.6%) and Buddhist/Neo-Buddhist women (29.5%) also report significant levels of violence, while Sikh women report comparatively lower rates at 11.7%. Women from “Other” religions, including smaller minority groups, recorded among the highest prevalence at 30.7%. These figures reveal that while GBV cuts across communities, women from minority religions, particularly Muslims and Buddhists, face compounded risks due to layered socioeconomic exclusion, patriarchal control, and systemic discrimination.

3.3.6 Symbolic Violence and Media Representation

Symbolic violence also plays a critical role in perpetuating inequalities. Media coverage often privileges cases involving upper-caste, middle-class women, portraying them as educated or professionally accomplished, thereby eliciting public empathy. In contrast, cases involving Dalit, tribal, or Muslim women are frequently depersonalised, with their caste, tribe, or religious identity minimised or erased (Krishnan, 2022). The Hathras case illustrates this selective visibility, where systemic caste-based violence was downplayed, reinforcing the invisibility of marginalised women's suffering.

Hence, caste, tribal, and religion based GBV in India is not incidental but deeply embedded in the country's social and political order. Dalit women face sexual violence as an instrument of caste oppression; tribal women are subjected to deprivation, displacement, trafficking, and conflict driven violence; and Muslim women experience layered exclusions that heighten their vulnerability. These intersecting systems of visible, structural, and symbolic violence reveal how hierarchies of caste, ethnicity, and religion reinforce gender oppression. Addressing them requires intersectional approaches that strengthen institutional accountability, challenge entrenched sociocultural hierarchies and provide holistic protections to women from marginalised communities.

3.4 Online Gender Based Violence

The rapid digital transformation has expanded opportunities for women and girls, but it has also opened new frontiers of violence. Online gender based violence (OGBV) encompasses a range of harmful acts perpetrated, amplified, or facilitated through digital technologies. The United Nations (2023) defines Technology Facilitated Gender based Violence (TFGBV) as any act using information and communication technologies that results in physical, sexual, psychological, social, or economic harm. This form of violence, intensified during the COVID-19 pandemic, now represents one of the most pressing challenges for gender equality in digital spaces.

3.4.1 Forms and Manifestations

OGBV takes diverse forms including cyberstalking, sextortion, image-based abuse, doxxing, impersonation, online grooming, and hate speech. UN Women (2020) highlights that the most frequently reported

abuses are misinformation and defamation (67%), cyber harassment (66%), hate speech (65%), impersonation (63%), and hacking or stalking (63%). In many cases, online abuse exacerbates offline violence, such as intimate partner abuse or trafficking. The UNESCO-ICFJ global survey (2020) of women journalists further underscores the severity of the problem: 73% reported experiencing online violence, including threats of physical (25%) and sexual violence (18%). These attacks often forced women to self-censor or withdraw from online spaces, curbing freedom of expression and civic participation (UNESCO, 2020).

3.4.2 Political and Public Life

For women in political and public life, online abuse is especially acute. Amnesty International's *Troll Patrol India* (2018) found that one in seven tweets mentioning women politicians was abusive, with nearly 20% of such content explicitly misogynistic. Muslim women politicians faced 94.1% more religious slurs compared to others, while women from marginalised castes endured 59% more caste-based abuse. Unmarried or divorced women politicians were also disproportionately targeted. Such attacks not only silence women but reinforce patriarchal exclusions from democratic participation.

3.4.3 Intersectional Vulnerabilities

Intersectionality shapes women's experiences of online abuse. Muslim women in India have been subjected to sexualised auctions and "pornified" memes in the infamous *Bulli Bai* and *Sulli Deals* cases, illustrating how misogyny, Islamophobia, and casteism converge in digital spaces (Udupa & Lahiri, 2022). Similarly, Indigenous Jarawa women in the Andaman Islands were subjected to humiliating online circulation of "human safari" videos, where their objectification was commodified as entertainment. These cases highlight how marginalised women—whether defined by religion, caste, or tribe—bear disproportionate burdens of OGBV.

3.4.4 From Online to Offline Harm

The Pollachi sexual assault case demonstrates the continuum between digital and physical violence, where online blackmail and circulation of videos escalated into systemic sexual exploitation. Such cases underline that OGBV cannot be seen in isolation; rather, it is part of broader patriarchal violence that migrates seamlessly between digital and physical worlds.

3.4.5 Consequences

The consequences of OGBV are profound. Survivors report stress, anxiety, depression, PTSD, and even suicidal ideation (United Nations, 2023). Politically, it undermines women's participation in democratic spaces; socially, it silences their voices; economically, it drives women out of digital labour markets. The UNESCO-ICFJ study revealed that many journalists responded to abuse by self-censoring or withdrawing from online interaction, while the Amnesty International report highlighted how platforms like Twitter fail to provide adequate safeguards. These findings demonstrate that OGBV is not merely a private or individual issue, but a structural barrier to gender equality and democratic participation.

According to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB, 2023), a total of 19,510 cyber crimes against women were reported in India in 2023. Among these, cyber pornography and hosting/publishing obscene sexual materials constituted the largest category with 2,767 cases, followed by cyber stalking or bullying (1,358 cases) and cyber blackmailing or threatening (304 cases). Other reported offences included defamation and morphing (505 cases), fake profiles (102 cases), and miscellaneous online offences (14,474 cases).

At the state level, Karnataka (7,002 cases), Telangana (1,447 cases), and Uttar Pradesh (1,463 cases) reported the highest absolute numbers, whereas states like Mizoram and Ladakh recorded no cases, reflecting uneven reporting or prevalence. Among Union Territories, Delhi (135 cases) and the Andaman & Nicobar Islands (37 cases) reported the highest numbers.

These figures (table 8 and table 9) indicate that cyber crimes against women are widespread and manifest in diverse forms, from harassment and defamation to more exploitative acts such as pornography and stalking.

3.5 Trafficking and Exploitation

3.5.1 Defining Human Trafficking

The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) defines human trafficking as the "recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of people through force, fraud or deception, with the aim of exploiting them for profit." This crime knows no boundaries, and men, women, and children of all ages and backgrounds are vulnerable.

Traffickers often rely on violence, fraudulent recruitment agencies, and false promises of education or employment to lure and coerce victims into situations of exploitation. The forms of exploitation are varied, spanning commercial sexual exploitation, forced labour, domestic servitude, and debt bondage. Victims are frequently stripped of their autonomy through restrictions on movement, non-payment of wages, confiscation of identification documents, and exposure to physical and sexual abuse (Iyer & Radha, 2016).

3.5.2 Mechanisms of Exploitation

In India, trafficking for sexual exploitation remains one of the most entrenched forms of abuse. Research in Mumbai's Kamathipura red-light district documents how women face coercion and violence not only from traffickers and brothel managers but also from intimate partners and clients. These women, often sold into sex work at a young age, endure repeated physical assaults, sexual coercion, and economic exploitation. The structural criminalisation of sex work further marginalises them, deterring survivors from seeking protection from law enforcement and exposing them to heightened risks of HIV and other health consequences (Karandikar et al., 2014). The exploitation does not stop at entry into sex work; coercive relationships where clients transition into partners and later into pimps are common, deepening cycles of violence and dependence.

3.5.3 Cross-Border Trafficking

The problem of trafficking is not confined to domestic circuits. Indian women have historically been trafficked to the Middle East and Europe for sexual exploitation and domestic servitude. At the same time, cross border flows complicate the picture. Bangladeshi women and children are trafficked into India or through India into Pakistan and Gulf countries, while Nepali children are trafficked into India for circus labour and other exploitative purposes (Iyer & Radha, 2016). This transnational dimension underscores the entanglement of trafficking with migration, poverty, and weak border governance.

3.5.4 Data and Trends

According to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) statistics, human trafficking remains a significant concern in India. Between 2018 and 2022, India registered between 1,714 and 2,278 cases annually under

the Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956 (women victims only). In 2023, a total of 1,788 cases were reported, involving 2,648 women victims, indicating that the annual incidence has remained broadly consistent over the last five years.

The highest number of cases in 2023 were reported in Karnataka (308 cases), Tamil Nadu (619 cases), and Maharashtra (211 cases). Other states with notable figures included Bihar (58 cases), Telangana (57 cases), and Delhi (59 cases). Within these cases, procuring or inducing children for the sake of prostitution accounted for 403 cases, while detaining a person in premises where prostitution is carried on accounted for 253 cases nationally. Union Territories collectively reported 78 cases, with Delhi contributing 59 cases and Daman & Diu 8 cases (Government of India, Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2024; NCRB, 2023) (Table 6).

3.5.5 *Legal and Institutional Responses*

The Government of India has adopted a range of legal and institutional measures to address these challenges. The *Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act of 1956* remains the primary legislation targeting commercial sexual exploitation, though newer provisions under the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita* (BNS) (2023) and *Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita* (BNSS) strengthen anti-trafficking enforcement, making such offences cognisable and non-bailable. To operationalise these laws, 827 Anti-Human Trafficking Units have been established across the country. National databases, such as the National Database of Human Trafficking Offenders, now track over 1.2 lakh profiles to aid investigations. The Ministry of Women and Child Development has also instituted rehabilitation schemes like Shakti Sadan, designed to provide shelter, counselling, and reintegration support for victims (Government of India, Ministry of Women and Child Development, 2024).

3.5.6 *Persistent Challenges*

Despite these interventions, trafficking thrives on systemic inequalities and entrenched patriarchal norms. Poverty, unemployment, and stigma remain powerful drivers, trapping women in exploitative conditions with few avenues for reintegration. Survivors often cite social attitudes, family expectations, and the absence of long-term rehabilitation services as barriers to exiting the trade (Iyer & Radha, 2016). The voices from Mumbai's Kamathipura demonstrate that beyond legal frameworks, the lived experiences of trafficked women are marked by violence,

dispossession, and silence, reflecting the structural complicity of institutions in perpetuating exploitation (Karandikar et al., 2014).

3.6 Honour Killings and Forced Marriages

3.6.1 Forced Marriage as a Human Rights Violation

Forced marriage is widely recognised as a form of domestic abuse, child abuse, and a violation of human rights. It occurs when one or both individuals cannot or do not consent to a marriage due to coercion, threats, or manipulation. In the UK, the *Anti-social Behaviour, Crime and Policing Act (2014)* criminalised forced marriage, extending liability to situations where individuals are taken abroad to be married or where people lacking the mental capacity to consent are involved. Since 2023, compelling a child under eighteen to marry, even without overt threats, is also treated as a criminal offence (Hampshire, Isle of Wight, Portsmouth and Southampton (HIPS), n.d.)

In South Asia, including India, forced marriages are deeply tied to patriarchal and caste based structures that prioritise family honour over individual choice. Girls are often withdrawn from education, isolated, and subjected to repeated sexual violence, forced pregnancies, and ongoing abuse within marriage. For many victims, disclosure is rare, given the stigma and the fear of ostracisation, leaving them trapped in cycles of silence and subjugation.

3.6.2 Honour Based Violence and Its Social Roots

Honour-based violence is defined as violence, threats, or coercion committed to protect or defend the perceived honour of a family or community. Such acts are typically triggered when women transgress social norms, whether by rejecting arranged marriages, choosing partners across caste or religious boundaries, or asserting autonomy in their personal lives (Hampshire, Isle of Wight, Portsmouth and Southampton (HIPS), n.d.). The ideological foundation of these crimes lies in patriarchal traditions where women's sexuality and choices are controlled to safeguard lineage, inheritance, and community prestige. Historical practices such as *karo kari* in Sindh or *siyahkari* in Baluchistan illustrate how women accused of dishonour were stigmatised and killed to erase shame (Nisha et al., 2024).

In India, the caste system further intensifies the phenomenon. Inter-caste or inter-religious marriages, particularly those involving an upper-caste woman and a lower-caste man, are often viewed as dishonourable and invite violent reprisals. Social institutions such as *khap* panchayats in northern India continue to sanction violence, undermining state law and constitutional protections for individual liberty.

3.6.3 Contemporary Indian Context

Despite constitutional safeguards, honour killings remain a pressing concern in India. According to National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) data presented in Parliament, a total of 29,193 murder cases were reported in 2020, 29,272 in 2021, and 28,522 in 2022 across the country. Within these numbers, cases of murder specifically linked to “honour killings” accounted for 25 in 2020, 33 in 2021, and 18 in 2022 (Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India, 2025). While numerically smaller compared to overall murders, these crimes carry immense symbolic weight because they target individuals for exercising their basic rights to choice and autonomy. States such as Haryana, Punjab, Madhya Pradesh, and Jharkhand consistently reported multiple cases, showing that the practice is entrenched in regions where caste and community codes exert significant control.

The brutality of these incidents is evident in recent cases. In Kalaburagi, Karnataka, 18-year-old Kavita Kollura was strangled and burnt by her father and relatives for pursuing an inter-caste relationship, with police attributing the murder to long standing caste enmity (Times of India, 2025). In August 2025, in Darbhanga, Bihar, 25-year-old medical student Rahul Kumar was shot dead by his Brahmin father-in-law for marrying his daughter, despite state schemes promoting inter-caste marriages (Bhelari, 2025). These incidents illustrate how notions of family honour continue to override constitutional guarantees of equality and personal liberty.

3.6.4 State and Institutional Responses

The Indian state has attempted to respond to these crimes with both preventive and remedial measures. Following a 2018 Supreme Court judgement, the Ministry of Home Affairs issued directives to states to identify vulnerable districts, act quickly on reports of honour crimes, and ensure security for threatened couples. NCRB data disaggregated by motive has further allowed policymakers to track the persistence of honour killings within overall murder statistics (Ministry of Home Affairs,

Government of India, 2025). Additional initiatives such as Women Help Desks in police stations, One Stop Centres for survivors of violence, and helplines (181 and 112) have been established to provide immediate assistance.

Nevertheless, the persistence of honour killings highlights the gap between law and practice. These crimes reveal the enduring strength of caste, kinship, and patriarchal norms that continue to dictate women's lives. While overall murders may be declining slightly, the persistence of honour-based killings underscores the deep cultural resistance to change, where young people asserting autonomy in marriage continue to face lethal consequences.

3.7 Discrimination and Violence Against LGBTQI+ People

3.7.1 Global Perspectives

Across the world, LGBTQI+ communities continue to face systemic discrimination, harassment, and violence. The United Nations highlights that in at least 77 countries, consensual same-sex relations remain criminalised, with punishments ranging from imprisonment to the death penalty in five countries (UN, 2023). These laws legitimise homophobia and transphobia, creating a culture of impunity for hate crimes. LGBTQI+ people are singled out for physical attacks, sexual assault, torture, and killings, often with no legal protection. Intersectionality worsens this reality, as racial, ethnic, and religious minorities within the LGBTQI+ spectrum are disproportionately exposed to violence and exclusion.

The European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights' *EU LGBTIQ Survey III* (2023) provides stark evidence of persistent inequality. Although EU law prohibits discrimination in employment and related spheres, 36% of respondents reported experiencing discrimination in daily life. Employment (19%), education (15%), healthcare (14%), and housing (12%) remain major areas of exclusion. Violence has escalated: 14% reported being attacked in the past five years, with trans and intersex individuals facing the highest risks. Harassment remains widespread, with over half (54%) experiencing at least one incident in the preceding year. Alarming, very few reported cases to authorities, citing distrust, normalisation of violence, and fear of further victimisation.

3.7.2 Indian Realities

India presents a complex picture of progress and setbacks. While the Navtej Singh Johar judgment of 2018 decriminalised same-sex relations, lived experiences show that LGBTQI+ people remain vulnerable. A 2024 study across six Indian cities revealed that 78.7% of gay men and 44% of bisexual men faced violence, with Delhi recording the highest prevalence of sexual violence against men who have sex with men (44%), followed closely by Kolkata, where 80% reported some form of violence (Butani, 2024). Caste and religion intersect significantly with sexuality: OBC respondents (84.1%) and SC/ST respondents (71.6%) reported much higher levels of violence than upper-caste counterparts, while Muslim respondents were 2.6 times more likely to experience sexual violence compared to Hindus.

For lesbians and bisexual women, violence often originates within the family. Research shows that queer women are subjected to forced marriages, home confinement, denial of education, and coerced psychiatric treatment when they assert their identities (Dagras, 2021). They may also face eviction from landlords and harassment from neighbours, leaving them vulnerable to both economic and social exclusion. Groups such as Sahayatrika in Kerala have documented how lesbian and transgender women are punished through isolation, financial deprivation, and forced institutionalisation, reflecting the invisibility and denial of same-sex relationships in Indian society.

3.7.3 Legal and Institutional Gaps

Despite legal recognition of LGBTQI+ rights, significant gaps persist. The *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS)*, which replaced the Indian Penal Code in 2024, failed to include provisions on rape of men or transgender people, stripping away protections that existed under the IPC. This omission has left male and trans survivors of sexual violence without legal recourse. Furthermore, police often fail to protect queer individuals, instead advising reconciliation with abusive families, thereby reinforcing cycles of violence (CJP, 2023). For lesbians and bisexual women, the *Domestic Violence Act* excludes same-sex couples, further narrowing avenues for redress.

3.7.4 Vulnerability of Transgender People

Transgender persons face compounded marginalisation. A 2016 study by the National Institute of Epidemiology found that law enforcement agencies themselves were frequent perpetrators of violence (Times of India, 2016). In healthcare, trans and queer persons often face ridicule, denial of treatment, and “conversion practices” (Smallens, 2025). The EU survey’s finding that one in three LGBTQI+ respondents contemplated suicide in the previous year resonates strongly in India, where stigma, discrimination, and lack of supportive services exacerbate mental health crises.

3.7.5 Structural and Social Barriers

The study (Dagras, 2021) emphasises how systemic heterosexism and lack of social recognition underpin the marginalisation of LGBTQI+ people. Beyond overt violence, queer individuals face discrimination in schools, workplaces, and housing. Many are forced into heterosexual marriages, while others conceal their identities to avoid harassment or job loss. Lesbian women, in particular, suffer a double burden of gender and sexuality based discrimination, often being pathologised by doctors or subjected to forced psychiatric treatment. Cultural taboos, moral policing, and inadequate sex education further perpetuate hostility, while homophobic slurs and bullying normalise abuse from a young age.

3.7.6 Towards Equality

Civil society has taken steps to fill institutional voids. The NHRC has urged awareness campaigns around the NALSA (2014) and Navtej Singh Johar (2018) rulings and called for police sensitisation. NGOs across India are working to provide legal advocacy, shelters, and community networks. Yet, as activists like Harish Iyer argue, decriminalisation is only a starting point. Embedding equality requires transforming social attitudes, strengthening legal protections, and ensuring that LGBTQI+ individuals can live with dignity and safety.

In India, the struggle for LGBTQI+ rights highlights the paradox of formal legal recognition alongside deep-rooted social prejudice. While the law has evolved, the persistence of violence, institutional neglect, and family-based oppression underscores that equality remains elusive for many. For those at the intersections of caste, class, religion, and sexuality, the risks are even greater, demanding a more inclusive and intersectional response.

3.8 Institutional Gender-Based Violence: Custody and Healthcare

Custodial gender-based violence (GBV) is one of the starkest violations of human rights, occurring in spaces that should guarantee justice and protection. The recent 2024 Bhubaneswar case demonstrates this reality in chilling detail. A woman unlawfully detained while attempting to lodge a complaint was physically assaulted, verbally abused, and sexually harassed by police officers. Dragged by her hair, tied with her own clothing, and humiliated through sexualised violence, her ordeal illustrates how custodial institutions often transform into sites of domination where state power is weaponised against the vulnerable. Instead of finding redress, women who approach law enforcement risk further victimisation by those entrusted with their safety (Barik, 2024).

National patterns reveal the scale of the crisis. Between 2017 and 2022, 275 cases of custodial rape were registered in India, with Uttar Pradesh accounting for the highest number at 92, followed by Madhya Pradesh. Offenders include police personnel, jail staff, members of the armed forces, and public servants. Women's rights advocates argue that such crimes are driven by patriarchal norms, inadequate gender sensitivity training, and systemic impunity. As Poonam Muttreja of the Population Foundation of India observed, custodial settings "provide unique opportunities for abuse, with state agents often using their power to force or coerce sexual access." Survivors of trafficking or domestic violence, ostensibly placed in custody for protection, often face sexual violence under the guise of state care (PTI, 2024).

Testimonies reinforce these concerns. Pallabi Ghosh of the Nguvu Collective has documented accounts of survivors alleging rape and assault by police officers, stressing that victim-blaming attitudes, even among junior staff and women constables, are normalised. Survivors also face systemic barriers to justice: unless they name individual perpetrators, complaints are frequently disregarded, leaving them exposed to further intimidation and silencing. These obstacles perpetuate a cycle where reporting is discouraged, and impunity thrives (PTI, 2024).

Custodial violence is not limited to police stations. Hospitals, remand homes, and other institutions reflect similar patterns of abuse. Bhattacharya et al. (2025) note that women in Indian hospitals often experience neglect, inappropriate physical contact, discriminatory attitudes, and breaches of privacy. Women from marginalised

communities face particular vulnerability due to systemic inefficiencies and entrenched hierarchies. The lack of privacy protocols, overburdened facilities, and inadequate gender sensitivity training among healthcare providers create conditions where GBV is pervasive yet under-reported. Consequences include psychological trauma, diminished trust in healthcare, and avoidance of medical treatment. In effect, hospitals mirror the failures of custodial policing, reproducing harm rather than safeguarding rights.

Reforms such as the creation of Women's Police Stations (WPSs) were designed to address distrust and provide safer avenues for reporting violence. However, evidence suggests their impact has been uneven. A study found that WPSs often fail to serve women from lower classes and marginalised castes. Despite increased reporting rates, outcomes remain bleak due to systemic backlogs: over 32% of reported cases of violence against women in 2016 were not investigated within the year, while nearly 90% of such cases in 2017 remained pending in courts (Sikri et al., 2021). These findings illustrate that institutional barriers extend beyond policing to the broader justice system, where delays effectively deny survivors meaningful recourse.

International research shows similar trends. Evans et al. (2024) document how trans and gender-diverse individuals in custody across the US, UK, Canada, and Australia face misgendering, denial of medical care, and widespread harassment. Staff are frequently perpetrators of abuse, and protective policies are inconsistently applied. Wilson et al. (2017) likewise highlight that sexual minority youth are disproportionately represented in US juvenile custody and report alarmingly high rates of sexual victimisation by peers and staff. Both studies underscore that custodial institutions magnify vulnerability, reinforcing social inequalities and policing non-conforming identities through violence.

Taken together, the Bhubaneswar case, NCRB data, and international studies highlight a common conclusion: custodial GBV is structural, not incidental. It arises from unchecked institutional power, patriarchal hierarchies, and systemic neglect of accountability. Addressing it requires more than disciplining individual officers. Structural reforms, independent oversight of custodial facilities, mandatory gender sensitivity and accountability training for law enforcement and healthcare staff, and accessible survivor-centered reporting mechanisms are essential. Without such measures, custodial GBV will remain a persistent stain on the promise of justice and state protection.

4 Impact of GBV

Gender-based violence (GBV) inflicts profound and multifaceted harm across individual, familial, and societal levels. Victims often endure severe physical injuries, unwanted pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections, and long-lasting mental health disorders such as depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Public Administration Institute, 2024; The Guardian, 2025).

Beyond personal suffering, GBV imposes significant socioeconomic burdens, including lost productivity, job loss, increased healthcare expenses, and educational disruptions—costing nations between 1.2% and 2% of GDP (Public Administration Institute, 2024; World Bank Group, n.d.). The repercussions also span generations, as children exposed to GBV are at heightened risk of adverse behavioural, emotional, and developmental outcomes, undermining family stability and perpetuating cycles of violence (Public Administration Institute, 2024).

At the structural level, GBV strains legal and health systems, erodes social cohesion, and reinforces systemic inequities that limit access to justice, healthcare, and economic opportunities (Montesanti & Thurston, 2015; Public Administration Institute, 2024). Simultaneously, the civic and political dimensions of GBV are starkly evident in the unique nature of public participation, citizenship, and visibility of survivors in social and political arenas. The sections that follow will explore these dimensions in detail.

4.1 Health Consequences of Gender-Based Violence

Evidence from diverse contexts shows that GBV, particularly intimate partner violence (IPV), is strongly associated with a wide range of health problems. These extend beyond acute injuries to chronic, recurrent, and often hidden conditions affecting sexual and reproductive health, neurological functioning, stress-related illness, and mental health outcomes.

4.1.1 Sexual and Reproductive Health

Gynaecological morbidity is among the most consistently documented health consequences of GBV. Campbell et al. (2002) reported that survivors of IPV had 50%–70% higher rates of gynaecological problems compared to non-abused women, including vaginal infections, bleeding, pelvic pain, painful intercourse, and urinary tract infections.

Importantly, both physically and sexually abused women exhibited elevated risk, though sexual abuse was associated with a higher number of concurrent gynaecological symptoms.

Suri et al.'s (2022) analysis of Indian survey data provides further nuance by linking domestic violence to reproductive decision-making and adverse outcomes. Women experiencing violence had 35.5% higher odds of undergoing a medical termination of pregnancy, a result that was statistically significant. These abortions were frequently associated with severe complications, suggesting that violence not only increases unintended pregnancies but also channels women towards unsafe or high risk medical procedures. In contexts where access to safe abortion services is limited, this represents a critical reproductive health risk that compounds the burden of IPV.

Closson et al. (2024) similarly found that IPV exposure among African women was strongly linked to heightened HIV risk and reproductive complications, while Yan et al. (2024) reported elevated rates of sexually transmitted infections among lesbian, gay, and bisexual adults in Hong Kong exposed to IPV. These studies highlight the structural vulnerabilities of marginalised groups, where violence interacts with stigma and poor health system access to produce disproportionate reproductive health harms.

4.1.2 Neurological and Stress-Related Health

Campbell et al. (2002) identified significant increases in central nervous system (CNS) complaints among abused women, including headaches, fainting, seizures, and chronic back pain. Stress-related conditions such as digestive problems, loss of appetite, abdominal pain, and hypertension were also elevated. These findings underscore how prolonged exposure to fear and trauma manifests physically through chronic stress responses, affecting neurological and gastrointestinal systems.

Henry et al. (2018) added that injuries from IPV are often concentrated on the face, head, chest, and abdomen, creating pathways for long-term neurological consequences such as traumatic brain injury and chronic pain syndromes. Repeated trauma also contributes to cardiovascular risk, which identified hypertension and immune suppression as common sequelae. The latter may help explain the higher

prevalence of viral infections such as colds and flu among survivors, as stress and trauma can depress immune functioning.

4.1.3 Broader Physical Health

Beyond specific clusters of symptoms, survivors report worse general health status. Campbell et al. (2002) found that abused women were significantly less likely to rate their health as excellent and more likely to describe it as poor or fair. These differences reflect the cumulative burden of multiple conditions rather than a single identifiable illness. WHO (2021) also emphasised that GBV is linked to unintended pregnancies, complications during pregnancy, unsafe abortions, and maternal mortality, positioning violence as a significant driver of global health inequities.

4.1.4 Mental Health Outcomes

The psychological toll of GBV is substantial and often persistent. Campbell et al. (2002) noted that chronic stress-related symptoms overlap with psychological trauma, suggesting that mental health consequences are both direct and embodied. Survivors commonly experience depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), with some studies documenting heightened risk of suicidal ideation and attempts.

Suri et al. (2022) highlighted that while PTSD and anxiety are common, depression often mediates the relationship between GBV and suicidal ideation, particularly in low-resource contexts. This mediation pathway underscores the importance of recognising depression not only as a common outcome of violence but also as a mechanism linking violence to suicide risk. Similarly, Patel and colleagues, examining Indian slum communities, found that women experiencing GBV in conjunction with trauma events were significantly more likely to report suicidal thoughts, with depressive symptoms explaining much of this association (Patel et al., 2021).

Henry et al. (2018) drew attention to the cyclical nature of this relationship: survivors with depression or PTSD may be more vulnerable to further victimisation due to diminished coping resources and social isolation, while repeated victimisation worsens psychiatric symptoms, creating a reinforcing cycle of violence and mental ill-health.

Closson et al. (2024) and Yan et al. (2024) further demonstrated that mental health effects are shaped by structural inequalities. Among African women, IPV correlated with high rates of depressive symptoms

and barriers to accessing mental health care, while in Hong Kong, lesbian, gay, and bisexual adults exposed to IPV reported poorer mental health and lower health related quality of life. These findings emphasise how minority stress and stigma intensify the psychological consequences of violence.

4.1.5 Integrated Burden

The combined physical and psychological sequelae of GBV reveal its role as a complex, multi-system health determinant. Survivors frequently present with overlapping gynecological, neurological, and stress-related symptoms alongside depression, PTSD, and anxiety. Campbell et al. (2002) argued that these recurrent and diffuse health complaints often go unrecognised as consequences of IPV, leading to underdiagnosis in primary care. Without sensitive screening, clinicians may treat symptoms in isolation, missing the underlying link to violence. Subsequent research supports this point, showing that survivors often remain underserved due to fragmented care systems and limited integration of GBV into health services.

4.2 Economic and Educational Consequences of Gender Based Violence

4.2.1 Macroeconomic Impacts

GBV generates measurable macroeconomic costs by constraining women's participation in the labour force and depressing aggregate productivity. Ouedraogo and Stenzel (2021), analysing African data, found that a 1% rise in women's exposure to violence led to up to an 8% reduction in local economic activity. This reduction was mediated primarily through women's withdrawal from employment, either due to direct restrictions imposed by partners or because of health burdens that limited productivity. The effect was most pronounced in resource-dependent economies and in contexts lacking legal protections against violence, demonstrating that the economic consequences of GBV are exacerbated by weak institutional frameworks.

Complementary estimates from the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) suggest that violence costs the EU 366 billion Euros annually, with intimate partner violence alone accounting for nearly half. Lost output represents about 14% of this figure, but the more significant costs stem from survivors' health consequences and the diversion of public resources into justice and social support services (European Institute for

Gender Equality (EIGE), 2021). Together, these findings illustrate that GBV drains both private and public resources, reinforcing poverty cycles and undermining long term development.

4.2.2 Everyday Economic Violence

Beyond macro indicators, GBV manifests in direct economic exploitation. Sarac and Odabas (2025) have conceptualised economic violence as a distinct dimension of GBV encompassing coerced debt, income sabotage, and control over resources. By undermining financial independence, perpetrators entrench dependency, which in turn reduces women's bargaining power and exit options. Accounts from India during the COVID-19 lockdown highlighted how such practices adapted to digital banking: women reported partners seizing control of online accounts, withholding household funds, and exploiting dowry and marital assets. These mechanisms not only reduced women's immediate access to income but also produced long-term exclusion from financial institutions through coerced debt and damaged credit histories (Chowbey, 2023).

The feminisation of poverty is therefore both a cause and consequence of GBV. As the Council of Europe notes, women disproportionately occupy insecure labour sectors, heightening susceptibility to job loss when violence disrupts attendance or performance. Paradoxically, evidence also shows that women's economic empowerment, when not supported by broader shifts in gender norms, can trigger violence driven by perceived threats to male status (Council of Europe, n.d.). Thus, economic participation is not a guaranteed protective factor unless coupled with changes in social structures and enforcement of rights.

4.2.3 Educational Access and School Related Violence

School-related GBV (SRGBV) is a key pathway through which violence constrains educational attainment and fuels intergenerational inequality. Evidence from South Africa, Ethiopia, and multi-country consultations with girls highlights that both the threat and the experience of violence significantly shape school participation.

The Girls' Vision for Education consultation, conducted by the Malala Fund in 2024, revealed that fear of harassment on the way to school was among the most cited barriers to education across 30 countries. Girls described "creepy strange guys" staring or harassing them during commutes, which deterred attendance and created a climate of exhaustion

and fear. Sexual harassment by male peers and teachers, alongside inadequate facilities such as unsafe toilets, was also reported as a persistent deterrent to staying in school. Importantly, these insights emerged unprompted, underscoring the severity of SRGBV in shaping girls' educational experiences. Unsafe travel routes, bullying, and school-based harassment collectively drive dropout rates and reinforce restrictive gender norms, as girls internalise risks associated with public visibility (Mann, 2024).

In South Africa, Chitsamatanga and Rembe (2020) documented how SRGBV persists despite legal safeguards, manifesting as bullying, corporal punishment, and sexual abuse. Both girls and boys reported victimisation, but consequences were disproportionately severe for girls, including violation of dignity, compromised health, and heightened exposure to HIV/AIDS. The study stressed that unchecked impunity normalises violence in schools, with long term effects including absenteeism, reduced academic performance, and school withdrawal. Proposed remedies included embedding SRGBV prevention into teacher training, increasing anonymous reporting mechanisms, and allocating adequate resources to support survivors.

4.2.4 Empirical Evidence from Ethiopia

Beyene et al. (2021) provide quantitative evidence on the educational effects of GBV among 1,199 Ethiopian high school girls. More than half (54.9%) reported lifetime experiences of some form of GBV, with perpetrators including family members, peers, boyfriends, and teachers. Educational consequences were pronounced: 36.1% of survivors of sexual violence reported poor academic performance, 34.6% reported absenteeism, and 28.9% had dropped out of school. These educational outcomes were intertwined with physical and psychological sequelae such as genital injuries, unusual vaginal discharge, self-blame, and anxiety. Notably, most cases went unreported to authorities, reflecting stigma and fear of retaliation. The study highlights how GBV simultaneously undermines health and educational trajectories, creating complex disadvantages.

4.2.5 Educational Barriers and Intergenerational Impact

Economic abuse is closely linked with restrictions on women's access to education and skills development. The Council of Europe (n.d.) notes that socioeconomic deprivation, such as denying access to schooling

or paid work, operates as both a cause and a consequence of GBV. Denial of education creates long-term economic dependence, reducing women's ability to exit abusive relationships.

At the household level, a study showed that GBV constrains young women's empowerment through restrictions on mobility, decision-making, and access to resources. The SAWERA study (Mehra et al., 2023) of married youth in India found that women without decision-making power faced more than double the odds of experiencing physical or sexual violence. Conversely, greater economic resources and mobility were protective factors that lowered the risk of abuse. This dynamic illustrates how education and empowerment function as both outcomes and determinants of GBV.

Educational deprivation has broader intergenerational implications. Economic violence against women often translates into limited resources for children's education, especially for girls, perpetuating cycles of dependency and reinforcing gendered poverty. Evidence from India and Europe shows that when women lack financial autonomy, household expenditures on children's schooling are deprioritised, resulting in higher dropout rates and restricted opportunities.

4.3 Intergenerational and Structural Impacts of Gender-Based Violence

4.3.1 Transmission Across Generations

The impacts of GBV are not limited to direct survivors but reverberate through families, children, and communities. Research on intergenerational trauma shows that childhood exposure to abuse heightens vulnerability to victimisation and perpetration later in life, creating repeating cycles of harm. Salter et al. (2025), drawing on case studies of two Australian grandmothers, demonstrated how abuse experienced in childhood influenced adult victimisation and subsequently affected children and grandchildren. They highlight dissociation as a central mechanism: survivors cope by distancing themselves from trauma, while communities and institutions reinforce collective silencing. This interaction sustains environments where violence is normalised and transmitted across generations.

Maternal and infant health provides a critical entry point for understanding these cycles. A birth cohort study in Vietnam found that women who experienced childhood maltreatment and prenatal intimate partner violence (IPV) were nearly twice as likely to suffer poor mental health during pregnancy and up to 3.5 times more likely to give birth to infants with complications such as low birth weight or preterm delivery (Phuc et al., 2021). Pathways included adverse childhood experiences, neighbourhood disorder, and lack of partner support, showing how early exposure interacts with social environments to produce intergenerational vulnerabilities.

Children of survivors are also more likely to experience emotional, behavioural, and educational difficulties. A population-based study in New Zealand showed that parental exposure to violence during both childhood and adulthood was associated with the highest prevalence of children's school difficulties, including absenteeism and poor academic performance, as well as emotional behavioural problems (Hashemi et al., 2022). Where parents had childhood exposure alone, risks for children were lower, indicating that cumulative exposure across a parent's life course amplifies harm. These findings underscore that intergenerational cycles are not inevitable but are intensified by repeated or overlapping experiences of violence.

Adolescence represents another stage where intergenerational effects are visible. Exposure to interparental violence influences beliefs about conflict and intimate relationships. Temple et al. (2013) found that adolescents who witnessed violence at home were more likely to perpetrate dating violence themselves, though patterns differed by gender: boys were especially influenced by mother-to-father violence, while girls were influenced by both directions of interparental aggression. Importantly, these effects were mediated by attitudes towards condoning violence, highlighting the role of social norms in shaping transmission. Thus, intergenerational impacts are expressed not only in health and educational outcomes but also in the reproduction of violent behaviours.

4.3.2 Structural Burdens on Health and Social Systems

The intergenerational nature of GBV contributes to its profound structural burden on health, legal, and social systems. Survivors face elevated risks of chronic physical and reproductive health problems, including sexually transmitted infections, unintended pregnancies, and

pregnancy complications (OECD, 2023). They also have higher rates of depression, panic disorders, and post-traumatic stress disorder, with IPV survivors facing up to a sevenfold risk of PTSD and a threefold risk of anxiety and depression (OECD, 2023). These conditions create sustained demand for health systems through repeated emergency visits, ongoing treatment, and mental health care (OECD, 2023). Children exposed to violence add to this burden, requiring paediatric, psychological, and social interventions, which stretch service capacity.

Legal and social services also carry significant costs. Survivors often rely on shelters, counseling, and judicial recourse, while perpetrators' controlling behaviours increase victims' dependence on public services (OECD, 2023). Shame and stigma discourage reporting, forcing many survivors into prolonged cycles of informal coping that eventually spill into formal systems when crises escalate (OECD, 2023). Communities are indirectly affected through diminished trust in institutions and reduced social participation of survivors, weakening civic cohesion.

4.3.3 Economic Costs and National Development

Economic analyses further reveal the structural scale of GBV. As mentioned earlier, GBV costs countries between 1% and 2% of GDP annually, reflecting lost productivity, reduced labour supply, and service expenditures (Public Administration Institute, 2024; World Bank Group, n.d.). In the European Union, annual costs are estimated at 366 billion Euros, with IPV accounting for nearly half. Of this, 14% relates to lost economic output, 21% to justice and service provision, and the largest share to physical and emotional harm (OECD, 2023). In the United States, IPV costs are estimated at USD 3.6 trillion annually (OECD, 2023), while in Canada lifetime income losses linked to GBV total USD 334 billion (OECD, 2023).

Similar findings are reported in Latin America and the Caribbean, where GBV reduces women's labour supply and worsens child health outcomes (OECD, 2023). New Zealand estimated the 2020 costs of sexual violence at NZD 6.9 billion, largely borne by individuals and families (OECD, 2023), while Switzerland estimated IPV costs at CHF 164 million annually, equivalent to the budget of a medium-sized city (OECD, 2023).

These figures demonstrate that GBV undermines human capital formation and long-term growth. By restricting survivors' educational and employment opportunities and perpetuating intergenerational

disadvantages, GBV entrenches inequality and erodes developmental gains (OECD, 2023). Structural impacts are therefore not only financial but also social, as survivors' exclusion from civic and political life reduces representational diversity and weakens democratic participation (OECD, 2023).

4.3.4 Cycles of Harm and Systemic Response

Intergenerational and structural impacts of GBV are closely linked. Trauma transmitted across generations compounds the demand on health, education, and justice systems, while the structural costs of GBV reflect the accumulation of these individual and familial harms at societal scale. Children who witness or experience violence often face compromised educational trajectories and reduced economic opportunities, which perpetuate cycles of poverty and inequality. At the same time, states bear the financial and institutional burden of responding to recurring cases, highlighting the need for systemic prevention.

The OECD (2023) argues that calculating the costs of GBV can provide policymakers with a rationale to prioritise prevention and survivor-centered governance. While the human rights case for eliminating violence is paramount, its intergenerational and structural consequences show that GBV is also a fundamental barrier to sustainable development. Addressing it requires integrated responses across health, justice, and economic sectors that not only support survivors but also disrupt transmission to future generations.

4.4 Political and Civic Impact

4.4.1 Defining Violence Against Women in Political Life

The United Nations defines violence against women in political life as “any act of gender based violence, or threat thereof, that is likely to cause physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering and is directed against a woman in political life solely because she is a woman, or that affects women disproportionately” (UNDP & UN Women, 2018). This applies to all women in politics, including elected and appointed officials, candidates, civil servants, advisors, and activists. It is understood as a continuum of harm, encompassing sexist remarks, degrading behaviour, sexual harassment, psychological aggression, physical violence, and symbolic violence such as the reification of women (UNDP & UN Women, 2018).

Two elements distinguish this violence from what men in politics may experience. First, it is gender-motivated: women are targeted because they are women, with the purpose of reinforcing male domination of political space (Bardall, 2011). Second, it manifests in gendered forms, such as sexist insults, threats of rape, and questioning of competence based on femininity (UN Women, 2018). Violence against women in politics (VAWP) thus operates as a mechanism of control, undermining women's access to, and permanence in, political life. When it occurs within parliaments or public institutions, VAWP undermines the legitimacy of these bodies and strikes at the foundations of democracy itself (UNDP & UN Women, 2018).

4.4.2 Magnitude and Forms of Political Violence

The scope of VAWP is extensive. The Inter-Parliamentary Union (2016) surveyed women parliamentarians globally and found that 85% had experienced psychological violence, nearly 25% had been physically assaulted, 14.5% had suffered physical violence, and 6% reported sexual aggression while in office. Among female parliamentary employees, 40% reported sexual violence from MPs or colleagues, and half experienced sexual harassment. Such statistics show how violence pervades institutional hierarchies, eroding women's ability to work in safe environments.

Online spaces magnify this hostility. A UK study found that 86% of abusive tweets directed at MPs targeted women, with intersectional identities such as race, age, or sexual orientation exacerbating abuse (Ward & McLoughlin, 2020). This has chilling effects: women withdraw from public debate, censor themselves online, or leave politics altogether. The normalisation of such abuse signals to aspiring women leaders that political life is unsafe, discouraging new generations from entering public service.

4.4.3 Regional Dimensions and the Normalisation of Violence

In South Asia, violence has long been embedded in political life. The UN Women–Asia-Pacific (2014) study of India, Nepal, and Pakistan found that both candidates and voters routinely face threats, intimidation, and violence during elections. For women, these practices intersect with entrenched patriarchal norms that masculinise politics and portray it as a “dirty” domain unsuitable for women. Women politicians, particularly first-generation entrants, report political isolation within parties, denial of

meaningful roles, humiliation through inappropriate election symbols, and frequent harassment during campaigns.

Despite constitutional guarantees of equality, none of the three countries studied had legislation directly addressing VAWP (UN Women–Asia-Pacific, 2014). Instead, incidents are often dismissed as routine electoral violence, reinforcing a culture of silence within parties and institutions. This normalisation demonstrates how patriarchal structures sustain VAWP as a tool for policing women’s political participation and preserving male-dominated governance.

4.4.4 Consequences for Individuals and Institutions

At the individual level, VAWP generates humiliation, powerlessness, insecurity, and health consequences including anxiety, concentration difficulties, and insomnia (UNDP & UN Women, 2018). These harms directly affect women’s capacity to perform duties entrusted to them by voters. Some are forced to reduce their public visibility or abandon politics altogether.

The collective implications are even more significant. VAWP curtails women’s rights to equal participation, preventing them from contributing fully to policymaking and representation. The Inter-Parliamentary Union (2016) stresses that such violence undermines democratic legitimacy because elected officials cannot exercise their mandates in safety. UNDP & UN Women (2018) argue that violence functions as a deliberate mechanism to exclude women from political power, thereby reinforcing institutional inequalities. Over time, this erodes confidence in parliaments and political institutions, which fail to mirror the diversity of the societies they represent.

4.4.5 Policy Innovations and Democratic Safeguards

Recognising these dangers, some jurisdictions have enacted pioneering legislation. Catalonia’s Law 17/2020 amended its violence against women framework to explicitly include violence in politics, implementing recommendations from the UN, OAS, Council of Europe, and IPU. The law mandates codes of conduct against sexist speech, institutional protocols for prevention and investigation, sanctions for perpetrators, and reparation for victims. It also requires public officials and party members to undergo gender-equality training, obliges political parties to establish

equality plans, and ensures independent oversight of investigations (Verge, 2021).

Verge (2021) framed this innovation as recognition that violence against women in politics constitutes a systemic failure of democracy. By institutionalising protections, Catalonia positions itself as a European benchmark for ensuring that women’s political participation is not conditioned by gender. Such reforms highlight that addressing VAWP is not only about individual safety but also about safeguarding democratic integrity.

4.4.6 Democracy at Risk

VAWP is a direct threat to democracy because it excludes half the population from equal political participation. (UNDP & UN Women, 2018) emphasises that it is not merely a personal violation but a democratic injury: by deterring women’s engagement, it distorts representation and policymaking. It is described as a “mechanism of control” that preserves male dominance in political institutions. The Inter-Parliamentary Union (2016) warns that the widespread prevalence of harassment and violence in parliaments “undermines the foundation of democracy” by silencing elected representatives. Verge (2021) further argued that when women cannot participate freely, democracy itself fails to reflect the society it claims to serve.

In this sense, violence against women in politics is both a symptom and a driver of democratic weakness. It demonstrates how gender inequality is institutionalised in political systems and how patriarchy sustains itself through intimidation and exclusion. Unless governments and parties commit to feminist transformation as a democratic mandate (UNDP & UN Women, 2018), efforts to achieve inclusive governance will remain incomplete.

5 Institutional Addressal in India

5.1 Legal and Policy Framework

5.1.1 Rape, Sexual Assault, Sexual Violence, Sexual Abuse, Coercion, Non-Consensual act (Section 375 IPC and Section 376 IPC)

Historically, the offence of “rape” has had a narrow definition (penile-vaginal intercourse) and had marital exemptions, under the

Indian Penal Code (IPC, 1860). The major changes came into place after the public outrage in 2012 against the Delhi gang-rape (Nirbhaya) case. The government responded with the *Criminal Law (Amendment) Act* in 2013, which broadened the definition of rape, added aggravated offences, increased the terms of minimum punishments, and introduced new categories which included gang rape, custodial rape, and trafficking-related provisions (*The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*).

Since 2013, there have been further legal and policy developments which include specialised sexual offences law like the *Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act of 2012 (POCSO)*. Over the years, procedural directions from courts have also shaped investigations, medical examinations, evidence rules and victim support systems.

Section 375 IPC defines “rape” as sexual intercourse and “penetrative acts to any extent” including with objects, mouth, anus, etc., without free and voluntary consent, or with consent obtained by coercion, deception, or when the person is incapable of giving consent (*The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*).

Section 376 IPC prescribes minimum custodial terms and gradations of punishment depending on age of victim, aggravating circumstances (police/jail staff, causing grievous injury or death, repeated rape, gang rape), up to life imprisonment or, in the rarest cases, death (*The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*; Devgan, 2022).

Chart 2

Key Elements in Law Against Rape, Sexual Assault, Sexual Violence, Sexual Abuse, Coercion, Non-Consensual Act

Key Elements

1 Actus reus/penetrative sexual act:
Penetration (to any extent) of vagina, mouth, urethra or anus by penis/object/part of body or forcing the victim to engage in such acts. The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act in 2013 made "penetration to any extent" explicit.

2 Mens rea/lack of consent:
Absence of free, voluntary consent; consent obtained by force, threat, fraud, intoxication, unsoundness of mind, or when the accused induces consent by impersonation

3 Capacity
Whether the victim had capacity to consent (age/mental incapacity/intoxication) to sexual activity with a person below statutory age attracts stricter provisions. Separate, mandatory child-specific protections exist under the POCSO Act for below 18 years of age

4 Aggravating conditions
Custody/trust relationship (police, jail staff, public servant), gang conduct, causing grievous harm/death, repeat offences, or victim being a minor—these raise different variations of punishments

Source: The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013; Devgan, 2022

Hospitals must provide first aid and medical examination. Forensic sampling and DNA profiling is explicitly part of examinations. Medico-legal reports must be promptly forwarded to investigators and courts. The *Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita (BNSS)* sets timeframes and requires female examiners wherever possible and that survivor statements be recorded early by a Magistrate (preferably a woman) and may be recorded by audio-video methods.

BNSS continues the practice that trials for rape and related sexual offences be conducted in camera and, where practicable, by a woman judge or magistrate to protect survivor privacy. Publishing trial material is restricted. Many states have set up fast-track courts, and guidelines emphasising survivor support services.

The persons subject to non-consensual penetrating sexual acts, historically have been viewed as women in IPC language, but the substantive offence protects any survivor of forced non-consensual penetrative sexual violence. The law also protects persons in custodial or trust relationships which include patients, prisoners, children in institutions, etc., from abuse by those in authority (Devgan, 2022).

The historic drafting and statutory language have been gendered; in practice victims who are trans or gender non-conforming can be victims of penetrative sexual violence, but legal recognition, investigative sensitivity, and access to gender-appropriate medical and forensic services remain inconsistent. Courts and policy recommendations have urged for inclusive interpretation, but implementation gaps persist.

Under Section 376 IPC, the basic punishment for rape is rigorous imprisonment not less than 10 years, which may be extended to life imprisonment, and a fine. Aggravated or special categories like rape of a survivor less than 16 or 12 years of age is given a minimum 20-year term, possibly life or death if it results in the death/vegetative state of the survivor. Gang rape carries heavy minimum punishment (20 years to life), custodial rape and rape by persons in positions of trust carry minimum 10 or more years. Repeat offenders may face life imprisonment or death in extreme cases. BNSS mirrors these gradations in its sections on sexual offences (Devgan, 2022).

Subsequent policy changes were made in judicial interpretations on forensic procedures and the two-finger test ban, free emergency care to survivors, and minor legislative amendments in other linked laws like

trafficking provisions, *POCSO*, etc. Many reform proposals have continued, including debates about criminalising marital rape, but there has been no nationwide repeal or full criminalisation of marital rape in cohabiting marriages as of 2025 (*The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*).

BNSS (2023) is a consolidation of criminal procedure provisions (procedural law).

- Section 64 *BNSS* discusses rape.
- Section 64(2) investigates rape by police/public servant/custodial staff or by person in trust/authority.
- Section 65 has provisions for rape on minors with heavier minimum punishments.
- Section 66 talks about rape causing death/vegetative state.

BNSS prescribes in-camera trial for rape and related sections and suggests, where practicable, woman judges/magistrates to conduct trials and recording of witness statements by Magistrates as early as possible. *BNSS* sets out the duty and timeframes for medical examination of victims and for examination of accused where relevant, and medical reports must be prepared and forwarded promptly (*Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023*).

However, even after the policy changes with *BNSS*, investigation and conviction gaps still remain. Under-reporting, investigatory delays, poor evidence handling, and low conviction rates in many states remain systemic problems. Coordination between forensic labs, police, and prosecution is uneven (Paliwal, 2024).

The IPC still largely excludes forcible sex within marriage unless the couple is judicially separated in certain rare/extreme circumstances. Parliamentary and public debates continue but no uniform criminalisation of marital rape, except for cohabiting wives, has been enacted at the national level as of 2025. This remains a major normative and protection gap (Paliwal, 2024).

Statutory language, police practices, forensic processes, and medical facilities are yet to be consistently gender inclusive. Survivors who are trans or non-binary often face discrimination, mis-gendering, and barriers to appropriate medical or legal care. Judicial instructions and some guidelines urge inclusion, but lags in implementation by Fast-track courts, victim support schemes, forensic capacity and shelter services exist

but are patchy across states; rural and poor survivors face the highest barriers (Goyal, 2024).

5.1.2 Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956 (ITPA)(Sections 359–369 IPC and Sections 370–374 IPC)

The *ITPA* originated as the *Suppression of Immoral Traffic in Women and Girls Act, 1956*, enacted after India accepted the *UN Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic in Persons (1949)*. It was renamed and amended in 1986 as the *Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act*, with broadened scope beyond women and girls to include men and trans persons (Kotiswaran, 2018).

Sections 359–369 IPC (1860) cover kidnapping and abduction and is designed to prevent abduction for marriage, illicit intercourse, slavery, or other unlawful purposes (*The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*).

Sections 370–374 IPC cover trafficking, slavery, forced labour, and unlawful compulsory service. The *2013 Criminal Law Amendment* significantly redefined Section 370 to align with the international *Palermo Protocol*, introducing detailed definitions of trafficking, recruitment, transportation, harbouring, transfer by coercion, fraud and abuse of power (United Nations, 2000) (*The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*).

ITPA (1956) primarily had provisions for anti-trafficking statute targeting organised commercial sexual exploitation. It criminalises running brothels, living on earnings of sex work, procuring/trafficking persons for prostitution, soliciting in public places, and detaining persons in brothels.

Chart 3

Key Elements in Law for Prevention of Immoral Trafficking of Women and Children

Source: Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956; IPC, 1860

The *Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act (ITPA)* incorporates survivor-centred rescue provisions, empowering magistrates and the police to rescue individuals from brothels and place them in protective homes for rehabilitation and care. It also places a strong focus on organised crime, emphasising penalties against traffickers, brothel-keepers, pimps, and exploiters rather than targeting individuals engaged in prostitution. The *ITPA* complements the IPC, where sections on kidnapping and trafficking criminalise the supply chain of exploitation, including abduction, coercion, and the sale or purchase of persons. Importantly, the post-2013 definition of trafficking has been harmonised with international standards under the UN Protocol, marking a shift in approach from viewing prostitution through a moral lens to recognising and addressing it as an issue of exploitation and human rights (National Commission for Women, 2025).

The law seeks to protect women, girls, and persons of all genders, including transgender individuals, from being trafficked, kidnapped, abducted, or forced into sexual exploitation, slavery, or bonded labour. For children under 18 years, it provides stricter safeguards against sale, purchase, or trafficking for prostitution and other illicit purposes, recognising their heightened vulnerability. Although the *ITPA* was made gender-neutral after the 1986 amendments, in practice its implementation still largely assumes a cisgender female victim. As a result, transgender women and girls remain disproportionately vulnerable to trafficking and sexual exploitation, often facing systemic neglect in both rescue and rehabilitation efforts (National Commission for Women, 2025).

Under the *ITPA*, punishments vary depending on the offence: brothel-keeping is punishable with 1–3 years' imprisonment for a first offence and 2–5 years for subsequent offences; living on the earnings of prostitution carries up to 2 years' imprisonment; procuring or inducing a person into prostitution is punishable with 3–7 years, or up to life imprisonment if a child is involved; detaining someone for prostitution attracts 7 years to life imprisonment; and soliciting in public may result in up to 6 months imprisonment (National Commission for Women, 2025).

Under the Indian Penal Code (IPC), kidnapping or abduction for various purposes can result in 7 years to life imprisonment, along with fines. Section 366 IPC specifically addresses kidnapping or abduction of a woman to compel marriage or illicit intercourse, punishable with up to 10 years' imprisonment. Section 370 IPC criminalises trafficking, prescribing

rigorous imprisonment of a minimum of 7 years and up to life. Sections 372–373 IPC deals with the sale or purchase of minors for prostitution, with penalties of up to life imprisonment. Section 374 IPC addresses unlawful compulsory labour, punishable with up to 1 year’s imprisonment, a fine, or both (The Indian Penal Code, 1860).

The *ITPA* has undergone several key amendments and proposed reforms. The 1986 amendment renamed the *Suppression of Immoral Traffic in Women and Girls Act (SITA)* to the *Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act (ITPA)* with broadened protections, and included provisions against trafficking of men. The *2013 Criminal Law Amendment* expanded the definition of trafficking under Section 370 IPC, introducing aggravated forms of the offence and harsher punishments.

The proposed *Trafficking of Persons (Prevention, Protection and Rehabilitation) Bill, 2018*, sought to establish a comprehensive anti-trafficking framework with dedicated agencies, rehabilitation measures, and cross-border provisions; however, it lapsed in Parliament, and a fresh draft has been debated but not enacted as of 2025 (PRS Legislative Research, 2018). Ongoing debates critique the *ITPA* for over-criminalising sex work rather than targeting traffickers, with advocates calling for the decriminalisation of voluntary sex work while strengthening anti-trafficking measures.

The *Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita (BNSS), 2023*, consolidates procedural aspects for trafficking and kidnapping offences. It mandates time-bound investigations of sexual and trafficking offences, compulsory medical examinations for rescued victims, and recording of victim statements before a magistrate, preferably a woman. *BNSS* ensures in-camera trials and confidentiality of victim identities. Under this framework, Sections 359–369 and 370–374 IPC have been renumbered in the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 (BNS)*, and *BNSS* aligns trial and investigation procedures, including the establishment of special courts and standardised rescue protocols. Additionally, *BNSS* provides for the attachment of traffickers’ property, protection of victims during investigations, and the admissibility of audio-visual evidence (*Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023*).

As of 2025, several challenges remain in addressing trafficking under existing laws. Conviction rates remain low, with NCRB 2022 data highlighting high case pendency and limited successful prosecutions.

Survivors, particularly sex workers, frequently face criminalisation under *ITPA* solicitation provisions, while traffickers often evade prosecution. Transgender and LGBTQ+ individuals, especially trans women and girls, continue to be disproportionately targeted by traffickers, yet rehabilitation services remain largely non-inclusive. Implementation gaps are widespread, with rescue and rehabilitation homes often overcrowded, underfunded, and at times violating basic rights. Moreover, efforts to enact comprehensive anti-trafficking legislation have stagnated, leaving the *ITPA* outdated and criticised for being more moralistic than rights-based.

5.1.3 Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 (Amended 1986)(Sections 304B, 498, 498A IPC)

Dowry has been a longstanding social practice in South Asia, frequently resulting in harassment, cruelty, and even deaths of women in their marital homes. Rising reports of young brides dying by suicide or being murdered over dowry demands in the 1950s and 1960s prompted the then-Parliament to enact the *Dowry Prohibition Act* (DPA) in 1961. The initial legislation, however, imposed weak penalties and suffered from poor enforcement. In response to the increasing incidence of “dowry deaths,” major amendments were introduced in 1984 and 1986, strengthening punishments and closing legal loopholes. To further criminalise dowry-related violence, the Indian Penal Code was amended in the 1980s to include Sections 304B IPC, addressing dowry deaths, and Section 498A IPC, addressing cruelty by husbands or their relatives. Together, these provisions form the core criminal law framework against dowry-related violence (*Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005*).

The *Dowry Prohibition Act* (DPA), 1961, prohibits the giving, taking, or demanding of dowry before, during, or after marriage, and applies to both the bride’s and groom’s families. Section 304B IPC defines “dowry death,” establishing that if a woman dies under abnormal circumstances within seven years of marriage and was subjected to dowry-related cruelty or harassment shortly before her death, the husband and his relatives are presumed responsible. Sections 498 and 498A IPC address cruelty and related offences: Section 498 IPC (the older provision) deals with the enticement, abduction, or detention of a married woman with criminal intent, while Section 498A IPC, added in 1983, specifically criminalises cruelty by a husband or his relatives, including physical or mental harassment, particularly in connection with dowry demands (The Indian Penal Code, 1860).

Chart 4

Key Elements in Law for Prevention of Dowry

Key features of the dowry law framework include the presumption clause under Section 304B IPC, which shifts the burden of proof to the accused once the prosecution establishes the basic ingredients of a dowry-related death. Offences such as dowry death and cruelty are non-bailable and cognisable, requiring police to act without a magistrate's prior order. States are empowered to establish special courts to adjudicate dowry offences, ensuring focused and expedited trials. Additionally, the seven-year time frame under Section 304B provides protection for women during the early years of marriage, a period identified as particularly high-risk for dowry-related violence (National Commission for Women, Government of India, 2025).

The law primarily protects women and girl brides from harassment, cruelty, and physical or mental abuse related to dowry demands. It also safeguards them against deaths—including suicides, homicides, burns, or poisoning—that are linked to dowry, as well as economic exploitation and coercion by in-laws. Indirectly, the legislation protects the families of women, shielding them from extortion or undue pressure associated with dowry transactions.

Under the *Dowry Prohibition Act*, taking or giving dowry is punishable with up to five years' imprisonment and a fine of Rs. 15,000 or the value of the dowry, whichever is higher, while demanding dowry carries imprisonment from six months to five years along with a fine. IPC Section 304B, dealing with dowry deaths, prescribes a minimum of seven years to life imprisonment. IPC Section 498A, which addresses cruelty by a husband or his relatives, provides for imprisonment of up to three years along with a fine (The Indian Penal Code, 1860).

The *Dowry Prohibition Act*, 1961, was amended in 1984 and 1986 to expand punishments, clarify definitions, and make offences cognisable. IPC Section 304B, addressing dowry deaths, was added in 1986, while Section 498A, criminalising cruelty by husbands or relatives, was introduced in 1983. Judicial interpretations have clarified that "soon before death" under Section 304B refers to a proximate, though not necessarily immediate, period prior to the woman's death. The Supreme Court, in rulings from 2014 and 2022, cautioned against the misuse of Section 498A while reaffirming its importance for safeguarding women (Lok Sabha Un-Starred Question No 2151 to Be Answered on 29.07.2016, 2016). As of 2025, no major new dowry-specific legislation has been

introduced post-2020, though related reforms are reflected in broader criminal code changes, including the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023*.

Under the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS), 2023*, IPC provisions have been renumbered, with Sections 304B and 498A retained with equivalent provisions. The *Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita (BNSS)*, which governs procedural law, ensures time-bound investigations for offences against women, early recording of victim and family statements, in-camera trials, and protection of witnesses. Presumption clauses from the original laws have been carried forward, and dowry-related offences remain cognisable and non-bailable, with procedural safeguards in place to protect victims while ensuring a fair trial.

As of 2025, dowry-related violence continues to pose significant challenges. NCRB data from 2022 reports over 6,000 dowry deaths annually in India, with many cases likely under-reported or disguised as accidents. Conviction rates remain low, with fewer than 35% of dowry death and cruelty cases resulting in convictions, despite stringent legal provisions. Debates over the alleged misuse of Section 498A, involving false or exaggerated complaints, have led to police and court guidelines advocating cautious arrests, though women's groups argue that such measures weaken protection for genuine survivors. Culturally, dowry remains deeply entrenched, including among educated and middle-class families, limiting the law's deterrent effect. Additionally, the legal framework is primarily designed for cisgender women in marriages, leaving trans women and girls who are forced into exploitative marriages largely unprotected, highlighting a critical gap in intersectional coverage.

5.1.4 Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986 (Section 354A, 354B, 354C, 354D, 509 IPC)

The *Indecent Representation of Women Act, 1986 (IRWA)*, was enacted amid growing concerns in the 1980s over the objectification of women in advertisements, publications, paintings, films, and other media. Its primary aim was to curb the commodification of women's bodies and uphold their dignity in public spaces. Prior to this, Sections 354 and 509 IPC, dating back to 1860, criminalised assault or criminal force intended to outrage a woman's modesty, as well as words or gestures insulting her modesty. Following the 2012 Delhi gang rape (Nirbhaya case), the *Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*, expanded the legal framework by introducing Sections 354A–D IPC to specifically address sexual harassment, assault

with intent to disrobe, voyeurism, and stalking, thereby recognising and criminalising modern forms of gender-based violence (National Commission for Women, Government of India, 2025).

The *Indecent Representation of Women Act, 1986 (IRWA)* prohibits the publication, writing, painting, or any form of representation that depicts women indecently, covering advertisements, books, pamphlets, films, writings, and similar media. Under the IPC, Sections 354A–D and 509 provide specific protections against sexual harassment and related offences. Section 354A criminalises sexual harassment, including unwelcome physical contact, demands for sexual favours, showing pornography, and sexually coloured remarks. Section 354B IPC addresses assault or use of criminal force to disrobe a woman. Section 354C IPC criminalises voyeurism, defined as watching or capturing images of a woman engaged in a private act without her consent. Section 354D IPC targets stalking, including repeated following, contacting, or monitoring a woman via internet or electronic means despite her disinterest. Section 509 IPC penalises words, gestures, or acts intended to insult the modesty of a woman (The Indian Penal Code, 1860).

Chart 5

Key Elements in Law Against Indecent Representation of Women

Source: Indecent Representation of Women Act, 1986; IPC, 1860

Key features of the legal framework include the *IRWA*'s broad coverage of various media forms, such as print, paintings, figures, and advertisements, and its applicability to publishers, advertisers, and distributors. The Section 354 A-D IPC introduces gradations of offences, including sexual harassment, voyeurism, and stalking, and explicitly recognises digital and electronic harassment, particularly under Section 354D IPC on stalking. Post-2013 reforms mandate that women's statements be recorded by female officers and establish victim-friendly procedures to ensure sensitive handling of cases. Section 509 IPC serves as a broad safety net, addressing gestures, words, or acts intended to insult a woman's modesty that may not fall under the more specific harassment provisions.

These provisions protect women and girls from indecent representation in public and media under the *IRWA*, and from harassment in workplaces, streets, homes, and online spaces under IPC Sections 354A–D and 509. Although the laws primarily use gendered language, judicial and policy practice increasingly recognises trans women and girls under protections against harassment and disrobing. Beyond individual safeguards, the laws serve a collective interest by upholding the societal dignity of women as a class and shielding them from objectification.

Under the *IRWA*, a first conviction can result in up to two years' imprisonment and a fine of up to Rs.2,000, while subsequent convictions carry up to five years' imprisonment and a fine ranging from Rs.10,000 to Rs.1 lakh. Under IPC Sections 354A–D, punishments vary by offence. Section 354A (sexual harassment) prescribes up to three years' imprisonment and a fine for physical contact or demands, and up to one year plus a fine for sexually coloured remarks. Section 354B (assault to disrobe) carries three to seven years' imprisonment plus a fine. Section 354C (voyeurism) imposes one to three years' imprisonment for a first offence and three to seven years for repeat offences, along with a fine. Section 354D (stalking) provides up to three years plus a fine for a first offence and up to five years plus a fine for repeat offences. Section 509 IPC carries a penalty of up to three years' imprisonment along with a fine (The Indian Penal Code, 1860).

Recent amendments and legislative developments have sought to modernise protections under the *Indecent Representation of Women Act (IRWA)* and related IPC provisions. The 2012 *Indecent Representation of Women (Amendment) Bill* aimed to extend *IRWA*'s scope to electronic

media and the internet while introducing stricter penalties, but it lapsed in Parliament. The 2013 Criminal Law Amendment inserted IPC Sections 354A–D, expanded punishments, and addressed modern forms of sexual harassment, including digital and workplace misconduct. In 2024–2025, new bills tabled in the Rajya Sabha propose further strengthening of sexual harassment and online indecent representation laws, aligning them with the *Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023*. Judicial developments have emphasised that women’s dignity must not be trivialised, recognising that online harassment and non-consensual circulation of images, such as “revenge porn,” are punishable under Section 354C and relevant provisions of the *IT Act*.

Under the *BNSS, 2023*, procedural safeguards for offences under Sections 354, 354A–D, and 509 IPC are reinforced. *BNSS* mandates in-camera trials and requires that victim statements be recorded promptly by magistrates, preferably female officers, with the use of audio-visual recording permitted. Investigations into sexual harassment offences are to be conducted within specified time frames. The equivalent offences have been renumbered under the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS), 2023*, while preserving provisions on sexual harassment, voyeurism, stalking, and indecent acts, along with the corresponding punishments.

The legal framework has achieved notable successes. Following the 2013 amendments, harassment, stalking, and voyeurism are recognised as standalone offences, which has increased reporting and visibility of such crimes. Sections 354C and 354D explicitly address cyberstalking and non-consensual image sharing, providing survivors with legal recourse in the digital era. Institutional reforms have also improved responsiveness, with courts, universities, and workplaces better equipped to handle complaints, partly due to the concurrent implementation of the *POSH Act (2013)* alongside these IPC provisions.

As of 2025, several challenges persist in addressing indecent representation and harassment of women. Enforcement of the *IRWA* remains weak, with prosecutions rare and the law criticised for outdated definitions of “indecent representation” and a moralistic tone, leaving many instances of online indecency beyond its scope. Online harassment has surged, with cases of cyberstalking, doxxing, deepfakes, and revenge porn increasing rapidly, while enforcement struggles to keep pace with evolving technology despite Sections 354C/D IPC and the *IT Act*. Conviction rates under Sections 354A–D remain low, often due to

inadequate evidence collection and victim shaming. Cultural trivialisation persists, with street harassment (“eve-teasing”) still normalised and women frequently discouraged from filing complaints. Furthermore, trans women survivors are often excluded in practice, despite gender-neutral interpretations by courts.

5.1.5 Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971 (Amended 2021) (Sections 312, 313, 314 IPC)

Under the Indian Penal Code, 1860, abortion was largely criminalised, permitted only when necessary to save the life of the woman (Section 312–314 IPC), which drove many women to seek unsafe procedures. The Shantilal Shah Committee (1964) investigated the high maternal mortality resulting from unsafe abortions and recommended liberalisation of the law. In response, Parliament enacted the *Medical Termination of Pregnancy (MTP) Act, 1971*, allowing abortion under specified conditions by registered medical practitioners. Subsequent amendments in 2002 and 2021, along with rules issued in 2023–24, expanded the gestational limit, included unmarried women, strengthened confidentiality safeguards, and broadened the base of qualified providers authorised to perform abortions (The Medical Termination of Pregnancy (Amendment) Act, 2021).

The *Medical Termination of Pregnancy (MTP) Act, 1971*, as amended, governs the circumstances under which pregnancies may be lawfully terminated in India. It lays down the gestational limits and specific conditions, and identifies who is authorised to perform such procedures. Alongside the *MTP Act*, Sections 312–314 IPC continue to operate. Section 312 criminalises voluntarily causing a miscarriage unless it is carried out in good faith to save the life of the woman. Section 313 deals with causing miscarriage without the woman’s consent, treating it as a graver offence, while Section 314 prescribes enhanced punishment when the act of miscarriage results in the woman’s death (The Indian Penal Code, 1860).

Chart 6

Key Elements in Law for Medical Termination of Pregnancy

Source: Medical Termination of Pregnancy (MTP) Act, 1971; IPC, 1860

Important features of India's abortion law framework lie in its balance between criminalisation and exception. While the Indian Penal Code criminalises abortion, the *Medical Termination of Pregnancy (MTP) Act* creates lawful exceptions under specified conditions. A key safeguard introduced through the 2021 amendment is the confidentiality clause (Section 5A), which makes disclosure of a woman's identity punishable with imprisonment or fine. In 2022, the Supreme Court in *X v. NCT of Delhi* extended the scope of the law by recognising the right of unmarried

women to access abortion up to 24 weeks, thereby reinforcing reproductive equality (Jain, 2023). More recently, the 2023–2024 rules expanded the provider base by permitting tele-consultations in certain cases and enabling trained non-specialist doctors to carry out specified terminations, reflecting efforts to improve accessibility and reduce delays.

The *MTP Act* and related IPC provisions extend protection to multiple groups from different forms of harm. Primarily, women and girls are safeguarded from unsafe and illegal abortions by ensuring access to safe, legal procedures. Survivors of rape, incest, and minors are explicitly recognised within the extended gestation categories, reflecting their heightened vulnerability. Although the *MTP Act* uses the term “woman,” progressive judicial interpretations—such as by the Delhi High Court (2022) and Madras High Court (2023)—have extended its scope to cover transgender men and non-binary persons with reproductive capacity. In addition, the framework protects against coerced abortions under Section 313 IPC and addresses the risk of unsafe abortions leading to death under Section 314 IPC. This combined approach affirms reproductive autonomy while guarding against exploitation and harm.

The punishment framework surrounding abortion in India combines the penal provisions of the IPC with safeguards under the *MTP Act*. Under Section 312 IPC, voluntarily causing a miscarriage is punishable with up to three years’ imprisonment, or up to seven years if the woman is “quick with child.” Section 313 IPC, which deals with miscarriage without the woman’s consent, prescribes far harsher penalties—imprisonment for life or up to ten years with fine. Section 314 IPC addresses cases where death results from a miscarriage procedure, imposing ten years to life imprisonment, and in cases without the woman’s consent, the punishment may even extend to the death penalty (though this is rarely applied in practice). In addition, the *MTP Act* Section 5A, introduced in 2021, creates a separate safeguard for patient confidentiality, making its breach punishable with up to one year’s imprisonment and fine. Together, these provisions reflect both the gravity of coercive and unsafe abortions and the importance of protecting women’s privacy and dignity in reproductive healthcare.

Amendments and recent developments to the *Medical Termination of Pregnancy (MTP)* framework reflect a gradual but significant shift towards recognising reproductive autonomy in India. The 2002 amendment simplified the approval process for abortion facilities, making

services more accessible. The 2021 amendment was particularly transformative: it extended the gestational limit for termination from 20 to 24 weeks for specific categories such as survivors of rape, minors, and women with foetal abnormalities; introduced the requirement of Medical Boards for late-term abortions; and incorporated a confidentiality clause to protect patient identity. The 2023–2024 rules further expanded the list of categories eligible for termination up to 24 weeks, and emphasised capacity-building through training of providers, including tele-consultation in certain cases. Parallely, the judiciary played a crucial role in expanding rights. In *X v. NCT of Delhi* (2022), the Supreme Court held that unmarried women are equally entitled to abortion up to 24 weeks, reading reproductive choice into the ambit of Article 21 of the Constitution. Collectively, these reforms mark a clear move towards greater inclusivity, safety, and autonomy in abortion law and practice.

The *Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita* (BNSS), 2023, which replaces the Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC), introduces procedural safeguards relevant to abortion cases, especially where termination is linked to sexual offences. It mandates time-bound medical examination and reporting in cases of rape or child sexual abuse, ensuring prompt care for survivors. The law also provides for in-camera proceedings and strict confidentiality protections in trials involving abortion arising out of sexual offences under the *POCSO Act* or IPC provisions. Substantively, the offences relating to miscarriage under Section 312–314 IPC have been re-numbered and carried forward without change in the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita* (BNS), 2023, ensuring continuity of the criminal framework while integrating it into the new penal code.

Since the enactment of the *Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act* in 1971, India has witnessed significant maternal health gains, particularly through the reduction of unsafe abortion-related deaths. The legal framework has provided women with safer, regulated options, contributing to a decline in maternal mortality linked to clandestine procedures. The 2021 amendment further expanded access by allowing termination up to 24 weeks for categories such as rape survivors, minors, and cases involving severe foetal abnormalities. Importantly, the 2022 Supreme Court judgment recognised reproductive autonomy as a core component of the constitutional right to privacy and dignity, strengthening the jurisprudential foundation of abortion rights in India. The inclusion of a confidentiality clause has also empowered women to seek safe services without fear of social or legal repercussions.

However, several challenges persist in 2025. Access remains uneven, with rural women continuing to face barriers due to a shortage of trained providers and inadequately equipped facilities. The system of Medical Boards, while designed to safeguard late-term abortions, often introduces delays because of bureaucratic inefficiency, forcing women to seek judicial intervention. Social stigma and medical gatekeeping also pose serious obstacles, as some doctors refuse services despite the law. Moreover, while courts have recognised the rights of transgender men and non-binary persons with reproductive capacity, the lack of explicit statutory language leaves them at risk of exclusion in practice. Finally, despite legal reforms, unsafe abortions continue to occur, with WHO estimates indicating that a substantial proportion of abortions in India still take place outside authorised facilities, underscoring the gap between law and ground realities.

5.1.6 Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987

Sati refers to the historical practice in which a widow sacrificed (burned) herself on her husband's funeral pyre (a quantity of wood piled together for burning a dead body), a ritual often glorified as the ultimate symbol of devotion. Although it was legally prohibited under colonial rule through the *Bengal Sati Regulation of 1829*, some incidents infrequently continued in independent India. The most infamous of these was the Roop Kanwar case in Deorala, Rajasthan (1987), where an 18-year-old widow was allegedly coerced into committing sati. The widespread public glorification of her death sparked national outrage and renewed debate about entrenched patriarchal norms (Pandey, 2024). In response, Parliament enacted the *Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987* (CSPA), which not only criminalised the act of sati itself but also prohibited its glorification, recognising that cultural and social pressures played a central role in perpetuating the practice.

The *Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987*, is a central legislation that prohibits both the actual commission of sati and its glorification in any form. It lays down strict punishments for individuals who aid, abet, or encourage a woman to commit sati, as well as for those who promote or celebrate it through public ceremonies, processions, or the construction of memorials. The Act also empowers authorities to take preventive measures such as seizing temples or sites associated with sati and banning any public glorification, ensuring that the practice is not only criminalised but also socially delegitimised.

Chart 7

Key Elements in Law to Prevent Sati

The *Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987*, prescribes stringent punishments to deter both the act and promotion of sati. The commission or attempt of sati attracts the most severe penalties, including the death

penalty or life imprisonment. Similarly, anyone found abetting sati is liable for the same level of punishment. Glorification of sati, such as organising festivals, processions, or other celebratory acts, carries imprisonment of 1–7 years along with a fine of up to Rs.30,000. The Act also empowers the State to forfeit property or temples used in the promotion or glorification of sati, ensuring both preventive and punitive measures are enforced.

The *Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987* remains the governing legislation, with no major amendments introduced since its enactment. Implementation is periodically reinforced through state-level rules, such as those in Rajasthan, which provide additional guidance for enforcement. While occasional demands have arisen for stricter monitoring of sati temples and community practices that glorify sati, no national-level amendment has been tabled or enacted since 2010.

The substantive offence of sati remains governed by the *Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987*, rather than the IPC or Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS). Under the BNSS, which governs procedural law, provisions ensure in-camera trials, protection of witnesses, and the use of special courts for gender-based offences, supporting effective enforcement. Preventive measures such as prohibiting public gatherings and seizing temples or properties associated with sati continue to be enforceable through state machinery, maintaining both the punitive and deterrent intent of the Act.

Since the enactment of the *Commission of Sati (Prevention) Act, 1987*, reported cases of sati have become virtually nonexistent, reflecting the law's strong deterrent effect. State actions have successfully curtailed public glorification through bans on festivals, processions, and constructions honouring sati, while the Act itself stands as a landmark legal recognition that certain cultural practices constitute gender-based violence. Its symbolic importance reinforces the idea that the law can challenge deeply entrenched social norms that harm women.

Despite these successes, several challenges remain. Shrines and temples commemorating alleged satsis still exist in parts of Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh, and authorities sometimes tolerate them to avoid community backlash. Community-level rituals, folklore, or stories occasionally continue to glorify sati, allowing its ideological influence to persist underground. More broadly, while the practice of sati has been virtually eradicated, the cultural logic underpinning it—control over

widows' lives—continues to manifest in forms such as widow shaming, social exclusion, and property dispossession. Limited awareness among younger generations about the Act further weakens its preventive role, highlighting the need for ongoing education and vigilance to sustain the law's impact (Pandey, 2024).

5.1.7 Information Technology Act, 2000—Sections 67, 66C, 66D, 66E

The *Information Technology Act, 2000*, was India's first comprehensive cyber law, enacted to regulate electronic commerce, digital signatures, and cybercrime. With the rise of internet misuse—including pornography, online sexual harassment, identity theft, and cyber fraud—amendments in 2008 expanded its criminal provisions. Sections 67, 66C, 66D, and 66E specifically address gender-based violence and exploitation online, targeting the circulation of obscene content, digital voyeurism, and impersonation for exploitation.

Under the *IT Act*, Section 67 punishes the publication or transmission of obscene material in electronic form. Section 66C addresses identity theft, penalising the unauthorised use of another person's password, digital signature, or other credentials. Section 66D criminalises cheating by personation using computer resources, covering fraudulent impersonation, phishing, and fake profiles. Section 66E protects bodily and sexual privacy by punishing the capturing, publishing, or transmission of images of private areas without consent, addressing digital voyeurism (The Information Technology Act, 2000).

Chart 8

Key Elements in Information Technology Act, 2000

Key Elements

1 Section 66C

- Dishonest/fraudulent use of another's credentials
- Credentials being passwords, biometric data, digital signature or any other unique identification feature of a person.

2

Section 66D

- Cheating by personation using digital devices.
- Includes catfishing, phishing, and fraudulent impersonation.

3

Section 66E

- Intentional capturing/transmitting of images of private parts without consent.
- Protects bodily and sexual privacy in digital space.

4

Section 67

- Publishing/transmitting obscene content electronically.
- Covers pornography and sexually explicit material.
- Includes penalties for intermediaries (platforms/ISPs) if they fail to act.

Source: Information Technology Act, 2000

The *IT Act* focuses on online gender-based violence, with Sections 67 and 66E particularly safeguarding women and girls from non-consensual sharing of intimate images, such as revenge porn and deepfakes. Intermediaries are required to remove obscene or non-consensual content once notified, reinforced under the IT Rules of 2021 and 2023. These provisions operate alongside IPC Section 354C (voyeurism), 354D (stalking), and 509 (insulting modesty) to provide a complementary legal framework. The law is technology-neutral, applying to phones, computers, social media, and OTT platforms.

The Act protects women and girls from circulation of obscene material, revenge porn, voyeuristic content, fake profiles, and cyber frauds. Trans persons are safeguarded under Section 66E, which protects bodily privacy for all, including trans and non-binary individuals. Children receive additional protection, with child pornography criminalised under Section 67B of the *IT Act* and under the *POCSO Act*.

Section 67 provides for 3–5 years imprisonment and a fine up to Rs.10 lakhs. Section 66C and Section 66D each carry penalties of up to 3 years' imprisonment and fines up to Rs.1 lakh. Section 66E prescribes up to 3 years of imprisonment and fines up to Rs.2 lakhs.

The 2008 Amendment introduced Section 66C, 66D, and 66E to address identity theft, online cheating, and digital voyeurism. The IT Rules of 2021 and 2023, under the Digital India framework, mandate 24-hour takedowns of non-consensual sexual imagery once flagged, and introduce grievance redressal mechanisms and oversight boards. The *Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023*, strengthens privacy rights, indirectly bolstering Section 66E by reinforcing consent in data handling. Additional 2024–2025 rules impose obligations on intermediaries to detect and remove deepfakes and AI-generated obscene material.

While substantive offences remain under the *IT Act*, procedural provisions under BNSS govern investigations. This includes time-bound investigation of cyber offences, admissibility of electronic evidence (emails, IP logs, metadata), and victim confidentiality with in-camera trials for sexual content cases. IPC equivalents for voyeurism and stalking are aligned in the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS), 2023*, with corresponding procedural protections in *BNSS*.

Since enactment, reporting of cybercrimes against women has increased, reflecting greater awareness and the establishment of cyber

police cells. Platforms like Meta, X, and OTT services are compelled by IT Rules to promptly remove flagged sexual content, and courts have upheld women's right to online dignity as part of Article 21 (right to life and privacy). Despite these successes, challenges persist. The surge of AI-generated sexual images and deepfakes has outpaced enforcement capacity. Cross-border jurisdiction issues complicate takedowns, while understaffed cyber police units contribute to low conviction rates. Survivors often face victim-blaming and stigma, deterring reporting. Trans survivors, though legally protected, frequently encounter barriers due to police bias.

5.1.8 Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 (PWDVA)

Before 2005, women facing domestic violence in India largely relied on Section 498A IPC (cruelty by husband or relatives), which criminalised dowry harassment but did not provide civil remedies such as shelter, residence, or maintenance. The women's movement, supported by organisations like the Lawyers Collective and the National Commission for Women, pushed for a comprehensive civil law to protect women from abuse in the home. This led to the enactment of the *Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA)*, 2005, which came into force in 2006. The Act aimed to provide speedy, accessible, and victim-centric remedies against violence occurring within domestic spaces.

The *PWDVA* is a civil law with quasi-criminal elements, addressing physical, sexual, verbal, emotional, and economic abuse within domestic relationships. It protects women from violence by husbands, live-in partners, or relatives residing in a shared household and provides immediate relief measures, including protection orders, residence rights, custody orders, and monetary relief.

Chart 9

Key Elements in Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA), 2005

PWDVA focuses on civil relief and rehabilitation rather than purely punitive measures. It provides protection orders to stop violence, residence orders to prevent eviction and secure housing, monetary relief for maintenance or compensation, custody orders for children, and compensation for damages. State-appointed Protection Officers assist women in filing cases, accessing shelters, medical aid, and legal services, while special courts are empowered to pass orders swiftly, ideally within

60 days. The Act links with the IPC, allowing courts to direct criminal proceedings if the violence constitutes a crime.

The Act protects women in domestic relationships, including marriage, consanguinity, adoption, and live-in relationships akin to marriage. It shields them from physical, sexual, emotional, verbal, and economic abuse and extends protection to mothers, sisters, daughters, and widows. Although primarily gender-specific, courts have urged gender-sensitive interpretations to include transgender women in certain cases.

While *PWDVA* itself provides civil remedies, breaches of protection, residence, or monetary orders are criminal offences under Section 31 IPC, punishable with up to one year of imprisonment, a fine of up to Rs.20,000, or both. Linked offences, such as physical assault or dowry harassment, are separately punishable under the IPC.

The 2012 Amendment Rules strengthened service of notice, interim protection, and access to legal aid. Judicial interpretations have expanded scope: in *Hiral P. Harsora v. Kusum Narottamdas Harsora* (2016, SC), the “adult male” restriction was struck down, allowing any relative, including women in-laws, to be respondents. Courts, including Delhi and Bombay High Courts, have recognised rights of women in live-in relationships akin to marriage. Parliamentary discussions in 2023–2024 considered expanding coverage to elder abuse and gender-neutral protections, but no amendment has been passed.

Procedural protections under BNSS support *PWDVA* cases by ensuring in-camera hearings and time-bound service of summons and hearing of protection order applications. Electronic evidence, including messages, emails, and call records, is admissible. While cruelty and assault offences are aligned in the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita* (BNS), the *PWDVA* continues as a standalone special law with procedural backing.

PWDVA has broadened recognition of domestic violence as a multi-dimensional harm and empowered women with civil remedies such as residence, monetary support, and custody rights. NGOs and legal aid cells have trained Protection Officers and increased awareness. Judicial activism has expanded the scope to live-in partners, in-laws, and trans women in certain cases. Protection Officers are underfunded or overburdened, many states lack adequate shelters or rehabilitation homes, and women often face low awareness and stigma. Cases frequently exceed the intended 60-day timeline, and the law does not explicitly address

LGBTQ+ persons, elderly women, or women with disabilities. Enforcement bias persists, with police sometimes prioritising “family compromise” over survivor safety.

5.1.9 Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006 (PCMA)

Child marriage has been a persistent practice in India, exposing girls—and occasionally boys—to early pregnancy, maternal mortality, loss of education, domestic violence, and trafficking. Colonial laws, such as the *Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929* (the “*Sarda Act*”), set minimum marriage ages but imposed weak penalties and did not void marriages. Despite amendments in 1978 raising the minimum age to 18 for girls and 21 for boys, enforcement remained poor. Growing concern over the health, education, and rights of girls led to the enactment of the *Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006*, which replaced the earlier law with stronger preventive, protective, and punitive measures.

The PCMA is a special law prohibiting child marriage, making such marriages voidable or void, and prescribing penalties for those who promote or solemnise them. It defines a “child” as a female below 18 years and a male below 21 years and provides for district-level Child Marriage Prohibition Officers (CMPOs) to prevent, report, and prosecute child marriages.

Chart 10

Key Elements in Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006 (PCMA)

Key Elements

- 1 Voidable marriages**
- At the option of the contracting party who was a child at the time of marriage. Automatically void if:
- Minor is enticed/compelled
 - Marriage is for trafficking/immoral purposes

- 2 Child Marriage Prevention Officers**
- Monitor vulnerable communities, create awareness, and liaise with police/NGOs

- 3 Custody and maintenance**
- Courts empowered to grant custody of children born from child marriages and award maintenance to the girl.

- 4 Preventive powers**
- Magistrates may issue injunctions to prohibit impending child marriages.

Source: Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006 (PCMA)

The PCMA casts a wide net of liability, punishing priests, parents, relatives, and community leaders who promote or permit child marriages. It provides both civil and criminal remedies: marriages can be annulled, and offenders can face imprisonment or fines. Survivor-centric reliefs, such as custody, residence, and maintenance orders, protect affected girls. Petitioners must file annulment requests within two years of the child attaining majority.

The Act primarily protects girls under 18 from forced or early marriages that may result in early pregnancy, interrupted education, and domestic violence. Boys under 21 are also protected from coerced early marriages, though the law mainly focuses on girls. Trans and non-binary children are excluded in the statutory wording, but courts increasingly advocate for purposive interpretation. The law also protects children from being trafficked or sold under the guise of marriage.

An adult male marrying a child faces up to two years imprisonment and a fine of up to Rs.1 lakh. Anyone promoting, permitting, or solemnising a child marriage is subject to the same punishment. Violation of an injunction or preventive order carries similar penalties.

In 2017, the Supreme Court in *Independent Thought v. Union of India* struck down the exception allowing marital sex with girls aged 15–18, making sex with a minor wife rape under IPC Section 375. The 2021 Prohibition of Child Marriage (Amendment) Bill proposed raising the minimum marriage age for women from 18 to 21 years to align with men; the Bill is pending before the Standing Committee as of 2025. In 2024, civil society and feminist groups challenged the Bill, arguing that raising the age without addressing poverty and patriarchy risks criminalising communities rather than empowering girls.

Offences under PCMA remain governed by the Act but are cognisable and non-bailable under BNSS. The BNSS ensures time-bound investigations, in-camera hearings to protect survivors, and implementation of custody and maintenance orders through magistrates. Linked IPC/BNS offences, such as rape and trafficking, are integrated for cases involving minor brides.

The Act has provided legal clarity, making child marriage punishable rather than merely restrained. Court interventions have increased annulment petitions, especially for girls aided by NGOs, while awareness campaigns led by CMPOs, NGOs, and government schemes like

Beti Bachao Beti Padhao have raised public consciousness. Judicial activism has consistently affirmed that child marriage violates constitutional rights. Challenges remain: the practice persists, particularly in rural and tribal areas, with NCRB and UNICEF estimating that one in four marriages still involves a child bride. Conviction rates are low due to social acceptance, and many CMPOs are under-resourced or inadequately trained. Intersectional neglect disproportionately affects girls from poor, Dalit, Adivasi, and Muslim communities, while trans children remain invisible in the law. Controversy surrounding the pending Bill to raise the marriage age to 21 years highlights concerns that without addressing structural factors like poverty, education, and dowry pressures, child marriages may simply move underground.

5.1.10 Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012 (POCSO)

Before 2012, child sexual abuse cases in India were prosecuted under general IPC provisions, such as Section 354, 375, and 377, which were inadequate, gender-biased, and limited in scope. The absence of a child-specific, gender-neutral law contributed to gross underreporting and poor conviction rates. Following sustained activism, Law Commission reports, and India's obligations under the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), the *Protection of Children from Sexual Offences (POCSO) Act, 2012*, was enacted to create a comprehensive, child-centred legal framework for sexual offences. The Act introduced special procedures, child-friendly trials, and strict punishments aimed at safeguarding children and ensuring justice.

The *POCSO Act* is a special law dealing exclusively with sexual offences against children below 18 years. It is gender-neutral, protecting all children including boys, girls, and trans/non-binary children. The Act covers a wide range of sexual offences, from penetrative assault to harassment and child pornography. It also provides for special courts, victim-friendly procedures, mandatory reporting obligations, and rehabilitation measures to ensure holistic protection.

Chart 11

Key Elements of Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, 2012 (POCSO)

The *POCSO Act* is gender-neutral, protecting any child irrespective of sex or gender identity, and consent is irrelevant—any sexual act with a child under 18 is an offence. Aggravated categories attract harsher

punishments when the offender is in a position of trust or power. The Act mandates speedy trials, ideally completed within one year, and provides victim protection measures such as in-camera trials, anonymity, psychological assistance, and compensation schemes.

The Act protects children under 18 from all forms of sexual abuse, including penetrative and non-penetrative assault, harassment, and pornography. It safeguards children in homes, schools, child-care institutions, workplaces, and online platforms. Transgender and intersex children are explicitly covered due to the gender-neutral drafting. The Act also protects families and guardians from coercion to suppress cases by imposing mandatory reporting duties.

Penetrative sexual assault (Section 4) attracts 10 years to life imprisonment plus fine. Aggravated penetrative assault (Section 6) carries 20 years to life, or the death penalty (post-2019 amendment). Sexual assault (Section 8) attracts 3–5 years imprisonment plus fine, and sexual harassment (Section 12) up to 3 years plus fine. Using a child for pornography (Section 14) carries 5–7 years plus fine, with repeat offences punishable from 7 years to life. Failure to report (Section 21) is punishable with up to 6 months imprisonment plus fine.

The 2019 Amendment introduced the death penalty for aggravated penetrative assault, enhanced fines and punishments, and criminalised storage of child pornography. Rules issued between 2021 and 2023 strengthened monitoring of online content and made reporting mechanisms for child sexual abuse material mandatory for intermediaries. In 2024, Parliamentary debates raised concerns about the misuse of *POCSO* against consensual adolescent relationships, potentially criminalising children, though no amendments were passed.

BNSS reinforces procedural protections under *POCSO*, ensuring in-camera trials, anonymity, and time-bound investigations (ideally within two months). Magistrates are required to record the child's statement within 24 hours, and electronic or video evidence is admissible. While substantive *POCSO* provisions remain standalone, BNSS facilitates fast-track procedures and harmonises them with IPC/BNS equivalents where relevant.

The Act has increased reporting, with NCRB data showing a steady rise in registered *POCSO* cases, reflecting awareness and enforcement. Its gender-neutral framework protects boys and trans children, closing

earlier legal gaps. Child-friendly trials in some states have reduced trauma, and harsh punishments, including the death penalty, act as a strong deterrent. However, challenges persist: case backlogs and court delays undermine the “speedy trial” mandate, and many cases involve consensual teenage relationships that inadvertently criminalise adolescents. Victim support, including shelters, counselling, and compensation, is often delayed or unavailable. Digital threats, including cross-border circulation of child sexual abuse material (CSAM), continue to outpace enforcement. Mandatory reporting obligations sometimes discourage children or families from seeking help, and trans children, while legally covered, face stigma and institutional neglect in practice.

5.1.11 Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013

The December 2012 Delhi gang rape and murder, widely known as the “Nirbhaya case,” sparked nationwide outrage, mass protests, and global attention. In response, the government constituted the Justice J.S. Verma Committee in 2013, which recommended sweeping reforms on sexual offences, police accountability, and women’s safety. Following these recommendations, Parliament enacted *the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*, which came into force on February 3, 2013, amending key provisions of the IPC, CrPC, and *Evidence Act*.

The 2013 Act represents a comprehensive reform of sexual offence laws in India. It broadened the definition of rape, introduced new offences such as stalking, voyeurism, and acid attacks, strengthened punishments, and incorporated victim-friendly trial procedures to improve survivor protection and dignity.

Chart 12

Key Elements in the Criminal Law Amendment Act, 2013

Key Elements

1

New offences introduced

- Sexual harassment (Section 354A).
- Assault with intent to disrobe (Section 354B).
- Voyeurism (Section 354C).
- Stalking (Section 354D).
- Acid attack (Section 326A, Section 326B).

2

Redefinition of rape (Section 375 IPC)

Now includes penetration “to any extent” of vagina, anus, mouth, or urethra, by penis, object, or body part. Consent must be unequivocal, voluntary, and not obtained by threat, fraud, or intoxication. “No means no.”

3

Stricter punishments

Enhanced minimums, including life imprisonment and death in cases where rape leads to death or vegetative state.

4

Procedural safeguards

- Recording of statements by women police officers.
- In-camera trials.
- No disclosure of victim's identity.
- Free medical treatment for rape survivors.

Source: Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013

The Act is victim-centred, prioritising the dignity, privacy, and safety of survivors. It directs speedy investigation and trial, bans invasive practices like the two-finger test, renders past sexual history irrelevant to consent, and enforces police accountability by penalising failure to register FIRs in sexual offence cases.

The law protects women and girls from a wide spectrum of sexual violence, including harassment, disrobing, stalking, voyeurism, rape, and acid attacks. Children under 18 remain primarily protected under *POCSO*, though the 2013 amendments strengthened IPC provisions relevant to minors. However, trans and non-binary persons faced gaps in protection due to the Act's binary language until subsequent legislation, such as the *Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019*.

Rape (Section 376 IPC) attracts 10 years to life imprisonment, with the death penalty if the act results in death, vegetative state, or in repeat offences. Aggravated rape (by custodians, police, teachers, etc.) carries a minimum of 10 years to life. Acid attacks (Section 326A) are punishable with 10 years to life plus fines, and attempted acid attacks (Section 326B) with 5–7 years plus fines. Sexual harassment (Section 354A) can lead to up to 3 years imprisonment for physical acts and up to 1 year for verbal harassment. Voyeurism (Section 354C) and stalking (Section 354D) carry escalating sentences for repeat offences. Failure of police to register FIRs (Section 166A IPC) is punishable.

The *2018 Criminal Law Amendment* introduced the death penalty for rape of girls under 12 years and a minimum 20-year sentence for rape of girls under 16 years. The *2019 POCSO Amendment* integrated harsher punishments for child sexual assault. No fresh amendments directly modifying this Act occurred between 2023–2025, but its provisions were incorporated into the *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita* (BNS), 2023, with equivalent numbering. Marital rape remains largely uncriminalised, except when the wife is under 18 or judicially separated, and continues to be a subject of debate.

BNS 2023 re-numbers but retains all provisions introduced in 2013. Rape is covered under *BNS* Section 63–70, acid attacks under Section 115–116, and harassment, disrobing, voyeurism, and stalking under Section 74–78. *BNS 2023*, the procedural code, mandates in-camera trials, recording survivor statements within 24 hours preferably by a female magistrate, guarantees free medical treatment, and ensures admissibility of digital/audio-video evidence.

The Act has broadened recognition of sexual violence, enabling survivors to prosecute harassment, stalking, voyeurism, and acid attacks, which previously fell through legal cracks. Procedural safeguards protect survivor dignity, and high-profile convictions have strengthened public

trust. Awareness initiatives, such as the Nirbhaya Fund (2013), financed women's safety projects, One-Stop Centres, and fast-track courts. However, challenges persist: NCRB data shows rape conviction rates remain low at 27%–30%, the marital rape gap persists, rural areas often lack forensic capacity and victim support centres, fast-track courts are overburdened, and statutory definitions remain gender-binary, marginalising trans and LGBTQ+ survivors despite inclusive judicial interpretations in some cases.

5.1.12 Acid Attacks (Section 326A & 326B IPC)

Acid attacks, a brutal form of gender-based violence, involve throwing acid on a person's face or body with the intent to disfigure, maim, or kill. They are most often perpetrated against women and girls, usually as revenge for rejecting marriage or sexual advances. For a long time, acid attack survivors had no specific legal remedy, with such crimes prosecuted under general provisions of grievous hurt (IPC Section 320) or attempt to murder (Section 307). After sustained campaigns by women's rights groups, the *Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013*, introduced Sections 326A and 326B IPC, specifically addressing acid violence. These sections recognised the distinctive cruelty of acid attacks and the need for stringent punishment and survivor rehabilitation.

Sections 326A and 326B of the IPC criminalise the act of causing permanent or partial damage, deformity, disability, or grievous hurt by throwing acid, administering acid, or attempting to do so. Section 326A punishes the actual act of causing harm, while Section 326B punishes attempted acid attacks, even where no injury results. Both provisions mark a legislative acknowledgement that acid violence is not only an assault on the body but also on the dignity, identity, and future of survivors.

Chart 13

Key Elements in Law Against Acid Attacks

Key Elements

1 Section 326A IPC

- Causes permanent/partial damage, deformity, burns, maiming, disfigurement, or disability.
- Act must be intentional.
- Involves use of acid or similar corrosive substance.

2 Section 326B IPC

- Throwing or attempting to throw acid.
- Intent to cause permanent/partial damage or deformity.
- Punishable even if actual harm is not caused.

Source: Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013

These provisions are distinctive because they focus on both the act and its lifelong consequences. Unlike general assault provisions, Section 326A mandates that the perpetrator compensate the survivor, with fines directed towards the victim's medical expenses. The minimum punishment is rigorous imprisonment of 10 years, which may extend to life, reflecting the gravity of the crime. Section 326B similarly prescribes strict minimum imprisonment of 5 years, extendable to 7 years. Another important feature is the acknowledgment of the economic burden of recovery—surgery, counselling, and rehabilitation costs—which are to be partly borne by the offender.

These sections primarily protect women and girls, who are disproportionately targeted in acid violence, often for rejecting advances, refusing dowry demands, or exercising autonomy in relationships. They

also extend protection to men, trans persons, and non-binary individuals, since the wording is gender-neutral. The law protects individuals from physical disfigurement, lifelong disability, pain, and the social ostracism that follows acid attacks. It also symbolically recognises survivors as victims of gender-based hate crimes, where violence is used to control women's bodies and choices.

Under Section 326A, the punishment is rigorous imprisonment of not less than 10 years, extendable to life imprisonment, along with a fine directed specifically to meet medical expenses of the survivor. Section 326B provides for rigorous imprisonment of not less than 5 years, extendable to 7 years, along with a fine. These provisions emphasise both deterrence and victim-centred reparations.

The provisions were inserted in 2013 and remain substantively the same. However, allied developments have shaped their implementation. In 2013, the Supreme Court in *Laxmi v. Union of India* directed state governments to regulate acid sales, provide free medical treatment for survivors, and compensate victims under state victim compensation schemes. In 2024, a Bill was introduced in Parliament seeking stronger monitoring of acid sales and enhanced state responsibility for rehabilitation, but it is still pending.

The *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita* (BNS), 2023, re-numbers Section 326A and 326B but retains their substantive content and punishments. The *BNSS*, 2023, further strengthens procedural protections: medical examinations must be immediate, compensation orders expedited, and survivor testimony protected through in-camera hearings. Audio-video recording of evidence is admissible to reduce re-traumatisation.

As of 2025, acid attacks continue to be reported, though in smaller numbers compared to the early 2010s. NCRB data indicates several hundred cases annually, with Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, and Delhi among the states with the highest incidence. The law has succeeded in recognising acid violence as a distinct gender crime, but challenges remain. Conviction rates are low due to delayed investigations and weak enforcement of acid-sale restrictions. Survivors often face prolonged medical struggles, social stigma, and inadequate rehabilitation support despite compensation schemes. Trans survivors remain under-documented, pointing to gaps in inclusivity.

On the preventive side, awareness campaigns and stricter acid-sale regulations have reduced easy access to corrosive substances in some states. Several high-profile survivor-led campaigns (e.g., Stop Acid Attacks) have mobilised public empathy and policy attention. Yet, implementation is inconsistent, and many survivors continue to rely on NGOs for long-term rehabilitation.

5.1.13 Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013 (POSH Act)

Sexual harassment at the workplace had long been a neglected issue in India, despite widespread prevalence. The turning point came in 1997, when the Supreme Court delivered the *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan* judgement, prompted by the gang rape of Bhanwari Devi, a social worker who resisted child marriage. The Court laid down the Vishaka Guidelines, making it mandatory for workplaces to establish complaint mechanisms against sexual harassment. For over 15 years, these guidelines acted as law in the absence of legislation. Finally, following mounting pressure from women's rights groups, the *Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013*, commonly known as the *POSH Act*, was enacted. It codified and expanded the Vishaka Guidelines, creating a statutory framework to address workplace harassment.

The *POSH Act* is a special legislation aimed at ensuring a safe working environment for women, free from sexual harassment. It applies to all workplaces—government, private, unorganised, and even domestic workspaces—and protects women employees, clients, and visitors. The Act mandates the constitution of Internal Complaints Committees (ICCs) in organisations with 10 or more employees, and Local Complaints Committees (LCCs) at the district level to cover smaller workplaces or women in the informal sector.

Chart 14

Key Elements in Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013

The Act's strength lies in its preventive as well as remedial approach. It recognises sexual harassment as a violation of a woman's right to equality, life, and dignity under the Constitution. Unlike earlier ad hoc measures, it establishes permanent structures (ICCs/LCCs) for complaints. It also explicitly covers domestic workers, ensuring even women in private homes have legal recourse. Importantly, the Act stresses confidentiality during inquiry, to protect the dignity of both complainant and respondent.

The *POSH Act* protects all women, irrespective of age or employment status, from sexual harassment in any workplace. This includes women in formal jobs, informal sectors, domestic workers, interns, and clients visiting offices. It primarily protects women from unwelcome physical, verbal, or visual sexual behaviour, ensuring that the workplace is free of intimidation, hostility, or coercion. However, men, trans persons, and non-binary individuals are excluded under the current law, even though some organisations extend coverage voluntarily in their policies.

The Act does not directly prescribe criminal penalties for sexual harassment but operates through workplace disciplinary mechanisms. Upon substantiation of a complaint, the ICC/LCC may recommend actions such as written apology, warning, reprimand, withholding promotion, termination, or monetary compensation to the aggrieved woman. In cases where the conduct amounts to a criminal offence (e.g., IPC Section 354A), the ICC/LCC must forward the complaint to police. Employers failing to comply can face fines up to Rs.50,000, with repeat violations leading to cancellation of business licenses or deregistration.

Since its enactment, the *POSH Act* has not been substantively amended. However, in 2024, two Private Member Bills were introduced in the Rajya Sabha. The first sought to make the law gender-neutral, extending protection to men and trans persons. The second proposed greater accountability for employers, including public disclosure of POSH cases and penalties for non-functioning ICCs. As of 2025, these bills remain under discussion and have not yet become law.

The *POSH Act* is a special statute, but many of its cases intersect with *BNS, 2023* offences such as sexual harassment, assault, stalking, and voyeurism (BNS Section 74–78). The *BNSS, 2023* supports its enforcement by streamlining complaint procedures, ensuring in-camera trials for sexual harassment offences, and protecting the anonymity of complainants.

Over a decade since its passage, the *POSH Act* has raised awareness about workplace harassment and prompted organisations to create internal mechanisms for redressal. High-profile cases in corporate and political spaces have pushed employers to take compliance more seriously. In sectors such as IT and banking, ICCs are well-functioning and women are more aware of their rights.

Yet, challenges remain significant. In many small companies and informal sectors, ICCs do not exist or function only on paper. Survivors often hesitate to file complaints due to fear of retaliation, victim-blaming, or lack of trust in committees. Domestic workers face special barriers as enforcement in private households is weak. Further, the exclusion of men and trans persons from statutory protection has drawn criticism for being discriminatory. As of 2025, the *POSH Act* has laid the foundation for workplace safety but requires stronger monitoring, gender-neutral coverage, and cultural change to dismantle entrenched hierarchies of power.

5.1.14 Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019

For decades, transgender persons in India faced systemic exclusion, discrimination, and violence, with little legal recognition or protection. The Supreme Court's landmark judgment in *NALSA v. Union of India* (2014) recognised the right of transgender persons to self-identify their gender and directed the State to provide affirmative measures in education, employment, and healthcare. In response, Parliament introduced the Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Bill in 2016, which faced widespread protests due to its weak provisions and dilution of NALSA principles. After revisions, the *Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019*, was passed, followed by the Rules, 2020, which operationalised the law. Despite criticism, it remains India's first comprehensive law addressing the rights of transgender persons, including protection from violence.

The Act is a rights-based law prohibiting discrimination against transgender persons in education, employment, healthcare, housing, public services, and access to goods. It obligates governments to frame welfare schemes and sets procedures for legal gender recognition. It also criminalises certain forms of abuse and exploitation of transgender persons, thereby addressing gender-based violence targeted at this community.

Chart 15

Key Elements of Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019

A significant feature of the Act is its attempt to provide legal recognition and anti-discrimination protection for transgender persons. It creates a statutory obligation on governments to promote inclusivity and mandates welfare measures, though without clear funding commitments. Another important aspect is the criminalisation of violence specific to trans persons, such as family abandonment and public harassment. However, the law requires trans persons to apply to the District Magistrate for certification of identity, and demands proof of medical intervention for recognition as male/female, which has been widely criticised as violating the principle of self-identification established in NALSA.

The Act protects transgender persons, genderqueer persons, and intersex individuals from discrimination and violence in multiple spheres. It specifically guards them against family abandonment, denial of housing, harassment in public spaces, verbal and physical abuse, and exclusion from healthcare and education. By criminalising targeted forms of abuse, it aims to reduce everyday violence and structural discrimination. However, critics note that it does not sufficiently protect against sexual violence, as punishments are disproportionately lighter compared to similar IPC provisions for cisgender women.

Offences under the Act are punishable with imprisonment of 6 months to 2 years and fine. This includes denial of access to public places, removal from households, forced or bonded labour, and physical, sexual, verbal, or emotional abuse of transgender persons. The relatively mild punishments compared to other gender-based violence laws have been a key criticism, as they do not reflect the severity of crimes often committed against trans persons.

Since 2019, the Act has not been amended. However, the Rules of 2020 expanded procedural clarity on issuing identity certificates and welfare responsibilities of governments. In 2023 and 2024, civil society organisations and parliamentary discussions raised concerns about aligning the law with *BNSS 2023* provisions and strengthening punishments for sexual violence against trans persons. Activists continue to demand amendments to remove the medicalisation of gender recognition and to ensure parity in punishments with other gender violence laws.

The BNSS and BNS (Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023) provide broader procedural safeguards for survivors of violence, which also apply to transgender persons under this Act. In-camera hearings, anonymity protections, and time-bound investigations mandated under BNSS extend to complaints filed by trans persons. However, substantive gaps remain: for example, rape provisions under BNS still use gender-binary language, meaning trans persons may be excluded from the full protection of rape laws. The *Transgender Act* provisions, therefore, operate alongside but are not fully integrated with BNS protections.

As of 2025, the Act has created visibility for transgender rights and provided a framework for welfare schemes. Some states have introduced pension schemes, skill training programmes, and health insurance for transgender persons. The establishment of the National Council for Transgender Persons has opened a formal dialogue between government and community representatives.

However, challenges are profound. Many trans persons still face routine violence from families, police, and society, and access to justice remains limited. The requirement of identity certification through the District Magistrate is seen as bureaucratic and humiliating, deterring many from registering. Punishments under the Act are considered too mild to deter offenders. Moreover, systemic discrimination in employment, housing, and healthcare continues to perpetuate vulnerability. Activists argue that the Act falls short of the transformative potential envisioned in the NALSA judgment, as it prioritises administrative control over genuine self-determination and safety.

5.1.15 Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023

India's digital ecosystem expanded rapidly over the past decade, with increasing reliance on social media, online services, and digital platforms. Alongside these developments, incidents of cyberstalking, doxxing, revenge porn, online harassment, and misuse of personal data for targeting women and minorities surged. For years, India lacked a comprehensive privacy law, relying instead on patchy provisions of the *IT Act, 2000*. Following the Supreme Court's Puttaswamy judgment (2017), which recognised privacy as a fundamental right, the government initiated work on a new data protection framework. After several drafts and committee reports, Parliament passed the *Digital Personal Data Protection (DPDP) Act, 2023*, which came into effect with operational Rules notified

in 2025. This Act represents India's first full-scale privacy law, with significant implications for protection from gendered digital violence.

The *DPDP* Act regulates the collection, processing, storage, and sharing of personal data by government, companies, and intermediaries. It seeks to balance individual privacy rights with legitimate uses of data for governance and business. It establishes the Data Protection Board of India as the regulatory authority, empowered to investigate breaches, penalise violators, and ensure compliance. For women, children, and trans persons vulnerable to digital abuse, the Act provides new legal mechanisms to demand accountability from platforms and organisations mishandling their data.

Chart 16

Key Element of Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023

The *DPDP Act's* most important feature is its recognition that personal data is a matter of dignity and autonomy. It expands privacy protection from mere financial fraud to issues of bodily safety and online dignity. By regulating how platforms handle sensitive information (such as sexual orientation, gender identity, or medical records), it reduces risks of targeted harassment. The Act also prohibits tracking and profiling of children, which helps prevent online grooming, trafficking, and sexual exploitation. The 2025 Rules further strengthen this by requiring platforms to establish age-verification systems, complaint escalation mechanisms, and mandatory reporting of data breaches within 72 hours.

The Act protects all digital users, but it has a strong relevance for women, girls, and trans persons who are disproportionately subjected to cyber harassment, revenge porn, identity theft, and stalking. It shields children from harmful online design and advertising practices, which are often exploited by predators. It also indirectly protects survivors of gender-based violence by granting them control over their digital identity, making it harder for perpetrators to misuse leaked or intimate data.

While the *DPDP Act* does not criminalise offences directly (these remain under *IT Act 2000/BNS 2023* provisions such as Section 74–78 on stalking/harassment), it imposes heavy financial penalties on companies and platforms:

- Up to Rs. 250 crores for data breaches.
- Penalties for non-compliance with children's data protection obligations.
- Sanctions for failing to provide grievance redressal.

These fines create corporate liability, pushing companies to act swiftly in cases of harassment-related misuse of data (e.g., leaked images, impersonation).

The 2025 Rules operationalised the Act by:

- Setting procedures for age verification and parental consent for minors.
- Mandating 72-hour breach reporting to the Data Protection Board.
- Establishing a graded penalty system based on severity of breach.
- Requiring “consent dashboards” so individuals can track and withdraw data permissions.

Civil society continues to press for stronger survivor-focused protections, such as mandatory takedown timelines for revenge porn or doxxing. As of 2025, these are still being debated.

The *DPDP Act* operates alongside *BNS/BNSS*. Cases of cyberstalking, voyeurism, sexual harassment, identity theft, or dissemination of obscene material are prosecuted under *BNS, 2023* (successor to Section 354A–D IPC, 509 IPC, 67 IT Act, etc.). *BNSS* procedural safeguards, such as electronic evidence admissibility, in-camera hearings, and time-bound investigations, strengthen enforcement in cases where women’s or children’s intimate data is misused.

As of 2025, the *DPDP Act* and Rules represent a major step forward in India’s digital governance. Big tech companies and digital platforms have begun implementing compliance measures, such as data dashboards, grievance officers, and parental consent systems. Women’s rights groups have welcomed its potential to hold platforms accountable for privacy violations that enable gendered violence.

However, challenges remain. Awareness of individual rights is still low, especially in rural areas. Enforcement depends heavily on the efficiency of the Data Protection Board, which is newly established and under-resourced. Civil society groups argue that the law overemphasises state surveillance exemptions while being weaker on empowering citizens against government misuse of data. Survivors of cyber harassment also point out that while corporate liability is strong, timely removal of harmful content is not guaranteed.

5.2 Police and Judiciary

5.2.1 Specialised Police and Support Systems

5.2.1.1 Mahila Police, All-Women Police Stations, and One-Stop Centres

Specialised police units and stations were established to create a more trustworthy and accessible environment for female victims of crime. The presence of all-women police stations significantly increases the reporting of crimes like kidnapping and domestic violence. This increased reporting can be attributed to the perception that female officers are less likely to exhibit skewed gender norms and more likely to handle complaints with compassion and without further harassment, thus enhancing community trust and police legitimacy.

5.2.1.2 One-Stop Centres (OSCs)

Also known as *Sakhi* Centres, OSCs were established in 2015 to centralise support services for women affected by violence. They operate 24/7 and provide a holistic "one-stop" solution by offering services such as police facilitation, medical assistance, psychological support, legal aid, and temporary shelter for women and their children. However, a critical analysis of the scheme reveals significant implementation gaps. Despite being fully funded by the Nirbhaya fund, a substantial portion of the allocated funds remains unutilised in several states. This underutilisation is compounded by other systemic issues, including low salaries for workers, bureaucratic hurdles, and a persistent lack of public awareness, particularly in rural areas, which severely hampers the scheme's overall effectiveness.

5.2.2 Judicial Challenges

The Indian judiciary is grappling with a chronic crisis of case pendency, with many of the cases pending across all court levels. This backlog leads to the widely recognised issue of "justice delayed is justice denied" and is estimated to cost India more than 2% of its GDP. The primary causes of these delays are a chronic shortage of judges and inadequate infrastructure. India has only 15 judges per million people, far below the recommended 50, and many judicial positions remain vacant. This is further compounded by inefficient case management and frequent adjournments, contributing to a significant disparity in resolution times, particularly for civil cases.

Regarding biases, a study by Ash et al. (2025) of over five million criminal cases in lower courts found no systemic in-group bias in acquittal decisions based on shared religion, gender, or caste. This finding is notable as it contrasts with patterns observed in other countries. It suggests that while the broader legal profession may suffer from deeply entrenched biases, the act of judging in criminal cases may be impartial, possibly due to professional norms and secure judicial tenure. However, this does not mean the system is free from bias. Systemic biases persist in structural and discretionary elements of the system, such as judicial appointments. The low representation of female judges, especially in higher courts, is attributed to a combination of "structural and discretionary bias." This includes unwritten rules like the "seniority norm" and transfer policies that disproportionately affect women due to their familial responsibilities.

The lack of women in senior positions creates a vicious cycle with fewer mentors and role models, and a masculine understanding of the profession, coupled with a lack of supportive infrastructure like daycare centers, further impedes career progression for female legal professionals.

5.3 National and State Commissions

5.3.1 National and State Commissions for Women

The National Commission for Women (NCW) was established in 1992 as a statutory body under the *National Commission for Women Act, 1990*. Its mandate is to review constitutional and legal safeguards for women, recommend legislative measures, and facilitate the redressal of grievances. The NCW is empowered with the powers of a civil court to summon witnesses and compel the production of documents. It has played an active role in policy reforms, public awareness campaigns, and intervening in cases of human rights violations. State Commissions for Women, such as the Maharashtra and Meghalaya Commissions, were established with similar mandates to operate at the state level. They investigate practices unfavourable to women, review laws, and advise the state government on improving women's status.

5.3.2 Commission for Protection of Child Rights

The National Commission for Protection of Child Rights (NCPCR) is a statutory body under the Ministry of Women and Child Development. Its mandate is to ensure that all laws, policies, and administrative mechanisms align with a child rights perspective. The NCPCR investigates violations of child rights, protects vulnerable children, and promotes child rights literacy among various sections of society. A notable recent initiative is the GHAR (Go Home and Reunite) portal, a digital tool developed to monitor and track the restoration and repatriation of children.

5.3.3 National Council for Transgender Persons

Established in 2020 under the *Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019*, the National Council for Transgender Persons (NCTP) is a statutory body of the Government of India. Its primary function is to advise the government on all policy matters affecting transgender and intersex persons. The council consists of a chairperson and members from the transgender and intersex communities, and is part of the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment.

5.3.4 Effectiveness and Gaps

A consistent gap across all these commissions is their limited legal power. Their role is largely "recommendatory," meaning they cannot enforce their recommendations or take direct legal action against violators. This lack of enforcement power significantly curtails their influence on the executive branch. Additionally, the NCW has been criticised for limited outreach, making it difficult to reach women in remote and rural areas, as well as for not adequately representing marginalised women from different social and religious backgrounds.

5.4 Civil Society and Community-Based Mechanisms

5.4.1 Grassroots Justice Mechanisms and NGO Legal Aid

Grassroots justice mechanisms are often undertaken by civil society organisations (CSOs) and grassroots justice defenders who work directly with communities to empower vulnerable people by helping them "know, use, and shape the law." The National Legal Services Authority (NALSA) has sought to institutionalise this approach through the NALSA (JAGRITI) Scheme, 2025. This scheme aims to build an informed and empowered citizenry by collaborating with local self-government institutions like Panchayats to provide legal information and support at the community level.

Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) play a vital role in providing pro-bono legal services to the marginalised. Organisations like CLAP, Guria, and Sayodhya Home offer rescue, legal intervention, rehabilitation, and livelihood opportunities to survivors of sexual exploitation and domestic violence. NALSA also works with NGOs to provide free and competent legal services to eligible persons, including women and children, in line with Article 39A of the Constitution.

The relationship between the state and civil society is complex. While NGOs are essential for service provision and holding the government accountable, some sources suggest that certain organisations can be used for "nefarious activities" or to spread "false propaganda" to disrupt law and order. This dual nature highlights the complex role of civil society as both a powerful force for social good and a potential vehicle for destabilising influence.

5.4.2 Helplines

Telephonic helplines like 181 for women and 1098 for children provide 24/7 emergency and non-emergency support. They offer a range of services, including emergency assistance, psychological counseling, and information about government schemes. These helplines are integrated with other services like One-Stop Centres and the 112 Emergency Response Support System to ensure a seamless transfer of cases. The advantage of helplines is that they are a cost-effective, confidential, and low-stigma entry point for individuals seeking help, particularly for those who are unable to leave their homes or communicate openly with others about their situation.

5.5 Budget Allocations

The Government of India has launched numerous schemes to prevent GBV and assist survivors. These span nutrition and empowerment programmes, direct safety initiatives, and emergency response systems. Many have been reorganised under flagship programmes;

Mission Shakti (WCD): A mission-mode scheme for women’s safety and empowerment, launched in 2021. It has two sub-components: “Sambal” (safety and security) and “Samarthya” (livelihood and empowerment. Under Sambal, programmes like Self-Defense training, awareness campaigns, and “Women Helplines” are funded (Mission Shakti absorbed earlier schemes like Beti Bachao and working women’s hostels.) In 2025–2026, Rs.3,150 crores was allocated for Mission Shakti, reflecting almost 12% of WCD’s budget. Of this, Sambal’s safety programmes received Rs.629 crores in 2025–2026 (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b).

One Stop Centres (OSCs): Centre-funded crisis centres for survivors of GBV, OSCs provide integrated support and assistance under one roof: medical aid, legal advice, police facilitation, and counseling (One Stop Centre Scheme Implementation Guidelines for State Governments/UT Administrations, 2017). They are located in hospitals or special facilities across India. As of early 2025, 812 OSCs were operational nationwide (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025), and have served over 1.08 million women since inception. OSCs are supported by both the Nirbhaya Fund (below) and WCD.

Women Helpline (Dial 181): A 24×7 emergency helpline launched in 2018 under the Universalisation of Women Helpline Scheme. It offers immediate assistance and referrals (to police, hospitals, legal aid and OSCs) for women facing violence in public or private spaces (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025). The helpline is funded by the Nirbhaya Fund and supplements local police response.

Safe City Projects: City-level programmes (financed via Nirbhaya Fund) that install CCTVs, emergency buttons, women’s patrols, and other measures in major urban areas to deter sexual violence in public. (E.g., Delhi and Kolkata were among the first “Safe Cities.”) These are funded under Nirbhaya.

Emergency Response (112/ERSS); India has integrated emergency services under a single number “112,” which routes calls to police, ambulance, fire etc. (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025). This includes assistance to women under distress. The previous women’s helpline number (181) has been subsumed into 112 in many states.

Sexual Harassment (SHe-Box): An online portal for reporting workplace sexual harassment (under the *POSH Act*). Launched by WCD, it provides a “single-window” digital complaint system accessible to all women. Complaints filed on SHe-Box are automatically forwarded to the appropriate authorities for action (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025).

Women’s Help Desks (WHDs) at Police Stations: Funded by the Nirbhaya Fund, WHDs are dedicated counters in police stations to make enforcement more accessible to women. Each desk is headed by a woman officer. Over 14,658 WHDs have been set up nationwide, of which 13,743 are headed by women officers (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025). These serve as first-points-of-contact for women lodging complaints, to ensure sensitivity and privacy.

Mahila e-HiN (Connectivity): Various state and district-level initiatives link women to support networks. For instance, Mahila Salah Kendras and Mahila Lok Adalats provide counseling, legal aid, and settlement fora for domestic disputes. While these vary by state, they supplement central schemes.

Ancillary Measures: The government also runs allied programmes like Nari Adalats (women’s courts) for domestic disputes, and promotes “gender budgeting” (allocating at least 30% of funds to women-specific programmes in ministries). Additionally, the Ministry of Health conducts training for healthcare workers in responding to GBV, and schemes like Stree Manoraksha (NIMHANS) train OSC staff in trauma care (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025).

5.5.1 Budget Utilisation: Gaps and Unspent Allocations

Most of the above programmes are financed by the central government. In recent budgets the Ministry of Women & Child Development (WCD) has received allocations in the range of Rs.25,000–27,000 crore . The WCD allocation was Rs.25,449 crores for the Financial Year (FY) 2023–2024 (Budget Estimates (BE)), which is 6% rise over FY 2022–2023 (PRS Legislative Research, 2023). In FY 2024–2025, it rose modestly to Rs.26,092 crores (2.5% above Revised Estimates (RE); (PRS Legislative Research, 2025)) and, the FY 2025–2026 Budget estimates Rs.26,890 crores (a 16% jump) (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b). Despite these increases, the Ministry’s share of the total Union Budget remains very small, which is only about 0.6% of the Union Budget in 2024–2025 (PRS Legislative Research, 2025), and projected 0.5% by 2025–2026 (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b). In other words, India spends under 1% of its total budget on schemes for women and children (PRS Legislative Research, 2023 ;PRS Legislative Research, 2025b), even as women face deep gaps in health, education, and safety.

The breakdown of WCD’s budget highlights where money is spent. Table 21 summarises allocations to the ministry’s flagship schemes for FY 2023–2024 through FY 2025–2026. It shows that by far the largest share goes to nutrition and child development (Saksham Anganwadi/Poshan), whereas women’s safety programmes get a much smaller share. The Nirbhaya Fund itself appears as a mere Rs. 30 crore line item in FY 2024–2025 and 2025–2026, after a one-time Rs.500 crores spending in FY 2023–2024.

The Saksham/Poshan programme (nutrition/child development) dominates the budget (82% of spending in FY 2025–2026 (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b)). Mission Shakti’s allocation surged in FY 2025–2026 (especially its empowerment arm, *Samarthya*, increase of 145%) (PRS

Legislative Research, 2025b), reflecting policy emphasis on livelihoods. By contrast, schemes specifically for women's safety remain under-funded. The *Sambal* sub-scheme (safety) received only Rs.629 crores in FY 2025–2026 (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b), and Nirbhaya Fund-backed projects are virtually frozen at Rs.30 crores. In fact, PRS notes that in FY 2024–2025 the actual Nirbhaya spending was Rs.500 crores, but the BE for both 2024–2025 and 2025–2026 is just Rs.30 crores (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b).

Underutilisation is also a chronic issue. PRS analysis observes that “actual expenditure by the Ministry has been lower than the budget allocation” in nearly every year (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b). For example, in 2019–2020 about 21% of WCD's allocation went unspent (PRS Legislative Research, 2023). A parliamentary panel warned that this shortfall reflects either poor planning or implementation gaps, and recommended better budgeting and monitoring (PRS Legislative Research, 2023)(PRS Legislative Research, 2025b). In practice, delays in state co-financing and bureaucratic hurdles often cause funds (especially from Nirbhaya) to remain unutilised (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b)(PRS Legislative Research, 2025). For instance, as of August 2023 only 68% of sanctioned Nirbhaya funds had even been released to states, and overall utilisation stood at just 62%(PRS Legislative Research, 2025).

Nirbhaya Fund (MHA): Set up in 2013 (after the Delhi gang-rape), this corpus is managed by the Ministry of Home Affairs to finance women's safety projects nationwide. Through FY 2024–2025, Rs.7,712.85 crore was budgeted under Nirbhaya, of which about Rs.5,846.08 crore (approximately 76%) was actually spent (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025). The Fund has supported 812 One Stop Centres, expansion of Emergency Response (112), the women's helpline (181), fast-track courts, Anti-Human-Trafficking Units, cyber forensic labs, Safe City and Safe Rail projects, and the Central Victim Compensation Fund(Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025). However, many sanctioned projects have lagged. A 2020 parliamentary committee noted slow progress and recommended a high-level oversight committee(PRS Legislative Research, 2025).

Safe City and Transport Safety: Nirbhaya has financed Safe City projects in metros (e.g. CCTV networks, Women Help Desks) and women’s safety in rail/road transport (e.g., emergency buttons in trains). These measures aim to protect women in public spaces.

Mahila Sasaktikaran (Women’s Empowerment) Schemes: Various programmes (now part of Samarthyaa) provide self-help group support, skill training, microcredit and incentives (e.g. Working Women’s Hostels, Swayam Sakhi helpline, STEP scheme). While not direct safety nets, such economic empowerment is viewed as reducing vulnerability.

Gender Budgeting: All ministries classify schemes by their share for women (“Gender Budget Statement”). In FY 2025–2026, India’s total “Gender Budget” (aggregate spending on women’s programmes across all ministries) was reported at Rs.4.49 lakh crores (8.9% of the union budget)(Ministry of Finance, Government of India, 2025). WCD’s share of that is small, reflecting a lack of targeted spending on women’s security relative to their needs.

5.6 Challenges

Social stigma and mistrust lead many survivors to stay silent. A Reuters report found victims often fear being “shamed” by family or community, so only approximately 40% of rapes are reported (Bhalla, 2013). GBV victims also distrust law enforcement; many hide the abuse or accept it as “private.” PRS and NGOs warn that this “underreporting due to stigma” means official case counts are a fraction of true incidence (DC Web Desk, 2025)(CJP Team, 2025). In practice, this makes it hard to allocate resources or measure the impact of interventions.

Implementation Gaps: Numerous assessments point to poor execution of GBV schemes. For example, PRS and parliamentary committees have repeatedly flagged under-spending and delays. Inadequate coordination between ministries and states has slowed Nirbhaya projects (PRS Legislative Research, 2025). States are often required to provide matching funds; when they fail to do so or launch corresponding programmes, central funds sit unused (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b). Even schemes subsumed under Mission Shakti sometimes suffer due to lack of clear guidelines or weak monitoring. According to a PRS report, underutilisation of funds “indicates either lack of financial prudence at the planning and budgeting stage or gaps in implementation”(PRS Legislative Research, 2025b). There have also been

reports of One Stop Centres lying non-functional due to staffing shortages. Overall, bureaucratic inertia and poor accountability mean that many survivors never see the benefits of the programmes on paper.

Budget and Resource Constraints: Funding for women's safety remains limited. The WCD budget, as noted, is under 1% of the total, despite women constituting half the population. Within that small budget, only a tiny fraction is earmarked for violence prevention. Mission Shakti's safety arm and Nirbhaya schemes together account for a few hundred crores per year, which is insufficient relative to the scale of the problem. Even these limited funds have been poorly utilised—the Nirbhaya Fund saw its own allocation plummet to almost zero in recent budgets (PRS Legislative Research, 2025b). The Women's Helpline and OSCs, while nationally rolled out, often operate on shoestring budgets at the local level. The Standing Committee has urged larger allocations, but successive budgets have only gradually expanded spending. In short, low budgetary priority for GBV interventions (in both absolute and percentage terms) constrains capacity.

Gender-Insensitive Personnel: A critical challenge is the attitude of frontline staff. Numerous studies and reports document that many police officers and officials lack gender-sensitivity training. Victims often face hostile, skeptical or humiliating treatment when they approach the police or health workers. A Reuters investigation noted that "police are generally highly insensitive to female victims" (Bhalla, 2013). Many officers harbour victim-blaming biases: asking survivors to justify their whereabouts or attire (Bhalla, 2013) (CJP Team, 2025). Even senior officials openly admit the police force needs training in this area (Bhalla, 2013). Less than 7% of India's police are women (Bhalla, 2013), further discouraging victims. Courts and prosecution are also criticised: trials drag on for years, and punishments (for offenses like rape or domestic cruelty) are often viewed as too lenient, signaling a lack of seriousness. In sum, systemic bias and insensitivity in law enforcement and the judiciary deter reporting and undermine justice.

Beyond staff attitudes, India lacks adequate shelters, counseling and mental health services for survivors. One Stop Centres exist, but are often overwhelmed or understaffed. A PRS analysis observes there is a "severe shortage of safe shelters and accessible counseling services" (CJP Team, 2025). Many women have nowhere safe to turn when they flee violence, and long-term rehabilitation programmes (legal aid, vocational

training) are scant. As a result, even when women do come forward, the social safety net often fails to protect them, pushing some back into abusive situations.

While India has built a framework of laws and programmes to combat GBV, implementation remains weak. Gaps in funding, planning, and personnel training mean that many victims fall through the cracks. Addressing these challenges will require not just more money, but greater political will to reform institutions, streamline schemes, and sensitize all officials who interface with GBV survivors.

6 Comparative Global Practices

6.1 Legal and Policy Reforms

The enactment of foundational legal and policy instruments is a global first step in combating GBV. Sweden's *Discrimination Act* (2009) and Criminal Code provisions for offenses like "gross violation of a woman's integrity" are pioneering examples of proactive legal measures that mandate gender equality and criminalize specific forms of violence (European Institute For Gender Equality, 2023). Similarly, South Africa has a robust framework that includes a *Domestic Violence Act* and a *Sexual Offences Act*, with recent legislative amendments aimed at a survivor-centred approach to combating gender-based violence (Soci, 2024; Burger Huyser Attorneys, 2025). Brazil's Maria da Penha Law (2006) stands out as a landmark piece of legislation in Latin America, defining five forms of violence and creating specialised domestic violence courts (Instituto Maria Da Penha (IMP), 2006). Rwanda is a regional leader, having criminalised all forms of domestic violence in 2008 and outlawing marital rape, which provides significant legal recourse for survivors, including grounds for unilateral divorce (Immigration and Refugee Board of Canada, 2019).

A recurring theme, however, is the significant gap between these progressive laws and their effective implementation. Despite having a "generous catalogue of rights" on paper with laws like Law 26.485, Argentina struggles with this deficit (Funes, 2017). The country's legal and criminal justice systems are rated poorly on enforcement, meaning that the law in the books is not the law in practice (World Justice Project, n.d.).

Similarly, in Nepal and Bangladesh, the Domestic Violence Acts have been lauded as a collaborative achievement of government and civil society (Sultan & Mahpara, 2024). However, in both countries, the laws are

undermined by a lack of political will, insufficient resources for enforcement, and a limited understanding of the legal frameworks among law enforcement and judicial officials (Sultan & Mahpara, 2024).

This dynamic demonstrates that a country can pass a comprehensive law and achieve a political win, but without corresponding budgetary allocation (Latin America Advisor: A Daily Publication of the Dialogue, 2022) and proper training for implementing agencies, the law becomes a symbolic gesture rather than a tool for meaningful change.

Proactive Policing: Rwanda's Community-level Police Gender Desks

Police Gender Desks in Rwanda offer a model for proactive, community-based policing to combat gender-based violence. Established in 2005, these desks are part of a broader initiative to enhance the Rwandan National Police's response to GBV by increasing capacity for investigation and counselling, particularly in rural areas (United Nations Development Fund for Women, 2009). The model emphasises capacity building for police officers, community sensitisation, and engaging men and boys as allies in the fight against violence. This approach aims to stimulate behavioural change and shift power relations at the local level by institutionalising gender-sensitive policing (United Nations Development Fund for Women, 2009). This model is particularly relevant for India, where police bias and apathy are significant barriers to reporting. It suggests that a fundamental shift in police culture from a reactive, disciplinary one to a proactive, community-oriented one can be a powerful tool in preventing and responding to gender-based violence.

6.2 Institutional and Service Delivery Models

Specialised, coordinated services are essential for providing immediate support to survivors. Isange One Stop Centres (IOSCs) in Rwanda are a powerful model of integrated care, providing free medical, psychological, legal, and investigation support in a single facility, which addresses the fragmentation of traditional justice and healthcare systems (Ministry of Gender and Family Promotion, Government of the Republic of Rwanda, 2021). This "one-stop shop" model is a survivor-centric approach that significantly reduces the logistical and emotional burden on a survivor, increasing the likelihood of a successful outcome and encouraging reporting (Soci, 2024).

South Africa has a similar model with its Thuthuzela Care Centres and the 24/7 Gender-Based Violence Command Centre (GBVCC), which uses multiple digital channels to provide accessible support (Soci, 2024). Brazil's "Casas da Mulher Brasileira" serve the same function, offering a range of legal, health, and psycho-social services (Latin America Advisor: A Daily Publication of the Dialogue, 2022).

A notable innovation to address the challenge of geographical access is the use of mobile courts and services. Malawi, for instance, has successfully implemented mobile court sessions in collaboration with NGOs to bring justice to remote, rural communities (UN Women Africa, 2024). This approach has proven effective in accelerating access to justice for women and girls and has resulted in a significant increase in reported gender-based violence cases, demonstrating that making the legal system physically present and accessible can transform it from an abstract concept into a tangible reality for survivors (Kalumbi, 2025). This is in stark contrast to Brazil and Bangladesh, where one-stop centres are often concentrated in urban areas, isolating women in rural regions who must travel long distances for help (Independent Advisory Group on Country Information (IAGCI), 2024).

Integrated Support Systems: The South African Thuthuzela Care Centre Model

The Thuthuzela Care Centre (TCC) model in South Africa provides a compelling example of an integrated, survivor-centered approach to sexual violence. TCCs are one-stop facilities located within hospitals that aim to reduce secondary victimisation, improve conviction rates, and shorten the time for case finalisation (National Prosecuting Authority, South Africa, 2025). The key to the model's success is its deep integration of services. A survivor can report a crime, receive immediate medical attention including DNA evidence collection, crisis counselling, and give a police statement, all in a private, dignified, and supportive environment (National Prosecuting Authority, South Africa, 2025).

This model contrasts sharply with India's One Stop Centres, which, while well-intentioned, often operate as separate facilities that require survivors to navigate a fragmented and often retraumatizing system involving multiple agencies and locations (Dlamini, 2023). The TCC model

demonstrates that a holistic approach, where all necessary services are seamlessly coordinated at the point of first response, is a gold standard for a truly survivor-centred care system.

6.3 Community-Based and Social Norms Transformation

Legal frameworks, while necessary, are often reactive and only punish a crime after it has occurred. To prevent gender-based violence, it is crucial to address the cultural and social conditions that enable violence to exist. Argentina's #NiUnaMenos movement, triggered by the murder of a 14-year-old girl in 2015, used social media and mass protests to shift public dialogue and demand government action (Iricibar, 2024). This movement, which successfully led to the creation of a Femicide Registry and the criminalisation of femicide, is a powerful example of how civil society can drive change from the ground up (Equal Measure 2030, 2024).

Governments and civil society organisations are increasingly focusing on engaging men and boys as allies to address the root causes of violence. In South Africa, the "Under-The-Tree Dialogues" aim to raise awareness and change attitudes among men and boys (Department of Justice and Constitutional Development, Republic of South Africa, 2022). In Rwanda, grassroots initiatives like Umugoroba w'Imiryango (Families' Evening Forum) are used for community education and to break the stigma around gender-based violence (Ministry of Gender and Family Promotion, Government of the Republic of Rwanda, 2021).

A critical observation from India's experience with the Men Against Violence and Abuse (MAVA) organisation is that traditional efforts focused solely on empowering women can inadvertently "insulate men from the process of transformation and further the gender divide" (Men Against Violence and Abuse (MAVA), 1993). MAVA's approach, which focuses on engaging and mentoring young men to challenge patriarchal norms, represents a vital shift in strategy. This work reframes gender-based violence not as a "women's issue" but as a "societal issue" (Therese, 2018), broadening the base of responsibility and creating a more sustainable, long-term solution by changing the attitudes of potential perpetrators (Men Against Violence and Abuse (MAVA), 1993).

Social Movements and Policy Change: The Impact of Argentina's *Ni Una Menos*

The *Ni Una Menos* (Not One Less) movement in Argentina demonstrates the power of grassroots social mobilisation to effect legislative and institutional change. Originating as a collective scream against femicide, the movement used social media to build a continental alliance of feminist forces (Medina, 2023). The movement's sustained advocacy led to significant policy outcomes, including the creation of a national Registry of Femicides and a Centre for the Registration, Systematisation, and Monitoring of Femicides (Medina, 2023). It also served as a catalyst for the passage of a comprehensive gender-violence law in 2015 and the eventual legalisation of abortion in Argentina ((Medina, 2023; Jaureguy, 2025).

The success of this movement highlights that legislative reform is often a direct result of a powerful and sustained "bottom-up" demand from civil society. For India, this suggests that institutional reforms, which often face bureaucratic inaction, can be accelerated by fostering and responding to a strong, mobilised public voice.

6.4 Technological Interventions

Technology is a double-edged sword in the fight against gender-based violence. While it offers powerful tools for support and data collection, it also creates new avenues for violence. South Africa's gender-based violence Command Centre demonstrates a sophisticated use of technology with its multi-channel support system, including a Skype line for the deaf community and a Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) "please call me" facility for those in danger (Department of Justice and Constitutional Development, Republic of South Africa, 2022). Brazil's pilot project in Recife represents a proactive use of technology, utilising semantic analysis and artificial intelligence to analyse health data patterns and predict the escalation of violence, which can help prevent femicides (Vital Strategies, 2025).

India has also adopted a range of digital platforms, including the National Commission for Women's Helpline (7827170170), the Emergency Response Support System (112), and the SHe-Box portal for reporting workplace sexual harassment (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025).

However, the increase of digital platforms has also created new challenges, as evidenced in South Africa and Brazil, where online abuse such as cyberstalking, revenge pornography, and deepfakes are on the rise (Marokoane, 2025). The anonymity and borderless nature of the internet present significant regulatory challenges, as perpetrators can operate from outside a country's borders with little recourse for survivors (Marokoane, 2025). This evolving threat necessitates a dual approach which is, leveraging technology for support while simultaneously investing in cybercrime prevention, digital literacy, and collaboration with tech companies to create safe digital spaces (UN Women, 2025).

6.5 Economic Empowerment Initiatives

Economic dependency is a major driver of gender-based violence, and empowering women financially is a crucial prevention and recovery strategy. In Sweden, government initiatives analyse the housing market from a gender-equality perspective to help women leave abusive relationships, recognising that economic conditions are often a barrier that stops women to escape (Ministry of Employment, Government Offices of Sweden, 2024). South Africa's National Strategic Plan on Gender Based Violence and Femicide (GBVF) includes a dedicated pillar for "Economic Power," with a government commitment to set aside a minimum of 40% of public procurement for women-owned businesses (Soci, 2024). In Malawi, the Umunthu Plus Initiative provides psychosocial and economic support, including vocational training and scholarships for girls who have left forced marriages, directly linking economic independence to escape from violence (Rights CoLAB, 2023). In Nepal, NGOs like Saathi provide income-generating skill training to survivors in their shelters, fostering a path to self-reliance (Saathi, 2022).

This approach addresses a root cause of violence, that a woman who is financially dependent on her abuser is less likely to report violence or leave the relationship for fear of poverty and a lack of social acceptance as a single woman (Independent Advisory Group on Country Information (IAGCI), 2024). By providing vocational training, access to capital, or preferential business treatment, governments and NGOs can break this cycle of dependency, making leaving an abusive relationship a viable option. This simultaneously disempowers the abuser and provides a tangible path to a life free from violence, making economic empowerment a primary prevention strategy as much as a recovery tool.

Holistic Governance: Sweden's Gender-Responsive Budgeting

Sweden's gender equality policy offers a model for mainstreaming gender perspectives across all levels of governance. Instead of viewing gender equality as a single issue, the Swedish government has made it a core objective across all policy areas (Ministry of Employment, Government Offices of Sweden, 2024). This is supported by a gender-responsive budgeting strategy that mandates all ministries to include a gender impact assessment as part of their proposals to the Ministry of Finance. The goal is to ensure that revenues and expenditures are actively restructured to recognise national gender equality objectives (Ministry of Employment, Government Offices of Sweden, 2024).

This approach contrasts with India's current Gender Budget Statement (GBS), which functions primarily as a reporting mechanism to track allocations rather than a mandatory, pre-budgeting analytical tool (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India, 2024). The Swedish model provides a blueprint for moving beyond symbolic budgeting towards a systemic approach that holds every government department accountable for its contribution to gender equality.

6.6 Comparative Analysis: International Practices vs. India's Approach

6.6.1 Legal and Policy Landscape: A Tale of Two Realities

India's legal framework for gender-based violence has made strides with laws such as the *Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA)* of 2005, which provides civil remedies and a broad definition of abuse (The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005). This is similar to the experiences of Argentina and Bangladesh, where progressive laws exist on paper but face significant implementation challenges on the ground due to a lack of resources and political will (World Justice Project, n.d.).

A critical point of difference, however, is India's legal position on marital rape. Unlike Rwanda, which criminalised marital rape as part of its comprehensive gender-based violence law in 2008, India's IPC (1860) and *BNSS* (2023) does not explicitly protect a married woman from non-consensual sexual intercourse with her husband, sending a message that a woman's right to bodily autonomy is conditional on her marital status (Immigration and Refugee Board of Canada, 2019).

This is a major gap compared to international human rights standards and a significant difference from the legal frameworks of countries like Sweden and Rwanda. The shared challenge across these nations is the need to ensure that a law is not merely a symbolic gesture but is accompanied by a strong implementation strategy that includes training for police, prosecutors, and judges who often lack the gender-sensitive perspective needed to enforce the legislation effectively (Sultan & Mahpara, 2024).

6.6.2 Institutional and Community Responses: Bridging the Gaps

The One Stop Centres (OSCs) in India provide integrated support to women affected by violence and are funded through the Nirbhaya Fund (Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India & PIB Delhi, 2025). This concept is a direct parallel to Rwanda's IOSCs and South Africa's Thuthuzela Care Centres (Soci, 2024). However, as with Brazil and Bangladesh, the number and capacity of these centres in India are inadequate for the vast population, and they are often concentrated in urban areas, leaving rural women isolated (Independent Advisory Group on Country Information (IAGCI), 2024). India can learn from Malawi's innovative mobile court model, which brings justice and legal services directly to remote communities, bypassing geographical and financial barriers and increasing reporting rates (UN Women Africa, 2024).

Furthermore, while traditional efforts in India have focused on empowering women, a growing number of NGOs, such as MAVA, are engaging men and boys in a similar manner to community dialogues in Rwanda and South Africa (Men Against Violence and Abuse (MAVA), 1993). This approach is crucial for addressing the cultural roots of gender-based violence, as it shifts the focus from a "women's problem" to a "societal problem," leading to a more sustainable reduction in violence by changing the attitudes of potential perpetrators rather than simply punishing them after the act. This is a vital complement to legal reforms, which often only address the symptoms of a much deeper cultural issue.

7 Best Practices for India: Policy and Practice Recommendations

7.1 Prevention

The prevalence of gender-based violence in India is fundamentally linked to the deep-rooted sociocultural and historical norms that have institutionalised the subordination of women and higher patriarchal control. Without a collaborative effort to transform these foundational beliefs, legal and correctional measures alone will be insufficient to effect lasting change.

Gender-sensitive Curricula

To address these deep-rooted issues, a crucial recommendation is to integrate mandatory, age-appropriate, gender-sensitive curricula into educational systems from elementary school through higher education. This curriculum should be designed to actively challenge patriarchal norms, expose the historical roots of gender-based violence in ancient texts such as the Manusmriti and literary epic like the Ramayana, and promote values of consent, equality, and mutual respect. The persistence of violence is not just about individual behaviour. It is about the normalisation of violence and inequality through social conditioning and historical texts, which have portrayed women as inherently flawed and morally suspect.

This systematic approach to education aims to deconstruct these harmful narratives from a young age, thereby creating a long-term, systemic intervention to foster a more equitable society. The research highlights that a significant proportion of men who grew up in violent households normalised aggressive behaviour and carried these attitudes into public life. Mandating a gender-sensitive education policy is a direct and strategic response to this finding, aimed at breaking the inter-generational cycle of violence by transforming the mindset of future generations.

Inclusive and Context-Sensitive Public Campaigns

Nationwide public campaigns are essential for transforming social norms at scale. The analysis of global movements, such as Argentina's #NiUnaMenos, demonstrates how public dialogue can successfully drive legislative change and create a powerful "bottom-up" demand for

accountability. For these campaigns to be effective in India, they must be inclusive and context-sensitive, designed to resonate with all communities, including Dalit, Adivasi, Muslim, and LGBTQ+ persons, whose experiences of violence are often "depersonalised" or "invisible" in mainstream media coverage.

A critical aspect of these campaigns should be the active participation and engagement of men and boys. The analysis reveals a significant gap where traditional efforts focused solely on empowering women can unintentionally exclude men from the process of transformation and further the gender divide. The most sustainable prevention strategy is one that actively involves men and boys as allies in the solution, reframing gender-based violence not as a "women's issue" but as a "societal issue". The success of organisations like MAVA in India and South Africa's Under-The-Tree Dialogues provides a clear blueprint for this approach, demonstrating how community-level interventions can effectively challenge patriarchal attitudes and change the behaviour of potential perpetrators.

7.2 Protection

Ensuring the physical and psychological safety of survivors is a prime priority, requiring a shift from fragmented, reactive services to an integrated, survivor-centric system. The analysis highlights that India's current protective mechanisms, such as One Stop Centres (OSCs), are often "inadequate in number and geographically inaccessible," particularly for rural and marginalised women. The structural inequity in access to justice is a critical barrier for survivors from marginalised communities.

Strengthen and Expand Shelter Homes and One Stop Centres

To address the implementation inequality and patchy nature of existing services, the number of One Stop Centres (OSCs) must be significantly increased, with a strategic focus on rural and geographically isolated areas. These centres must be fully funded and staffed by trained professionals, with standardised protocols for providing comprehensive care.

A valuable lesson can be drawn from South Africa's Thuthuzela Care Centres model, which provides a seamless "one-stop shop" for survivors, offering free medical, psychological, legal, and investigative support in a single facility. This model directly addresses the

fragmentation of India's traditional justice and healthcare systems, which often re-traumatise survivors as they navigate multiple agencies and locations. By integrating services at the point of first response, a survivor's logistical and emotional burden is significantly reduced, increasing the likelihood of a successful outcome and encouraging reporting. Furthermore, the mobile court model from Malawi offers a blueprint for overcoming geographical barriers, bringing legal services directly to remote communities and transforming the legal system from an abstract concept into a tangible reality for survivors.

Establish Safe Migration Protocols for Trafficked Persons

The research reveals that displacement and poverty are major drivers of trafficking, which disproportionately affects tribal women who are often subjected to exploitative labour and sexual harassment. While the *Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act (ITPA)* and the BNSS provide a legal framework, the human cost of trafficking remains high, fueled by the entanglement of trafficking with migration, poverty, and weak border governance. The persistence of this crime is not merely a legal issue but a socioeconomic one that demands a holistic response.

A crucial recommendation is to implement and strengthen protocols for protecting vulnerable migrant women and girls. This includes establishing public-private partnerships, mandating transparent recruitment agencies, and creating a national-level registry of offenders. This multi-faceted approach goes beyond law enforcement to address the root causes of vulnerability and exploitation, recognising that a purely disciplinary approach is insufficient when the drivers of the crime are deeply rooted in socioeconomic inequality. The analysis suggests that while the ITPA has been updated to align with international standards, its implementation struggles with low conviction rates and the fact that survivors are often criminalised rather than traffickers being prosecuted. Therefore, the focus must shift to a preventive approach that makes migration safer and more transparent for the most vulnerable populations.

7.3 Prosecution

While India's legal framework for gender-based violence has been strengthened through the *Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013* and the BNSS (2023), the analysis reveals a significant gap between these progressive laws and their effective implementation. Systemic problems such as investigatory delays, poor evidence-handling, and low conviction

rates remain. Without a streamlined and accountable judicial process, survivors' faith in the justice system will continue to reduce, leading to under-reporting and impunity.

Operationalise Fast-Track Courts and Strengthen Judicial Capacity

A policy recommendation is to fully invest in and operationalise a robust network of fast-track courts across the country, as mandated by the BNSS (2023). This requires dedicated judicial resources, specialised training for judges on gender sensitivity and legal precedents, and a zero-tolerance policy for case backlog and delay. The problem is not the lack of legal tools, but the lack of institutional will and resources to enforce them. The recurring issue of low conviction rates for crimes like dowry deaths and dowry-related cruelty, despite a strong presumption-based offence that shifts the burden of proof to the accused, underscores this gap between law and practice. This suggests that the existence of laws and special courts is a symbolic gesture" without corresponding budgetary allocation and training. The mandate for trials to be completed within one year under *POCSO* should be expanded as a national goal for all gender-based violence cases.

Strengthen Victim-Witness Protection and Forensic Capacity

The research emphasises that survivors face re-traumatisation and secondary victimisation during the investigative and prosecutorial stages, often worsened by poor evidence-handling and delays. To combat this, a comprehensive, national-level survivor-witness protection protocol is essential. This protocol should provide security, confidentiality, and psycho-social support to survivors throughout the legal process. Furthermore, strengthening forensic labs and providing mandatory chain-of-custody training for police and medical staff are critical steps to ensure timely and credible evidence handling. The South African Thuthuzela Care Centre model, which reduces secondary victimisation by integrating services and evidence collection at a single point, provides a direct lesson for India. The analysis reveals a cause-and-effect relationship where the systems' inability to protect the survivor is a direct contributor to low conviction rates and underreporting, perpetuating a cycle of silence and impunity.

Establish Accountability for Systemic Neglect

To address systemic failures and unchecked institutional power, it is necessary to establish an independent, third-party oversight mechanism. This body should be tasked with monitoring the timeliness and quality of GBV case investigations and prosecutions. The mechanism should publish a dashboard of disaggregated data on conviction timelines and attrition points by district and state, thereby holding police and judicial bodies accountable for delays and low conviction rates. The research's recommendation for data and accountability is not merely about transparency, but a strategic tool for systemic change. By making performance data public, this policy would create a feedback loop that incentivises agencies to improve their processes and rebuild public trust, which is a key component of effective governance.

7.4 Multi-stakeholder Collaboration

The analysis of gender-based violence in India reveals a problem that is public health, legal, economic, and educational in nature. A fragmented institutional response, where each sector works in isolation, cannot effectively address such a multidimensional problem. The lack of collaboration among ministries is a fundamental systemic challenge that perpetuates an inefficient response.

Foster Collectiveness of Ministries

A key recommendation is to adopt a model of gender-responsive budgeting and policy that mandates a coordinated approach across all ministries. This moves beyond the siloed governance where a single ministry, such as the Ministry of Women and Child Development, shoulders the entire burden. Inspired by Sweden's model, the goal is to ensure that gender equality is a core objective across all policy areas, with a gender impact assessment of all government proposals. This approach views gender-based violence as a shared responsibility across the entire state ministries, rather than a niche issue for a single department. It ensures that revenues and expenditures are actively restructured to realise national gender equality objectives.

Promote Police-NGO Partnerships

The research highlights institutional mistrust due to police conduct and procedural insensitivity, which is a major barrier to reporting and prosecution. To address this, formal partnerships between law

enforcement and civil society organisations (CSOs) at the district level should be mandated and funded. This includes establishing regular dialogues, joint training sessions, and a clear division of roles. The model of Rwanda's Community-level Police Gender Desks and Families' Evening Forum is particularly relevant, as it shows how police can engage with communities to build trust and increase reporting. This approach allows the police to shift from reactive, disciplinary actions to a proactive, community-oriented one, a change that can be a powerful tool in preventing and responding to gender-based violence. By formalising partnerships with trusted CSOs, the state can bypass a cycle of distrust.

7.5 Technology Use

The rapid digital transformation presents a dual challenge and opportunity. While technology has opened new frontiers of violence, it also offers powerful tools for support and data collection. The analysis suggests that a strategic approach requires both leveraging technology for safety and simultaneously addressing the new forms of harm it can enable.

Deploy Survivor-Centric Technology and Apps

A key recommendation is to develop and promote a unified, multi-platform, and multilingual mobile application for reporting gender-based violence. Inspired by South Africa's Gender-Based Violence Command Centre, the app should offer multiple reporting channels, including text, audio, and video, and provide features for secure location sharing and discreet SOS alerts. The app should also integrate a comprehensive digital guide to legal rights and available resources. The analysis reveals that the rise of online gender-based violence, from cyberstalking to deepfakes, is a direct result of technology. A national reporting app can not only facilitate reporting but also bypass traditional gatekeepers, such as insensitive police officers or biased family members, and provide a direct, secure line of communication for a survivor.

Enhance Digital Literacy and Safety Education

To combat the rising tide of online harm, it is essential to launch comprehensive, multi-platform campaigns to improve digital literacy. These campaigns should focus on raising awareness about online risks like doxxing, non-consensual sharing of sexual images, and deepfakes. The campaigns should also provide practical steps for securing personal data and digital identities, especially for women and girls. The vulnerability of women and girls to online abuse is not just a matter of technical knowledge but is also rooted in social norms that normalise such acts, as seen in the

Bulli Bai and Sulli Deals cases. A digital literacy campaign must therefore go beyond technical training and incorporate a strong gender-equality message to be effective.

Ensure Data Privacy and Safeguards

While the IT Rules, 2021, provide a step in the right direction for platform accountability, the analysis indicates that the law is only as strong as its enforcement. The advancement of deepfakes and AI-generated content, which outpaces enforcement, requires a more proactive regulatory approach that shifts the burden of prevention onto the platforms themselves. A crucial recommendation is to strictly enforce *the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023* by holding intermediaries accountable for 24-hour takedown of non-consensual sexual imagery and for implementing robust grievance redressal mechanisms. Mandatory, third-party audits of these platforms should be conducted to ensure compliance. The problem of cross-border jurisdiction and the failure of platforms to provide adequate safeguards are major challenges to combating online abuse, and a proactive policy is necessary to address these issues.

8 Conclusion

8.1 A Multidimensional Crisis of Gender-Based Violence

Gender-based violence in India is a pervasive and deeply rooted issue that extends beyond the boundaries of caste, class, religion, gender, identity, and geography. Violence is not merely an individual act, but a systemic problem supported by unequal power relations and existing patriarchal structures. The typologies of violence are diverse and evolving, ranging from the persistent issues of domestic and intimate partner violence and dowry deaths to newer forms like online gender-based violence, and intersectional forms like caste- and religion-based violence. The data from the NCRB and NFHS reports have consistently shown a high prevalence of violence, which disproportionately impacts marginalised communities, including Dalit, Adivasi, and Muslim women, as well as the LGBTQ+ community. The impacts of gender-based violence inflict not only severe physical and mental health damages but also significant economic and educational burdens and a chilling effect on political and civic participation. The inter-generational transmission of trauma ensures that the burden of violence is borne by future generations, which creates a vicious cycle of harm.

8.2 Reflections on Systemic Challenges and Emerging Opportunities

Despite laws like the *Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA)* and the *POCSO Act*, significant gaps remain in India's response to gender-based violence. There are fundamental gaps between law and practice, with persistent issues of under-reporting, investigation delays, and low conviction rates. The criminalisation of marital rape remains a major legal and human rights issue. Furthermore, the institutional response is often fragmented, under-resourced, and hindered by a lack of gender sensitivity and institutional trust.

However, the challenges are met with significant emerging developments. The rise of digital infrastructure and a mobilised, feminist civil society presents new avenues for intervention. Technology can be a powerful tool for safe reporting, data collection, and raising awareness. Similarly, the growing public discussions on gender-based violence, motivated by social movements like Argentina's *Ni Una Menos*, indicate a growing demand for accountability and change. The ongoing work of organisations like MAVA in engaging men and boys is a critical opportunity to reframe gender-based violence as a societal issue and address its root causes. The Thuthuzela Care Centre model in South Africa and the mobile courts in Malawi are not just interesting case studies. They are direct solutions to India's core problem of fragmented and inaccessible services. These models suggest that a meaningful response to gender-based violence in India must move beyond a slow and gradual approach to a fully integrated, cohesive, and context-sensitive system that addresses the legal, institutional, and social dimensions of the problem simultaneously.

8.3 A Call for Integrated, Inclusive, and Context-Sensitive Interventions

The findings of this report culminate in a compelling call for a transformative, intersectional, and multi-stakeholder strategy to combat gender-based violence in India. This approach requires a paradigm shift from viewing gender-based violence as an issue of individual crime to a systemic failure of institutions and social structures.

The response must be integrated, with legal reforms supported by strong institutions, and justice systems working in coordination with health, education, and social welfare services. This means fully operationalising One Stop Centres, streamlining police-NGO partnerships, and mandating a convergence of ministries through gender-responsive budgeting.

Interventions must be inclusive and context-sensitive, designed to the unique needs of women, girls, and LGBTQ+ persons from marginalised communities in mind. This requires moving beyond a one-size-fits-all approach to actively combatting symbolic, structural, and institutional violence.

Finally, any intervention must be context-sensitive, drawing lessons from global best practices while adapting them to India's unique sociocultural realities. The struggle against gender-based violence is a struggle for justice, dignity, and equality for all, and its success hinges on a collective commitment to build a violence-free future.

9 Way Forward

This working paper has provided a comprehensive overview of gender-based violence (GBV) in India through a synthesis of historical context, typologies, impacts, institutional responses, and comparative international practices. As a review of existing evidence and frameworks, it has laid the groundwork for deeper analytical and empirical exploration. The next phase of this research will move toward developing an integrated conceptual framework that connects the structural, social, and institutional dimensions of GBV. This framework will aim to explain how gendered power relations intersect with caste, class, religion, sexuality, and geography to shape patterns of violence and influence survivors' access to justice and support.

Future analysis will also build on the thematic areas identified in this paper. The study of domestic and intimate partner violence will be expanded to include changing family dynamics, migration, and economic insecurity. The examination of dowry deaths and caste- and religion-based violence will be deepened through intersectional and regional analyses. The exploration of digital and cyber violence will consider the implications of new technologies, data governance, and platform accountability for women's and gender-diverse persons' safety. The linkages between GBV and economic, educational, and political exclusion will also be analysed to understand how violence limits participation and empowerment.

Further work will examine how institutional mechanisms such as laws, courts, police systems, and commissions can be strengthened through better coordination, accountability, and resourcing. Global lessons discussed in this paper, such as integrated survivor services, preventive education, and community-led justice models, will be assessed for their

adaptability in India's socio-legal context. The forthcoming analysis will thus focus on translating the insights from this synthesis into a cohesive, context-sensitive framework that informs actionable strategies for prevention, protection, and prosecution. Building on this comprehensive foundation, the next stage of research will aim to advance a more analytical, evidence-based, and survivor-centred understanding of GBV in India.

Tables

Table 1

Crime Against Women (IPC+SLL), 2021–2023

Crime Against Women (IPC+SLL), 2021–2023							
S. No.	State/UT	2021	2022	2023	Mid-Year Projected Population (in Lakhs) (2023)	Rate of Total Crime Against Women (2023)	Charge Sheet Rate (2023)
STATES:							
1	Andhra Pradesh	17,752	25,503	22,418	266.1	84.2	95.2
2	Arunachal Pradesh	366	335	326	7.6	42.8	71.4
3	Assam	29,046	14,148	12,070	176.0	68.6	65.2
4	Bihar	17,950	20,222	22,952	611.9	37.5	75.5
5	Chhattisgarh	7,344	8,693	8,035	151.0	53.2	76.5
6	Goa	224	273	286	7.8	36.5	74.2
7	Gujarat	7,348	7,731	7,805	341.1	22.9	89.0
8	Haryana	16,658	16,743	15,758	142.9	110.3	56.0
9	Himachal Pradesh	1,599	1,551	1,604	36.9	43.5	72.9
10	Jharkhand	8,110	7,678	6,989	193.6	36.1	78.9
11	Karnataka	14,468	17,813	20,336	334.2	60.9	81.2
12	Kerala	13,539	15,213	16,025	186.2	86.1	93.7
13	Madhya Pradesh	30,673	32,765	32,342	421.2	76.8	81.2
14	Maharashtra	39,526	45,331	47,101	608.0	77.5	80.8
15	Manipur	302	248	201	16.1	12.5	69.6
16	Meghalaya	685	690	628	16.8	37.5	75.0
17	Mizoram	176	147	184	6.2	29.9	97.8
18	Nagaland	54	49	56	10.8	5.2	76.5
19	Odisha	31,352	23,648	25,914	230.5	112.4	73.4
20	Punjab	5,662	5,572	5,258	146.3	35.9	73.6

21	Rajasthan	40,738	45,058	45,450	396.0	114.8	53.6
22	Sikkim	130	179	134	3.3	41.0	76.6
23	Tamil Nadu	8,501	9,207	8,943	385.4	23.2	91.0
24	Telangana	20,865	22,066	23,678	189.6	124.9	88.1
25	Tripura	807	752	791	20.4	38.7	89.6
26	Uttar Pradesh	56,083	65,743	66,381	1133.5	58.6	77.1
27	Uttarakhand	3,431	4,337	3,808	56.9	66.9	71.3
28	West Bengal	35,884	34,738	34,691	486.4	71.3	93.8
	TOTAL STATE(S)	4,09,273	4,26,433	4,30,164	6582.6	65.3	77.9
UNION TERRITORIES:							
29	A&N Islands	169	178	205	1.9	107.3	92.4
30	Chandigarh	343	325	371	5.7	65.2	63.5
31	D&N Haveli and Daman & Diu	99	126	124	4.4	28.4	70.8
32	Delhi	14,277	14,247	13439	100.6	133.6	69.9
33	Jammu & Kashmir	3,937	3,716	3653	65.0	56.2	70.1
34	Ladakh	18	15	20	1.3	15.2	78.6
35	Lakshadweep	9	16	23	0.3	69.7	81.0
36	Puducherry	153	200	212	8.7	24.4	93.2
	TOTAL UT(S)	19,005	18,823	18,047	187.9	96.1	70.3
	TOTAL-ALL INDIA	4,28,278	4,45,256	4,48,211	6770.4	66.2	77.6

Source: Crime in India 2023 (National Crime Records Bureau).

Notes on Data and Interpretation

- *Crime Rate* is calculated as the number of crimes reported per one lakh population.
- *Population Source*: Report of the Technical Group on Population Projections (July 2020), National Commission on Population, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare (MoHFW).
- The figures are based on data provided by individual States/UTs. Clarifications are still pending from Nagaland.

- Crime statistics should not be used for direct comparison across States/UTs, as variations may arise from differences in reporting practices, population distribution, and local contexts.

Table 2

State and Union Territory-wise Dowry Deaths under Section 304B of IPC, 2023 (Highest Incidents to lowest, reported)

S. No.	State/UT	Dowry Deaths (Sec. 304B IPC) (I)	V	R
1	Uttar Pradesh	2122	2141	1.9
2	Bihar	1143	1143	1.9
3	Madhya Pradesh	468	469	1.1
4	Rajasthan	428	430	1.1
5	West Bengal	350	350	0.7
6	Odisha	231	231	1.0
7	Jharkhand	218	228	1.1
8	Haryana	207	211	1.4
9	Karnataka	156	160	0.5
10	Telangana	145	147	0.8
11	Assam	101	107	0.6
12	Andhra Pradesh	95	96	0.4
13	Maharashtra	170	173	0.3
14	Uttarakhand	48	48	0.8
15	Chhattisgarh	46	49	0.3
16	Punjab	44	44	0.3
17	Tripura	21	21	1.0
18	Gujarat	12	12	0.0
19	Tamil Nadu	11	11	0.0
20	Kerala	8	8	0.0
21	Jammu & Kashmir	9	9	0.1
22	Arunachal Pradesh	1	1	0.1
23	Goa	1	1	0.1
24	Manipur	1	1	0.1

25	Puducherry	1	1	0.1
26	Himachal Pradesh	0	0	0.0
27	Meghalaya	0	0	0.0
28	Mizoram	0	0	0.0
29	Nagaland	0	0	0.0
30	Sikkim	0	0	0.0
31	A&N Islands	0	0	0.0
32	D&N Haveli and Daman & Diu	0	0	0.0
33	Ladakh	0	0	0.0
34	Lakshadweep	0	0	0.0
35	Chandigarh	4	4	0.7
TOTAL STATES		6027	6082	0.9
TOTAL UTs		129	129	0.7
TOTAL ALL INDIA		6156	6211	0.9

*Note: Incidents=I, Victims=V, Rate=R.

Source: Crime in India 2023 (National Crime Records Bureau).

Table 3

IPC Crimes—Kidnapping & Abduction of Women

S. No.	State/UT	Kidnapping & Abduction of Women (Total)			Kidnapping and Abduction (Sec. 363 IPC)			Kidnapping and Abduction in order to Murder (Sec.364 IPC)		
		I	V	R	I	V	R	I	V	R
1	Andhra Pradesh	524	546	2.0	334	355	1.3	1	1	0.0
2	Arunachal Pradesh	38	39	5.0	28	29	3.7	0	0	0.0
3	Assam	3110	3310	17.7	645	731	3.7	3	3	0.0
4	Bihar	12136	12194	19.8	868	878	1.4	6	6	0.0
5	Chhattisgarh	2440	2477	16.2	2345	2382	15.5	0	0	0.0
6	Goa	51	53	6.5	41	43	5.2	0	0	0.0
7	Gujarat	1257	1283	3.7	646	665	1.9	0	0	0.0
8	Haryana	3204	3238	22.4	366	376	2.6	3	3	0.0
9	Himachal Pradesh	351	361	9.5	200	209	5.4	0	0	0.0

10	Jharkhand	1253	1253	6.5	93	93	0.5	4	4	0.0
11	Karnataka	2327	2447	7.0	2256	2297	6.8	1	1	0.0
12	Kerala	191	205	1.0	104	115	0.6	1	1	0.0
13	Madhya Pradesh	8557	9140	20.3	6833	7413	16.2	1	1	0.0
14	Maharashtra	9361	10054	15.4	9147	9804	15.0	2	2	0.0
15	Manipur	32	34	2.0	2	2	0.1	0	0	0.0
16	Meghalaya	54	76	3.2	32	54	1.9	0	0	0.0
17	Mizoram	1	1	0.2	0	0	0.0	1	1	0.2
18	Nagaland	7	7	0.6	4	4	0.4	0	0	0.0
19	Odisha	5611	5614	24.3	5400	5403	23.4	1	1	0.0
20	Punjab	1430	1463	9.8	12	13	0.1	1	1	0.0
21	Rajasthan	7522	7663	19.0	4528	4584	11.4	0	0	0.0
22	Sikkim	15	22	4.6	14	21	4.3	0	0	0.0
23	Tamil Nadu	290	291	0.8	57	58	0.1	0	0	0.0
24	Telangana	2152	2282	11.4	1816	1937	9.6	0	0	0.0
25	Tripura	111	114	5.4	36	37	1.8	1	1	0.0
26	Uttar Pradesh	14272	15074	12.6	3613	4367	3.2	19	19	0.0
27	Uttarakhand	698	743	12.3	136	136	2.4	0	0	0.0
28	West Bengal	6544	6920	13.5	3935	4043	8.1	6	6	0.0
	TOTAL STATE(S)	83539	86904	12.7	43491	46049	6.6	51	51	0.0
29	A&N Islands	16	16	8.4	16	16	8.4	0	0	0.0
30	Chandigarh	131	138	23.0	119	125	20.9	0	0	0.0
31	D&N Haveli and Daman & Diu	35	35	8.0	34	34	7.8	0	0	0.0
32	Delhi	3970	4089	39.5	3838	3952	38.2	0	0	0.0
33	Jammu & Kashmir	895	911	13.8	351	366	5.4	2	2	0.0
34	Ladakh	3	4	2.3	3	4	2.3	0	0	0.0
35	Lakshadweep	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
36	Puducherry	16	17	1.8	15	15	1.7	0	0	0.0
	TOTAL UT(S)	5066	5210	27.0	4376	4512	23.3	2	2	0.0
	TOTAL ALL INDIA	88605	92114	13.1	47867	50561	7.1	53	53	0.0

*Note: Incidents=I, Victims=V, Rate=R.

Source: Crime in India 2023 (National Crime Records Bureau).

Table 4*IPC Crimes—Kidnapping & Abduction of Women (Continued)*

S. No.	State/UT	Kidnapping for Ransom (Sec. 364A IPC)			K&A of Women to compel her for marriage (Total)			a) Women (Above 18 yrs)		
		I	V	R	I	V	R	I	V	R
1	Andhra Pradesh	5	6	0.0	132	132	0.5	58	58	0.2
2	Arunachal Pradesh	1	1	0.1	3	3	0.4	2	2	0.3
3	Assam	15	15	0.1	1371	1389	7.8	1000	1018	5.7
4	Bihar	2	2	0.0	9467	9486	15.5	4534	4545	7.4
5	Chhattisgarh	0	0	0.0	77	77	0.5	1	1	0.0
6	Goa	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
7	Gujarat	1	1	0.0	567	573	1.7	43	43	0.1
8	Haryana	0	0	0.0	968	970	6.8	656	657	4.6
9	Himachal Pradesh	0	0	0.0	144	144	3.9	13	13	0.4
10	Jharkhand	5	5	0.0	775	775	4.0	620	620	3.2
11	Karnataka	18	19	0.1	29	30	0.1	21	22	0.1
12	Kerala	0	0	0.0	39	40	0.2	15	16	0.1
13	Madhya Pradesh	3	3	0.0	1673	1675	4.0	51	52	0.1
14	Maharashtra	8	8	0.0	138	152	0.2	47	58	0.1
15	Manipur	1	1	0.1	12	13	0.7	7	8	0.4
16	Meghalaya	9	9	0.5	6	6	0.4	3	3	0.2
17	Mizoram	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
18	Nagaland	1	1	0.1	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
19	Odisha	8	8	0.0	64	64	0.3	4	4	0.0
20	Punjab	0	0	0.0	1383	1413	9.5	105	106	0.7
21	Rajasthan	11	12	0.0	1546	1624	3.9	884	961	2.2
22	Sikkim	0	0	0.0	1	1	0.3	0	0	0.0
23	Tamil Nadu	5	5	0.0	193	193	0.5	92	92	0.2
24	Telangana	0	0	0.0	220	222	1.2	97	97	0.5
25	Tripura	0	0	0.0	29	30	1.4	8	9	0.4

26	Uttar Pradesh	2	2	0.0	10627	10675	9.4	6978	7007	6.2
27	Uttarakhand	0	0	0.0	82	86	1.4	79	79	1.4
28	West Bengal	17	17	0.0	515	516	1.1	125	125	0.3
TOTAL STATE(S)		112	115	0.0	30061	30289	4.6	15443	15596	2.3
UNION TERRITORIES:										
29	A&N Islands	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
30	Chandigarh	0	0	0.0	9	9	1.6	0	0	0.0
31	D&N Haveli and Daman & Diu	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
32	Delhi	3	3	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
33	Jammu & Kashmir	0	0	0.0	426	427	6.6	416	417	6.4
34	Ladakh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
35	Lakshadweep	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
36	Puducherry	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
TOTAL UT(S)		3	3	0.0	435	436	2.3	416	417	2.2
TOTAL ALL INDIA		115	118	0.0	30496	30725	4.5	15859	16013	2.3

*Note: Incidents=I, Victims=V, Rate=R.

Source: Crime in India 2023 (National Crime Records Bureau).

Table 5

Crimes Against Women: Buying of Minor Girls & Rape (2023)

S. No	State/UT	Buying of Minor Girls (Sec. 373 IPC)			Rape (Sec.376 IPC)			A) Women (18 Yrs. And above)			B) Girls (Below 18 yrs)		
		I	V	R	I	V	R	I	V	R	I	V	R
	STATES:												
1	Andhra Pradesh	2	2	0.0	438	458	1.6	438	458	1.6	0	0	0.0
2	Arunachal Pradesh	0	0	0.0	71	72	9.3	35	35	4.6	36	37	4.7

3	Assam	0	0	0.0	989	1033	5.6	988	1032	5.6	1	1	0.0
4	Bihar	0	0	0.0	902	902	1.5	902	902	1.5	0	0	0.0
5	Chhattisgarh	0	0	0.0	1171	1171	7.8	1171	1171	7.8	0	0	0.0
6	Goa	0	0	0.0	97	98	12.4	35	35	4.5	62	63	7.9
7	Gujarat	0	0	0.0	634	637	1.9	632	635	1.9	2	2	0.0
8	Haryana	0	0	0.0	1772	1772	12.4	1769	1769	12.4	3	3	0.0
9	Himachal Pradesh	0	0	0.0	344	345	9.3	138	138	3.7	206	207	5.6
10	Jharkhand	0	0	0.0	1221	1221	6.3	1071	1071	5.5	150	150	0.8
11	Karnataka	0	0	0.0	656	658	2.0	656	658	2.0	0	0	0.0
12	Kerala	0	0	0.0	843	845	4.5	843	845	4.5	0	0	0.0
13	Madhya Pradesh	2	2	0.0	2979	2979	7.1	2979	2979	7.1	0	0	0.0
14	Maharashtra	0	0	0.0	2930	2932	4.8	2930	2932	4.8	0	0	0.0
15	Manipur	0	0	0.0	27	27	1.7	27	27	1.7	0	0	0.0
16	Meghalaya	0	0	0.0	66	69	3.9	66	69	3.9	0	0	0.0
17	Mizoram	0	0	0.0	36	36	5.9	28	28	4.6	8	8	1.3
18	Nagaland	0	0	0.0	10	10	0.9	7	7	0.6	3	3	0.3
19	Odisha	0	0	0.0	1195	1195	5.2	1193	1193	5.2	2	2	0.0
20	Punjab	0	0	0.0	457	459	3.1	457	459	3.1	0	0	0.0
21	Rajasthan	0	0	0.0	5078	5194	12.8	5078	5194	12.8	0	0	0.0
22	Sikkim	0	0	0.0	9	9	2.8	9	9	2.8	0	0	0.0
23	Tamil Nadu	0	0	0.0	365	365	0.9	365	365	0.9	0	0	0.0
24	Telangana	0	0	0.0	817	817	4.3	814	814	4.3	3	3	0.0
25	Tripura	0	0	0.0	57	57	2.8	57	57	2.8	0	0	0.0
26	Uttar Pradesh	0	0	0.0	3516	3556	3.1	3215	3255	2.8	301	301	0.3
27	Uttarakhand	0	0	0.0	421	421	7.4	421	421	7.4	0	0	0.0
28	West Bengal	0	0	0.0	1110	1112	2.3	1110	1112	2.3	0	0	0.0
TOTAL STATE(S)		4	4	0.0	28211	28450	4.3	27434	27670	4.2	777	780	0.1
UNION TERRITORIES:													
29	A&N Islands	0	0	0.0	14	14	7.3	14	14	7.3	0	0	0.0
30	Chandigarh	0	0	0.0	102	102	17.9	32	32	5.6	70	70	12.3

31	D&N Haveli and Daman & Diu	0	0	0.0	6	6	1.4	5	5	1.1	1	1	0.2
32	Delhi	0	0	0.0	1094	1094	10.9	1094	1094	10.9	0	0	0.0
33	Jammu & Kashmir	0	0	0.0	231	231	3.6	230	230	3.5	1	1	0.0
34	Ladakh	0	0	0.0	2	2	1.5	2	2	1.5	0	0	0.0
35	Lakshadweep	0	0	0.0	1	1	3.0	1	1	3.0	0	0	0.0
36	Puducherry	0	0	0.0	9	9	1.0	9	9	1.0	0	0	0.0
TOTAL UT(S)		0	0	0.0	1459	1459	7.8	1387	1387	7.4	72	72	0.4
TOTAL ALL INDIA		4	4	0.0	29670	29909	4.4	28821	29057	4.3	849	852	0.1

**Note: Incidents=I, Victims=V, Rate=R.*

Source: Crime in India 2023 (National Crime Records Bureau).

Table 6*Crimes Against Women: Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956 (2023)*

S. No.	State/UT	Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956 (Total)			A) Procuring, inducing Children for the sake of prostitution (Sec. 5)			B) Detaining a person in premises where prostitution is carried on (Sec. 6)		
		I	V	R	I	V	R	I	V	R
1	Andhra Pradesh	68	84	0.3	11	12	0.0	1	4	0.0
2	Arunachal Pradesh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
3	Assam	30	31	0.2	3	3	0.0	0	0	0.0
4	Bihar	58	90	0.1	29	55	0.0	11	11	0.0
5	Chhattisgarh	12	14	0.1	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
6	Goa	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
7	Gujarat	80	144	0.2	6	11	0.0	22	50	0.1
8	Haryana	38	38	0.3	11	11	0.1	2	2	0.0
9	Himachal Pradesh	10	19	0.3	6	9	0.2	0	0	0.0
10	Jharkhand	2	2	0.0	0	0	0.0	1	1	0.0
11	Karnataka	308	548	0.9	106	186	0.3	94	190	0.3
12	Kerala	13	15	0.1	0	0	0.0	1	3	0.0
13	Madhya Pradesh	21	39	0.0	5	11	0.0	2	4	0.0
14	Maharashtra	211	320	0.3	39	62	0.1	23	69	0.0
15	Manipur	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
16	Meghalaya	1	1	0.1	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
17	Mizoram	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
18	Nagaland	1	2	0.1	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
19	Odisha	15	18	0.1	3	3	0.0	0	0	0.0
20	Punjab	39	58	0.3	2	2	0.0	0	0	0.0
21	Rajasthan	16	17	0.0	6	7	0.0	0	0	0.0
22	Sikkim	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
23	Tamil Nadu	619	904	1.6	147	189	0.4	81	114	0.2

24	Telangana	57	67	0.3	15	22	0.1	0	0	0.0
25	Tripura	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
26	Uttar Pradesh	53	57	0.0	7	7	0.0	8	9	0.0
27	Uttarakhand	26	33	0.5	6	13	0.1	6	6	0.1
28	West Bengal	32	56	0.1	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
	TOTAL STATE(S)	1710	2557	0.3	402	603	0.1	252	463	0.0
	UNION TERRITORIES:									
29	A&N Islands	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
30	Chandigarh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
31	D&N Haveli and Daman & Diu	8	8	1.8	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
32	Delhi	59	68	0.6	1	1	0.0	1	1	0.0
33	Jammu & Kashmir	8	10	0.1	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
34	Ladakh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
35	Lakshadweep	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
36	Puducherry	3	5	0.3	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
	TOTAL UT(S)	78	91	0.4	1	1	0.0	1	1	0.0
	TOTAL ALL INDIA	1788	2648	0.3	403	604	0.1	253	464	0.0

*Note: Incidents=I, Victims=V, Rate=R.

Source: Crime in India 2023 (National Crime Records Bureau).

Table 7

Crimes Against Women: Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956, Section-wise (2023)

S. No.	State/UT	C) Prostitution in or in the vicinity of public places (Section 7)			D) Seducing or soliciting for purpose of prostitution (Section 8)			E) Other Sections under ITP Act		
		I	V	R	I	V	R	I	V	R
1	Andhra Pradesh	11	11	0.0	0	0	0.0	45	57	0.2
2	Arunachal Pradesh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
3	Assam	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	27	28	0.2
4	Bihar	2	3	0.0	0	0	0.0	16	21	0.0
5	Chhattisgarh	11	12	0.1	0	0	0.0	1	2	0.0
6	Goa	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
7	Gujarat	42	68	0.1	1	1	0.0	9	14	0.0
8	Haryana	9	9	0.1	0	0	0.0	16	16	0.1
9	Himachal Pradesh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	4	10	0.1
10	Jharkhand	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	1	1	0.0
11	Karnataka	37	66	0.1	3	12	0.0	68	94	0.2
12	Kerala	3	3	0.0	1	1	0.0	8	8	0.0
13	Madhya Pradesh	9	12	0.0	2	2	0.0	3	10	0.0
14	Maharashtra	26	34	0.0	73	73	0.1	50	82	0.1
15	Manipur	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
16	Meghalaya	1	1	0.1	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
17	Mizoram	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
18	Nagaland	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	1	2	0.1
19	Odisha	0	0	0.0	7	10	0.0	5	5	0.0
20	Punjab	4	22	0.0	2	2	0.0	31	32	0.2
21	Rajasthan	3	3	0.0	0	0	0.0	7	7	0.0
22	Sikkim	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
23	Tamil Nadu	38	71	0.1	32	33	0.1	321	497	0.8

24	Telangana	0	0	0.0	1	2	0.0	41	43	0.2
25	Tripura	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
26	Uttar Pradesh	9	12	0.0	1	1	0.0	28	28	0.0
27	Uttarakhand	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	14	14	0.2
28	West Bengal	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	32	56	0.1
	TOTAL STATE(S)	205	327	0.0	123	137	0.0	728	1027	0.1
	UNION TERRITORIES:									
29	A&N Islands	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
30	Chandigarh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
31	D&N Haveli and Daman & Diu	8	8	1.8	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
32	Delhi	0	0	0.0	1	5	0.0	56	61	0.6
33	Jammu & Kashmir	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	8	10	0.1
34	Ladakh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
35	Lakshadweep	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
36	Puducherry	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	3	5	0.3
	TOTAL UT(S)	8	8	0.0	1	5	0.0	67	76	0.4
	TOTAL ALL INDIA	213	335	0.0	124	142	0.0	795	1103	0.1

Source: Crime in India 2023 (National Crime Records Bureau)

Table 8*Cyber Crimes against Women - 2023*

Cyber Crimes against Women - 2023							
State/UT	Cyber Blackmailing / Threatening (Sec.506, 503, 384 IPC r/w IT Act)	Cyber Pornography / Hosting/ Publishing Obscene Sexual Materials (Sec.67A/67B (Girl Child) of IT act r/w other IPC/SLL)	Cyber Stalking/ Cyber Bullying of Women (Sec.354D IPC r/w IT Act)	Defamation/ Morphing (Sec.469 IPC r/w IPC and Indecent Rep. of Women (P) Act & IT Act)	Fake Profile (IT Act r/w IPC/SLL)	Other Crimes against Women	Total Cyber Crimes against Women
STATES:							
Andhra Pradesh	10	68	151	1	0	329	559
Arunachal Pradesh	0	0	0	0	0	4	4
Assam	11	97	2	74	0	285	469
Bihar	31	20	75	9	40	469	644
Chhattisgarh	3	195	0	0	0	44	242
Goa	1	8	0	0	0	19	28
Gujarat	9	45	43	0	0	356	453
Haryana	6	96	39	1	0	240	382
Himachal Pradesh	0	21	2	0	0	17	40

Jharkhand	0	12	7	0	0	1	20
Karnataka	0	457	4	1	0	6540	7002
Kerala	5	333	51	2	29	402	822
Madhya Pradesh	12	38	68	2	0	193	313
Maharashtra	18	40	415	0	23	2006	2502
Manipur	0	0	0	0	0	6	6
Meghalaya	0	9	0	1	0	19	29
Mizoram	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nagaland	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Odisha	0	358	0	403	0	0	761
Punjab	7	27	14	2	1	76	127
Rajasthan	10	212	97	0	3	199	521
Sikkim	0	4	0	0	0	4	8
Tamil Nadu	14	76	27	1	0	944	1062
Telangana	38	78	295	2	2	1032	1447
Tripura	0	13	0	0	0	1	14
Uttar Pradesh	92	389	18	2	2	960	1463
Uttarakhand	26	51	7	0	0	60	144
West Bengal	3	6	23	0	0	144	176
TOTAL STATE(S)	296	2654	1338	501	100	14350	19239

UNION TERRITORIES:							
A&N Islands	2	27	0	0	0	8	37
Chandigarh	0	5	1	0	0	11	17
D&N Haveli and Daman & Diu	0	3	0	0	0	0	3
Delhi	6	28	18	0	2	81	135
Jammu & Kashmir	0	39	1	4	0	24	68
Ladakh	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lakshadweep	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Puducherry	0	10	0	0	0	0	10
TOTAL UT(S)	8	113	20	4	2	124	271
TOTAL ALL INDIA	304	2767	1358	505	102	14474	19510

Source: Crime in India 2023 (National Crime Records Bureau).

Table 9

Special and Local Laws crimes (SLL) Crimes Against Women under the IT Act (State/UT-wise, 2023) (Cyber Crimes/Information Technology Act–Women Centric Crimes only)

Cyber Crimes/Information Technology Act (Women Centric Crimes only)										
S. No.	State/UT	Cyber Crimes/Information Technology Act (Women Centric Crimes only) (Total)			A) Publishing or Transmitting of Sexually Explicit Material (Sec. 67A/67B (Girls) IT Act)			B) Other Women Centric Cyber Crimes (Ex. Blackmailing/Defamation/Morphing/Fake Profile)		
		I	V	R	I	V	R	I	V	R
	STATES:									
1	Andhra Pradesh	79	87	0.3	68	76	0.3	11	11	0.0
2	Arunachal Pradesh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
3	Assam	182	186	1.0	97	101	0.6	85	85	0.5
4	Bihar	100	100	0.2	20	20	0.0	80	80	0.1
5	Chhattisgarh	198	199	1.3	195	196	1.3	3	3	0.0
6	Goa	9	18	1.1	8	17	1.0	1	1	0.1
7	Gujarat	54	54	0.2	45	45	0.1	9	9	0.0
8	Haryana	103	103	0.7	96	96	0.7	7	7	0.0
9	Himachal Pradesh	21	21	0.6	21	21	0.6	0	0	0.0
10	Jharkhand	12	12	0.1	12	12	0.1	0	0	0.0

11	Karnataka	458	478	1.4	457	477	1.4	1	1	0.0
12	Kerala	369	414	2.0	333	378	1.8	36	36	0.2
13	Madhya Pradesh	52	52	0.1	38	38	0.1	14	14	0.0
14	Maharashtra	81	83	0.1	40	42	0.1	41	41	0.1
15	Manipur	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
16	Meghalaya	10	15	0.6	9	14	0.5	1	1	0.1
17	Mizoram	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
18	Nagaland	1	1	0.1	1	1	0.1	0	0	0.0
19	Odisha	761	761	3.3	358	358	1.6	403	403	1.7
20	Punjab	37	37	0.3	27	27	0.2	10	10	0.1
21	Rajasthan	225	225	0.6	212	212	0.5	13	13	0.0
22	Sikkim	4	4	1.2	4	4	1.2	0	0	0.0
23	Tamil Nadu	91	91	0.2	76	76	0.2	15	15	0.0
24	Telangana	120	124	0.6	78	80	0.4	42	44	0.2
25	Tripura	13	13	0.6	13	13	0.6	0	0	0.0
26	Uttar Pradesh	485	495	0.4	389	399	0.3	96	96	0.1
27	Uttarakhand	77	77	1.4	51	51	0.9	26	26	0.5
28	West Bengal	9	9	0.0	6	6	0.0	3	3	0.0
TOTAL STATE(S)		3551	3659	0.5	2654	2760	0.4	897	899	0.1
UNION TERRITORIES:										
29	A&N Islands	29	29	15.2	27	27	14.1	2	2	1.0
30	Chandigarh	5	6	0.9	5	6	0.9	0	0	0.0

31	D&N Haveli and Daman & Diu	3	3	0.7	3	3	0.7	0	0	0.0
32	Delhi	36	36	0.4	28	28	0.3	8	8	0.1
33	Jammu & Kashmir	43	43	0.7	39	39	0.6	4	4	0.1
34	Ladakh	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0.0
35	Lakshadweep	1	1	3.0	1	1	3.0	0	0	0.0
36	Puducherry	10	10	1.1	10	10	1.1	0	0	0.0
TOTAL UT(S)		127	128	0.7	113	114	0.6	14	14	0.1
TOTAL ALL INDIA		3678	3787	0.5	2767	2874	0.4	911	913	0.1

*Note: I = Incidents (number of reported cases); V = Victims (number of individuals affected); R = Rate (crime rate per one lakh female population)

Source: Crime in India 2023 (National Crime Records Bureau)

Table 10*Experience of Physical Violence (Women Aged 18–49, India, 2019–2021)*

Background Characteristic	Ever Experienced Physical Violence (Since age 15)(%)	Experienced in Past 12 Months - Often (%)	Some times	Often or some times	Number of Women
Age					
18–19	16.4	1.5	10.0	11.5	4,907
20–24	22.8	2.8	15.0	17.8	12,190
25–29	28.1	3.5	19.2	22.8	12,040
30–39	31.9	3.9	20.6	24.5	23,613
40–49	32.1	4.0	20.2	24.2	19,306
Residence					
Urban	23.8	2.5	15.2	17.7	23,280
Rural	31.1	4.0	20.2	24.3	48,776
Schooling					
No schooling	39.3	5.5	26.1	31.5	18,294
<5 years complete	32.9	4.4	20.0	24.4	4,807
5–7 years complete	32.8	4.0	21.6	25.6	10,267
8–9 years complete	27.5	3.1	17.1	20.1	10,643
10–11 years complete	25.2	2.8	17.3	20.2	9,818
12 or more years complete	17.3	1.7	10.7	12.4	18,227
Employment (Past 12 Months)					
Not employed	25.2	2.9	16.8	19.7	47,249
Employed for cash	35.8	5.0	22.2	27.2	21,101
Employed not for cash	33.2	3.0	20.7	23.8	3,706
Marital Status					
Never married	12.9	1.0	6.9	7.8	9,600
Currently married	30.3	3.5	20.3	23.8	58,611
Married, <i>gauna</i> not performed	2.1	0.0	1.5	1.5	75

Widowed/Divorced/ Separated/Deserted	44.4	10.5	22.8	33.3	3,771
Household Structure					
Nuclear	30.6	3.6	19.7	23.3	36,509
Non-nuclear	26.8	3.4	17.5	20.9	35,547
Religion					
Hindu	29.7	3.7	19.4	23.1	56,423
Muslim	26.1	3.2	16.6	19.8	11,795
Christian	22.6	1.9	14.2	16.1	2,046
Sikh	11.7	1.7	6.6	8.3	646
Buddhist/Neo- Buddhist	29.5	3.9	17.8	21.7	732
Jain	18.2	0.9	4.4	5.2	186
Other	30.7	1.3	15.7	17.0	227
Caste/Tribe					
Scheduled Caste	33.9	4.5	22.1	26.6	14,959
Scheduled Tribe	31.0	4.1	19.5	23.6	6,409
Other Backward Class	30.0	3.5	20.1	23.6	30,055
Other	22.3	2.7	13.6	16.3	20,153
Don't Know	23.5	1.2	14.8	16.0	480
Wealth Quintile					
Lowest	37.7	5.7	24.1	29.8	13,270
Second	35.1	4.3	23.3	27.6	14,936
Middle	29.7	3.6	19.3	22.9	15,311
Fourth	24.1	2.5	15.4	17.9	15,263
Highest	16.8	1.5	10.8	12.2	13,276
Total	28.7	3.5	18.6	22.1	72,056

Note: Includes violence in the past 12 months. For women who were married before age 15 and who reported physical violence by their husband, the violence could have occurred before age 15.

Nuclear households are households comprised of a married couple or a man or a woman living alone or with unmarried children (biological, adopted, or fostered) with or without unrelated individuals. The remaining households are non-nuclear households.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 11

Persons Committing Physical Violence (Women Aged 18–49, India, 2019–2021)

Person Committing Violence	Ever Married (%)	Never Married (%)	Total (%)
Current husband/partner	82.9	NA	78.0
Former husband/partner	8.8	na	8.3
Current boyfriend	0.2	1.0	0.2
Former boyfriend	0.1	0.9	0.1
Father/step-father	7.9	35.7	9.5
Mother/step-mother	12.2	60.3	15.1
Sister/brother	5.2	24.9	6.4
Daughter/son	0.3	1.7	0.3
Other relative	1.3	3.5	1.4
Mother-in-law	0.7	na	0.7
Father-in-law	0.3	na	0.3
Other in-law	0.6	na	0.6
Teacher	1.2	8.0	1.6
Employer/someone at work	0.0	0.0	0.0
Police/soldier	0.0	0.0	0.0
Other	0.5	1.4	0.6
Number of women who have experienced physical violence since age 15	19,459	1,237	20,696

Note: Women can report more than one person who committed the violence; NA=Not applicable.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 12*Experience of Sexual Violence (Women Aged 18–49, India, 2019–2021)*

Background Characteristic	% Ever Experienced Sexual Violence	Number of Women
Age		
18–19	3.5	4,907
20–24	4.2	12,190
25–29	6.2	12,040
30–39	7.0	23,613
40–49	6.5	19,306
Residence		
Urban	4.7	23,280
Rural	6.7	48,776
Schooling		
No schooling	8.8	18,294
<5 years complete	8.9	4,807
5–7 years complete	6.8	10,267
8–9 years complete	5.3	10,643
10–11 years complete	4.8	9,818
12 or more years complete	3.2	18,227
Marital Status		
Never married	1.8	9,600
Currently married	6.2	58,611
Married, <i>gauna</i> not performed	8.9	75
Widowed/divorced/separated/deserted	13.8	3,771
Household Structure		
Nuclear	6.4	36,509
Non-nuclear	5.7	35,547
Religion		
Hindu	6.0	56,423
Muslim	6.5	11,795
Christian	4.1	2,046
Sikh	2.5	646
Buddhist/Neo-Buddhist	7.2	732
Jain	2.0	186

Other	11.1	227
Caste/Tribe		
Scheduled caste	7.2	14,959
Scheduled tribe	6.5	6,409
Other backward class	5.6	30,055
Other	5.6	20,153
Don't know	5.5	480
Wealth Quintile		
Lowest	10.0	13,270
Second	7.6	14,936
Middle	5.4	15,311
Fourth	4.2	15,263
Highest	3.2	13,276
Total	6.0	72,056

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 13

Persons Committing Sexual Violence (Women Aged 18–49, India, 2019–2021)

Person Committing Sexual Violence	Ever Married (%)	Never Married (%)	<18 Years (%)	18 years or Higher (%)	Don't Know (%)	Total (%)
Current husband	82.0	NA	86.1	85.3	57.9	78.7
Former husband	13.7	NA	14.6	14.9	8.3	13.2
Current/former boyfriend	1.6	16.1	2.6	0.8	4.5	2.2
Father/step-father	0.9	3.5	0.5	0.3	2.9	1.0
Brother/step-brother	0.5	3.9	0.1	0.0	2.5	0.7
Other relative	2.3	39.3	2.3	0.4	12.0	3.8
In-law	0.3	na	0.2	0.0	0.9	0.3
Own friend/acquaintance	1.0	2.6	1.0	0.5	2.3	1.1
Family friend	0.4	11.7	0.5	0.0	2.8	0.8
Teacher	0.0	3.9	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.2
Employer/someone at work	0.3	1.8	0.1	0.3	0.7	0.3
Police/soldier	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.1
Priest/religious leader	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0
Stranger	0.2	5.2	0.1	0.0	1.5	0.4
Other	0.6	12.0	0.7	0.2	3.1	1.0
Number of Women	4,169	176	1,158	2,100	1,087	4,345

Notes: *NA = Not applicable.

*Includes women who report having ever experienced sexual violence committed only by their current husband if currently married or most recent husband if widowed, divorced, separated, or deserted. For these women, the age at first experience of sexual violence is not known.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 14

Experience of Different Types of Violence (Women Aged 18–49, India, 2019–2021)

Background Characteristic	Physical Violence Only (%)	Sexual Violence Only (%)	Physical & Sexual Violence (%)	Physical or Sexual Violence (%)
India (Total)	25.1	1.0	5.5	31.5
Residence				
Urban	21.0	0.9	4.0	25.9
Rural	27.1	1.0	6.2	34.3
Age				
18–19	14.6	1.3	2.4	18.3
20–24	20.4	1.0	3.4	24.7
25–29	24.5	1.1	5.5	31.0
30–39	27.7	0.9	6.7	35.3
40–49	28.2	0.9	6.1	35.2
Marital Status				
Ever married	27.2	1.0	6.2	34.4
Never married	12.1	0.9	0.9	13.9
Woman's Children				
Only sons	25.6	1.3	5.5	32.4
Only daughters	24.3	0.9	6.1	31.2
Sons and daughters	30.1	0.9	6.7	37.7
No children	15.1	1.0	2.5	18.6
North				
Chandigarh	6.7	0.0	2.1	8.8
Delhi	20.6	2.8	5.5	28.9
Haryana	15.1	0.9	3.1	19.1
Himachal Pradesh	8.6	0.5	1.7	10.7
Jammu & Kashmir	7.0	0.4	2.5	9.9
Ladakh	9.2	2.4	5.4	17.0
Punjab	12.8	0.6	1.9	15.3
Rajasthan	20.1	1.0	4.4	25.6
Uttarakhand	15.5	0.2	2.9	18.7

Central				
Chhattisgarh	14.7	0.9	4.0	19.6
Madhya Pradesh	23.8	0.6	5.0	29.4
Uttar Pradesh	29.6	0.8	5.3	35.7
East				
Bihar	34.7	1.1	7.3	43.1
Jharkhand	27.1	1.2	5.7	34.0
Odisha	28.5	1.2	4.2	33.9
West Bengal	20.6	1.6	8.1	30.4
Northeast				
Arunachal Pradesh	18.9	1.8	5.0	25.7
Assam	29.2	1.0	6.6	36.7
Manipur	34.3	0.7	3.6	38.7
Meghalaya	10.9	2.0	4.0	16.9
Mizoram	7.4	0.3	1.1	8.9
Nagaland	8.9	1.0	0.6	10.5
Sikkim	12.6	1.1	0.9	14.6
Tripura	22.8	1.2	6.2	30.3
West				
Dadra & Nagar Haveli and Daman & Diu	14.0	0.5	3.8	18.2
Goa	17.5	1.2	2.6	21.3
Gujarat	11.1	0.9	2.4	14.3
Maharashtra	21.0	1.2	5.1	27.3
South				
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	18.8	0.6	1.5	20.9
Andhra Pradesh	31.6	0.2	3.4	35.2
Karnataka	37.2	0.9	10.4	48.5
Kerala	8.4	0.4	1.0	9.7
Lakshadweep	2.0	0.6	0.0	2.6
Puducherry	40.7	1.0	0.6	42.3
Tamil Nadu	40.1	0.5	2.3	42.9
Telangana	35.4	0.4	4.3	40.1

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 15

Forms of Spousal Violence among Ever-Married Women (Aged 18–49, India, 2019–2021)

Type of Violence	Ever Experienced (%)
Physical Violence	
Any form of physical violence	28.3
Pushed her, shook her, or threw something	12.2
Twisted her arm or pulled her hair	10.1
Slapped her	25.3
Punched her with fist/weapon	7.7
Kicked, dragged, or beat her up	8.3
Tried to choke or burn her on purpose	2.3
Threatened/attacked with a knife, gun, or other weapon	1.2
Sexual Violence	
Any form of sexual violence	6.3
Physically forced sexual intercourse	4.6
Forced to perform sexual acts (unwanted)	2.4
Forced with threats/other ways into sexual acts	3.8
Emotional Violence	
Any form of emotional violence	14.0
Humiliated in front of others	9.6
Threatened to hurt her/someone close	5.9
Insulted/made her feel bad	8.6
Combined Violence	
Any form of physical and/or sexual violence	29.2
Any form of physical and sexual violence	5.4
Any form of physical/sexual/emotional violence	31.9
Any form of physical, sexual, and emotional violence	3.6
Spousal Violence by Any Husband	
Physical violence	28.4
Sexual violence	6.4
Physical and/or sexual violence	29.3
Number of Ever-married Women	62,381

Notes: Husband refers to the current husband for currently married women and the most recent husband for widowed, divorced, separated, or deserted women. *NA = Not applicable.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 16

Spousal Violence by Background Characteristics (Ever-Married Women Aged 18–49, India, 2019–2021)

Background Characteristic	Emotional Violence (%)	Physical Violence (%)	Sexual Violence (%)	Physical or Sexual (%)	Emotional, Physical, or Sexual (%)	Number of Women
Age						
18–19	10.5	18.8	7.1	20.9	24.6	1,475
20–24	12.2	24.3	5.4	25.4	28.2	7,923
25–29	13.4	27.1	6.2	28.0	30.7	10,757
30–39	14.4	29.4	6.7	30.2	32.8	23,128
40–49	15.0	29.9	6.1	30.8	33.7	19,098
Residence						
Urban	12.2	23.8	4.8	24.5	27.3	19,173
Rural	14.9	30.3	6.9	31.2	34.0	43,208
Schooling						
No schooling	17.9	37.1	8.4	38.1	40.6	17,887
<5 years complete	16.2	31.3	8.8	32.7	35.7	4,660
5–7 years complete	14.8	30.6	6.5	31.3	33.9	9,801
8–9 years complete	12.1	25.6	5.5	26.8	29.3	9,533
10–11 years complete	13.1	24.4	5.2	25.1	28.7	8,324

12 or more years complete	9.2	17.0	3.4	17.7	20.3	12,175
Marital Status						
Currently married	13.2	27.3	5.8	28.3	31.0	58,611
Widowed/divorced/separated/deserted	26.9	42.9	13.4	43.6	46.4	3,771
Number of Living Children						
0	12.9	19.4	5.3	20.3	23.6	5,460
1-2	13.3	25.8	5.6	26.7	29.5	35,518
3-4	15.5	34.0	7.0	34.9	37.4	17,652
5 or more	15.7	37.6	10.5	38.9	41.0	3,752
Household Structure						
Nuclear	14.8	31.0	6.9	32.0	34.6	30,740
Non-nuclear	13.3	25.7	5.7	26.5	29.3	31,641
Religion						
Hindu	14.2	29.1	6.2	29.9	32.7	49,365
Muslim	13.7	26.2	7.3	27.5	30.3	9,993
Christian	13.3	22.0	4.6	22.8	26.3	1,610
Sikh	6.7	10.3	3.0	10.9	12.4	489
Buddhist/Neo-Buddhist	16.8	28.1	6.8	29.2	31.8	615
Jain	2.1	20.2	0.6	20.2	20.2	136
Other	7.6	24.3	6.5	25.3	26.4	172
Caste/Tribe						
Scheduled caste	16.9	33.7	7.4	34.7	37.3	13,148
Scheduled tribe	15.2	30.9	6.7	31.8	34.7	5,520
Other backward class	13.6	29.5	6.0	30.2	32.9	26,168

Other	12.3	21.6	5.7	22.6	25.6	17,108
Don't know	7.7	22.5	6.1	23.4	24.2	438
Wealth Quintile						
Lowest	18.6	36.9	10.2	38.4	41.2	12,113
Second	16.0	34.3	7.8	35.2	37.9	13,231
Middle	14.6	28.9	5.7	29.7	32.7	13,260
Fourth	11.7	23.4	4.3	24.2	26.7	12,886
Highest	8.8	16.5	3.1	16.9	19.7	10,892
Father Beat Mother						
Yes	26.3	53.2	11.9	54.4	57.7	11,814
No	11.0	21.9	4.7	22.7	25.3	48,656
Don't know	16.5	36.6	10.7	37.9	41.0	1,911
Total	14.0	28.3	6.3	29.2	31.9	62,381

Notes: Husband refers to the current husband for currently married women and the most recent husband for widowed, divorced, separated, or deserted women.

Nuclear households are households comprised of a married couple or a man or a woman living alone or with unmarried children (biological, adopted, or fostered) with or without unrelated individuals. The remaining households are non-nuclear households.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 17*Spousal Violence by State/Union Territory (India, 2019–2021)*

State/UT	Emotional Violence (%)	Physical Violence (%)	Sexual Violence (%)	Physical or Sexual (%)	Emotional, Physical or Sexual (%)
India (Total)	14.0	28.3	6.3	29.2	31.9
North					
Chandigarh	4.5	9.7	2.3	9.7	11.8
Delhi	13.1	20.4	7.2	22.5	25.8
Haryana	10.2	16.7	4.2	17.9	20.6
Himachal Pradesh	6.9	8.3	2.0	8.6	10.7
Jammu & Kashmir	7.2	9.3	3.9	9.7	12.8
Ladakh	18.7	16.9	7.7	17.7	27.7
Punjab	7.8	11.0	2.7	11.6	13.4
Rajasthan	9.4	23.1	5.4	24.1	26.3
Uttarakhand	8.0	15.2	3.4	15.3	17.8
Central					
Chhattisgarh	6.1	19.3	4.9	20.1	21.0
Madhya Pradesh	14.8	27.4	5.8	28.0	31.0
Uttar Pradesh	12.9	34.1	6.6	34.9	37.3
East					
Bihar	17.0	39.2	8.1	40.1	42.5
Jharkhand	11.6	30.2	6.6	31.4	32.8
Odisha	9.9	29.3	5.3	30.3	32.4
West Bengal	16.3	25.1	9.0	26.9	29.7
Northeast					
Arunachal Pradesh	12.9	23.8	6.3	24.9	26.6
Assam	11.8	31.3	7.3	32.2	34.3
Manipur	11.0	38.5	5.0	39.6	41.6
Meghalaya	13.7	13.2	6.2	15.0	21.1
Mizoram	5.9	9.9	1.9	10.3	11.9
Nagaland	7.6	6.1	0.9	6.5	11.0

Sikkim	14.6	10.6	3.1	12.4	21.3
Tripura	11.4	19.3	6.2	20.7	23.2
West					
Dadra & Nagar Haveli and Daman & Diu	7.1	16.8	3.2	16.8	17.7
Goa	6.3	6.7	4.6	8.3	9.7
Gujarat	7.3	13.0	3.4	13.9	16.1
Maharashtra	12.9	24.4	5.7	25.2	28.2
South					
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	3.4	16.6	1.2	17.2	18.3
Andhra Pradesh	14.9	29.6	3.6	29.9	33.4
Karnataka	24.8	43.4	10.8	44.4	48.4
Kerala	6.8	9.4	1.5	9.8	12.9
Lakshadweep	0.5	0.5	0.8	1.3	1.3
Puducherry	7.9	29.3	1.4	30.0	31.0
Tamil Nadu	11.0	37.9	2.4	38.1	39.7
Telangana	18.6	36.7	4.5	37.2	40.4

Note: Husband refers to the current husband for currently married women and the most recent husband for widowed, divorced, separated, or deserted women.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 18

Injuries to Women Due to Spousal Violence (India, 2019–2021) Ever Experienced

Type of Violence Experienced	Cuts, Bruises, or Aches (%)	Severe Burns (%)	Eye Injuries, Sprains, Dislocations, Minor Burns (%)	Deep Wounds, Broken Bones, Teeth, Serious Injury (%)	Any Injury (%)	Number of Women
URBAN						
Physical violence	21.9	3.5	7.3	6.7	24.6	4,563
Sexual violence	41.8	13.3	19.6	19.2	47.1	926
Physical or sexual violence	21.3	3.4	7.1	6.5	24.0	4,708
Physical and sexual violence	49.0	15.6	23.1	22.5	54.8	781
RURAL						
Physical violence	22.5	3.4	7.5	6.2	25.6	13,080
Sexual violence	37.9	8.4	18.1	16.2	43.7	3,009
Physical or sexual violence	22.0	3.3	7.4	6.1	25.1	13,501
Physical and sexual violence	42.8	9.6	20.5	18.5	49.3	2,588
TOTAL (Urban + Rural)						
Physical violence	22.3	3.4	7.4	6.4	25.3	17,643
Sexual violence	38.9	9.5	18.5	16.9	44.5	3,935

Physical or sexual violence	21.8	3.3	7.3	6.2	24.8	18,208
Physical and sexual violence	44.2	11.0	21.1	19.5	50.6	3,369

Note: Husband refers to the current husband for currently married women and the most recent husband for widowed, divorced, separated, or deserted women. 1 Includes violence in the past 12 months.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 19

Help Seeking by Women Experiencing Physical or Sexual Violence (India, 2019–2021)

Background Characteristic	Never Sought Help (%)		Have Sought Help from Any Source (%)	Total (%)	Number of Women
	Never Told Anyone (%)	Told Someone (%)			
Residence					
Urban	73.2	11.0	17.2	100.0	5,657
Rural	78.6	9.1	13.0	100.0	15,518
Marital status					
Never married	85.5	13.7	15.6	100.0	1,147
Currently married	78.3	8.7	13.0	100.0	18,326
Married, <i>gauna</i> not performed	*	*	*	100.0	2
Widowed/divorced/separated/deserted	59.5	15.7	24.8	100.0	1,700
Schooling					
No schooling	78.2	8.5	13.6	100.0	7,321
<5 years complete	75.1	8.7	16.4	100.0	1,636
5–7 years complete	77.8	10.1	12.2	100.0	3,452
8–9 years complete	75.5	10.3	14.5	100.0	3,031
10–11 years complete	74.9	11.5	14.1	100.0	2,541
12 or more years complete	78.4	9.6	15.8	100.0	3,193

Household Structure					
Nuclear	77.4	9.5	14.0	100.0	11,388
Non-nuclear	76.9	9.6	14.2	100.0	9,787
Religion					
Hindu	77.2	9.5	14.1	100.0	17,130
Muslim	76.8	9.8	13.8	100.0	3,178
Christian	74.6	9.0	16.9	100.0	474
Sikh	71.9	10.6	18.2	100.0	78
Buddhist/Neo-Buddhist	80.7	6.8	17.7	100.0	212
Jain	106.2	0.0	3.2	100.0	31
Other	86.3	26.2	4.7	100.0	72
Caste/tribe					
Scheduled caste	77.9	8.7	14.4	100.0	5,179
Scheduled tribe	75.6	9.2	16.0	100.0	2,033
Other backward class	76.8	10.2	13.6	100.0	9,189
Other	77.8	9.6	14.0	100.0	4,658
Don't know	78.8	5.5	15.8	100.0	116
Wealth quintile					
Lowest	78.0	8.9	13.6	100.0	5,157
Second	80.1	8.4	12.2	100.0	5,346
Middle	75.2	10.2	15.3	100.0	4,642
Fourth	76.8	10.8	13.7	100.0	3,756
Highest	73.0	10.4	18.3	100.0	2,274
Type of violence					
Physical only	79.4	9.0	11.7	100.0	17,006
Sexual only	99.5	6.5	9.5	100.0	567
Both physical and sexual	63.2	12.9	26.3	100.0	3,602
Persons committing violence					
Current husband only	80.1	8.6	11.3	100.0	14,410
Any previous husband only	60.0	16.4	23.6	100.0	1,423
Any husband and others	62.4	11.4	26.2	100.0	2,367
Own family members only	84.1	8.7	10.8	100.0	2,408
Person(s) other than husband/family	91.4	14.3	19.0	100.0	360
Missing	50.2	14.8	35.6	100.0	207
Total	77.2	9.6	14.1	100.0	21,175

Notes: An asterisk indicates that a figure is based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases and has been suppressed.

Nuclear households are households comprised of a married couple or a man or a woman living alone or with unmarried children (biological, adopted, or fostered) with or without unrelated individuals. The remaining households are non-nuclear households.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 20

Sources from Where Help Was Sought by Women Experiencing Violence (India, 2019–2021)

Source of Help	Physical Only (%)	Sexual Only (%)	Both Physical & Sexual (%)	Total (%)
Own family	62.2	58.4	58.3	60.9
Husband's family	30.4	13.9	28.1	29.3
Current/former husband	1.0	3.6	1.9	1.3
Current/former boyfriend	0.4	1.1	0.3	0.4
Friend	15.4	24.3	18.7	16.6
Neighbour	7.8	3.6	9.7	8.3
Religious leader	2.6	0.5	2.0	2.4
Doctor/medical personnel	2.7	1.2	1.7	2.4
Police	5.4	4.7	8.2	6.3
Lawyer	2.4	0.0	1.6	2.1
Social service organisation	3.3	0.0	2.2	2.9
Other	2.1	0.0	0.8	1.7
Number of Women	1,983	54	949	2,986

Note: Women can report more than one source from which they sought help.

Source: National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–2021, India.

Table 21*Budget allocations to major WCD schemes (Rs. crore)*

Scheme	FY2023-24 Actual	FY2024-25 RE	FY2025-26 BE	% change (RE→BE)
Saksham Anganwadi & Poshan 2.0	21,810	20,071	21,960	+9%
Mission Shakti (total)	1,522	1,451	3,150	+117%
– Samarthya	1,165	1,029	2,521	+145%
– Sambal	357	422	629	+49%
Mission Vatsalya (children)	1,391	1,391	1,500	+8%
Nirbhaya Fund schemes	500	30	30	0%
Others*	271	240	250	+4%
Total (WCD)	24,696	23,183	26,890	+16%

*Note: Others include bodies like NCW, child protection agencies, etc; FY – Financial Year; RE – Revised Estimates; BE – Budget Estimates

Source: PRS Legislative Research, Demand for Grants – Women & Child Development, 2025-2026.

Table 22*IPC Provisions Related to Women and Gender*

Section	Provision	Key Elements	Punishment
100	Right of private defense	Covers defense against offences like death, grievous hurt, rape, unnatural lust, kidnapping, abduction, wrongful confinement.	No punishment; acts as legal defense.
304B	Dowry death	(i) Woman dies under unnatural circumstances (burns, injury, otherwise) within 7 years of marriage; (ii) Harassment/cruelty connected to dowry demand; (iii) Such cruelty occurred “soon before” death.	7 years to life.
312	Causing miscarriage with consent	(i) Miscarriage voluntarily caused; (ii) Consent of woman obtained; (iii) Not justified by saving her life.	Up to 3 years + fine (woman herself: up to 7 years).
313	Miscarriage without consent	(i) Miscarriage caused; (ii) Without woman’s consent; (iii) By force or deceit.	Life or up to 10 years + fine.
314	Death during miscarriage	(i) Act intended to cause miscarriage; (ii) Woman dies as result; (iii) Consent/no consent determines severity.	Up to 10 years (with consent); life (without).
326A	Acid attack	(i) Permanent/partial injury, disfigurement, burns, disability; (ii) Intent or knowledge to cause harm; (iii) Use of acid or corrosive substance.	Min. 10 years to life + fine (victim compensation).
326B	Attempted acid attack	(i) Throwing/attempt to throw acid; (ii) With intent to cause injury, deformity, or fear.	5–7 years + fine.
354A	Sexual harassment	(i) Unwelcome physical contact; (ii) Request for sexual favors; (iii) Showing pornography against will; (iv) Sexually colored remarks.	Up to 3 years + fine.

354B	Assault with intent to disrobe	(i) Use of force/assault; (ii) Intention to disrobe or compel nudity.	3–7 years + fine.
354C	Voyeurism	(i) Watching/capturing woman's image; (ii) While she engages in private act (expectation of privacy); (iii) Dissemination/usage without consent.	1–3 years (first), 3–7 years (repeat).
354D	Stalking	(i) Repeated following/attempting to contact; (ii) Monitoring electronic communication; (iii) Against woman's will.	3 years (first), 5 years (repeat) + fine.
359–369	Kidnapping/abduction	(i) Kidnapping = taking away minor/woman from lawful guardianship; (ii) Abduction = using force/deceit for movement; (iii) Intentions: murder, ransom, sexual exploitation.	7–10 years (depending on intent).
370	Trafficking of persons	(i) Recruitment/transport/harboring by threat, coercion, fraud, abuse of power; (ii) Exploitation: sexual, slavery, labor, organ removal.	7 years to life (stricter for children, multiple victims).
371–374	Slavery/forced labour	Selling, buying, enslaving, unlawful compulsory labor.	Up to 10 years + fine.
375	Rape (definition)	(i) Penile-vaginal/oral/anal penetration; (ii) Object insertion; (iii) Circumstances: against will, without consent, consent under fear/fraud, under 18.	Definition section, punishment in 376.
376(1)	Rape (general)	Sexual intercourse without consent or against will.	10 years–life + fine.
376(2)	Aggravated rape	By public servant, police, relative, teacher, management, or authority figure.	10 years–life + fine.

376A	Rape causing death/vegetative state	Severe consequence of rape.	Life imprisonment or death penalty.
376AB	Rape of girl <12 years	Rape committed on child below 12.	20 years–life or death.
376B	Husband on wife during separation	Sexual intercourse without consent during judicial separation.	2–7 years + fine.
376C	Abuse of authority	Person in authority inducing woman to consent (hospital, custodial, educational settings).	5–10 years + fine.
376D	Gang rape	Rape by 2 or more persons.	20 years–life + fine.
376DA	Gang rape of girl <16	Aggravated gang rape.	Life imprisonment.
376DB	Gang rape of girl <12	Aggravated gang rape.	Life or death.
376E	Repeat offenders	Habitual rape convicts.	Life or death.
496	Fraudulent marriage	Going through marriage ceremony, knowing it invalid.	Up to 7 years + fine.
497	Adultery (struck down)	Intercourse with another’s wife without husband’s consent.	Earlier: 5 years + fine.
498	Enticing married woman	Taking/detaining married woman with intent of illicit intercourse.	Up to 2 years + fine.
498A	Cruelty by husband/relatives	(i) Willful conduct likely to drive woman to suicide; (ii) Injury to health (mental/physical); (iii) Harassment for dowry.	Up to 3 years + fine.
509	Insult to modesty	Word, gesture, act, intrusion into privacy with intent to insult modesty.	Up to 3 years + fine.

Source: Compiled by author; IPC (1860).

Table 23

Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS), 2023 – Key Sections on Gender and Protection

Section	Definition/ Provision	Key Elements	Punishment	Successor to IPC Section/ Notes
28	Definition of “Voluntarily”	Act proceeds from a person’s free will, not under compulsion.	Not penal.	General definition.
38	Common Intention	When several persons commit a criminal act with common intention, each is liable as if done individually.	Liability principle.	IPC 34.
63	Acid attack	Causing permanent/partial injury, burns, disfigurement by throwing acid or corrosive substances.	Min. 10 years to life + fine (victim compensation).	IPC 326A.
64	Attempted acid attack	Throwing/attempting to throw acid with intent to harm.	5–7 years + fine.	IPC 326B.
65	Assault to disrobe woman	Assault/use of force to disrobe or compel nudity.	3–7 years + fine.	IPC 354B.
66	Voyeurism	Watching, capturing, disseminating private acts/images without consent.	1–3 years (first); 3–7 years (repeat).	IPC 354C.
67	Stalking	Following, contacting, or monitoring a woman repeatedly against her will.	3 years (first); 5 years (repeat) + fine.	IPC 354D.

68	Sexual harassment	Unwelcome physical contact, sexual advances, pornographic material, sexually colored remarks.	Up to 3 years + fine.	IPC 354A.
69	Rape (definition)	Penile penetration, oral/anal penetration, object insertion; without consent/against will; or if victim <18.	Punishment in Sec. 70–77.	Marital exception if wife ≥18.
70	Rape (general)	Sexual intercourse without consent/against will.	Min. 10 years to life + fine.	IPC 376(1).
71	Aggravated rape	By police, public servant, relatives, authority figures.	Min. 10 years to life + fine.	IPC 376(2).
72	Rape causing death/vegetative state	Rape resulting in death or persistent vegetative state.	Life imprisonment or death.	IPC 376A.
73	Rape of woman <16 years	Rape of minor under 16.	20 years to life.	IPC 376DA.
74	Rape of woman <12 years	Rape of child below 12.	Life imprisonment or death.	IPC 376DB.
75	Husband raping wife during separation	Sexual intercourse without consent during judicial separation.	2–7 years + fine.	Partial marital rape recognition.
76	Abuse of authority (custodial/ position)	Sexual intercourse through abuse of power, trust, or authority.	5–10 years + fine.	IPC 376C.
77	Gang rape	Committed by 2 or more persons.	20 years to life + fine (compensation to victim).	IPC 376D.

78	Gang rape of woman <16	Gang rape of minor below 16.	Life imprisonment.	IPC 376DA.
79	Gang rape of woman <12	Gang rape of minor below 12.	Life imprisonment or death.	IPC 376DB.
80	Repeat offenders	Habitual/repeat rape offenders.	Life imprisonment or death.	IPC 376E.
81	Word/gesture to insult modesty	Words, gestures, acts intended to insult modesty/privacy of woman.	Up to 3 years + fine.	IPC 509.
83	Assault to outrage modesty	Assault/criminal force with intent to outrage modesty.	1–5 years + fine.	IPC 354.
84	Kidnapping from India	Conveying person beyond India's borders without guardian's consent.	Up to 7 years + fine.	IPC 360
85	Kidnapping from guardianship	Taking/enticing minor (girl <18, boy <16) or person of unsound mind without consent.	Up to 7 years + fine.	IPC 361
86	Kidnapping/maiming minor for begging	Kidnapping/maiming minor for begging.	10 years to life + fine.	IPC 363A
87	Kidnapping/abduction to murder	Taking/abducting with intent to murder/grievous hurt.	10 years + fine (up to life).	IPC 364
89	Kidnapping for ransom	Kidnapping/abduction for ransom.	Life or death + fine.	IPC 364A
90	Kidnapping/abduction for secret confinement	To secretly/confine person.	7 years + fine.	IPC 365
91	Kidnapping/	To compel marriage or unlawful labor.	10 years + fine.	IPC 366

	abduction for forced marriage/labor			
92	Procuration of minor girl	Procuring girl <18 for illicit intercourse.	10 years + fine.	IPC 366A
96	Importation of girl <21	Importing girl <21 for illicit intercourse.	Up to 10 years + fine.	IPC 366B
97	Buying/disposing person as slave	Engaging in slavery (buying/selling).	7 years + fine.	IPC 370-371
98	Habitual dealing in slaves	Habitual traffic in slavery.	Life or 10 years + fine.	Strengthened prohibition.
99	Unlawful compulsory labor	Compelling labour against will.	Up to 1 year + fine.	IPC 374
111	Dowry death	Woman dies under unnatural circumstances within 7 years of marriage, linked to dowry harassment.	7 years to life.	IPC 304B.
124	Cruelty by husband/relatives	Cruelty includes grave injury, suicide abetment, dowry harassment.	Up to 3 years + fine.	IPC 498A.
137	Adultery (struck down)	Sexual intercourse with another's spouse.	No punishment (decriminalised).	Retained for civil issues.
138	Cohabitation by deceitful marriage	Deceitfully inducing belief of lawful marriage to cohabit.	Up to 10 years + fine.	IPC 493
139	Concealment of former marriage	Concealing prior marriage from spouse at time of remarriage.	Up to 10 years + fine.	IPC 495/496
141	Fraudulent marriage ceremony	Going through marriage ceremony knowing it is void.	Up to 7 years + fine.	IPC 496.

142	Enticing married woman	Taking/detaining married woman for illicit intercourse.	Up to 2 years + fine.	IPC 498.
143	Word/gesture to insult modesty	Insulting modesty of woman through words, acts, gestures.	Up to 3 years + fine.	IPC 509.
144	Sexual intercourse by deceitful means	Sexual intercourse obtained by fraud, impersonation, promise of marriage, deceit.	10 years + fine.	Expands consent provisions.

Source: Compiled by author; BNSS (2024).

Table 24

Comparative Analysis: International Best Practices Vs. India's Approach

Intervention Type	India's Approach	Key Global Examples	Key Similarity	Key Difference/Learning
Legal & Policy	Has the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA) but lacks a law on marital rape.	Sweden, Rwanda, Brazil	India's PWDVA, like Argentina's Law 26.485, is a progressive civil law, but its effectiveness is hindered by poor implementation.	Unlike Sweden and Rwanda, marital rape is not criminalised, a critical legal and human rights gap.
Institutional & Service Delivery	Established One Stop Centres (OSCs) and helplines (181) under the Nirbhaya Fund.	Rwanda (IOSCs), South Africa (Thuthuzela Care Centres), Malawi (Mobile Courts)	The concept of India's OSCs is similar to the "one-stop shop" model in Rwanda and South Africa, which streamlines	India's OSCs are often inadequate in number and geographically inaccessible, a problem addressed by Malawi's

			services for victims.	mobile court model.
Community & Social Norms	NGOs like MAVA engage men and boys in social change; campaigns are often centered on women's empowerment.	Argentina (#NiUnaMenos), South Africa (Under-The-Tree Dialogues), Malawi (Umunthu Plus)	Indian NGOs and movements share the same goal of challenging patriarchal norms at the community level as those in Argentina and South Africa.	The scale of community-led social transformation is insufficient for the size of India's population; there is a need to move beyond isolated campaigns.
Technological	Multiple government-run digital helplines and platforms (112, 181, SHe-Box, Her Legal Guide).	South Africa (GBVCC), Brazil (AI pilot project)	India has embraced a multi-channel digital approach to GBV reporting and support, similar to South Africa's GBVCC.	The system is fragmented and not fully coordinated; India also needs to address the growing threat of technology-facilitated violence, as seen in Brazil.
Economic	Limited formal initiatives at a government level; some NGOs provide vocational training.	South Africa (public procurement quotas), Sweden (housing market analysis), Malawi (vocational training).	The recognition that economic empowerment is a critical component of a survivor's recovery is shared by both India and the other countries.	India lacks a comprehensive government-led economic strategy to address financial dependency as a root cause of violence, unlike South Africa.

Source: Compiled by author.

References

- Ash, E., Asher, S., Bhowmick, A., Bhupatiraju, S., Chen, D., Devi, T., Goessmann, C., Novosad, P., & Siddiqi, B. (2025). In-Group Bias in the Indian Judiciary: Evidence from 5 Million Criminal Cases. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 1–45. https://doi.org/10.1162/rest_a_01569
- Bardall, G. (2011). Breaking the mold: Understanding gender and electoral violence. International Foundation for Electoral Systems (IFES). https://igualdad.ine.mx/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/gender_and_electoral_violence_2011.pdf
- Barik, S. (2024, September 19). Woman subjected to custodial abuse in Bhubaneswar police station reveals chilling detail. *The Hindu*. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/odisha/woman-subjected-to-custodial-abuse-in-bhubaneswar-police-station-reveals-chilling-detail/article68660723.ece>
- Barman, M. (2024). Enhancing workplace safety: Assessing the PoSH Act for women in India. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14280467>
- Bergvall, S. (2024). Women's economic empowerment and intimate partner violence. *Journal of Public Economics*, 239, 105211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2024.105211>
- Beyene, A. S., Chojenta, C. L., & Loxton, D. J. (2021). Consequences of gender-based violence on female high school students in eastern Ethiopia. *PubMed*, 25(4), 22–33. <https://doi.org/10.29063/ajrh2021/v25i4.3>
- Bhalla, N. (2013, January 16). How India's police and judiciary fail rape victims. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/article/world/how-indias-police-and-judiciary-fail-rape-victims-idUSDEE90F0AZ/>
- Bharucha, J., & Khatri, R. (2018). The sexual street harassment battle: perceptions of women in urban India. *The Journal of Adult Protection*, 20(2), 101–109. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jap-12-2017-0038>
- Bhattacharya, S., Bhattacharya, K., Bhattacharya, N., & Bhattacharya, N. (2025). Gender-based violence against female patients in hospitals. *Tropical Doctor*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00494755251318089>
- Bhattacharyya, R. (2014). Understanding the spatialities of sexual assault against Indian women in India. *Gender Place & Culture*, 22(9), 1340–56. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0966369x.2014.969684>
- Bhelari, A. (2025, August 6). Bihar honour killing: 25-year-old man shot dead by father-in-law over inter-caste marriage. *The Hindu*. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/bihar/25-year-old-man-shot-dead-by-father-in-law-in-case-of-caste-killing-in-bihar/article69900458.ece>

- Bishwajit, G., Sarker, S., & Yaya, S. (2016). Socio-cultural aspects of gender-based violence and its impacts on women's health in South Asia. *F1000Research*, 5, 802.
<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.8633.1>
- Burger Huyser Attorneys. (2025). Which Laws Protect Against Gender-Based Violence in South Africa? | BHA. Burger Huyser Attorneys. <https://www.burgerhuyserattorneys.co.za/which-laws-protect-against-gender-based-violence-in-south-africa/>
- Butalia, R. E., & Bhasin, F. R. (2023). Socio-cultural dynamics and their implications on gender-based violence: A deep dive into India's diverse contexts. *Journal of Sociology, Psychology & Religious Studies*, 5(2), 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.53819/81018102t4216>
- Butani, A. (2024, November 11). High prevalence of sexual violence among gay, bisexual men across six cities: study. *The Hindu*. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/high-prevalence-of-sexual-violence-among-gay-bisexual-men-across-six-cities-study/article68856217.ece>
- Campbell, J., Jones, A. S., Dienemann, J., Kub, J., Schollenberger, J., O'Campo, P., Gielen, A. C., & Wynne, C. (2002). Intimate partner violence and physical health consequences. *Archives of Internal Medicine*, 162(10), 1157. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archinte.162.10.1157>
- Chakravarti, U. (1993). Conceptualising Brahmanical patriarchy in early India: Gender, caste, class and state. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 28(14), 579–85. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4399556>
- Chaudhary, S. (2013). Domestic violence in India. *Journal of Indian Research*, 1(2), 146–52. <https://jir.mewaruniversity.org/2021/02/20/volume-1-issue-2-jir-april-june-2013/>
- Chitsamatanga, B., & Rembe, N. (2020). School related gender-based violence as a violation of children's rights to education in South Africa: Manifestations, consequences and possible solutions. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 69(1–3). <https://doi.org/10.31901/24566608.2020/69.1-3.3203>
- Citizens for Justice and Peace [CJP]. (2024, February 1). India's LGBTQIA+ struggle: Beyond legal victories, battle for true equality remains. CJP. <https://cjp.org.in/indias-lgbtqia-struggle-beyond-legal-victories-battle-for-true-equality-remains/>
- CJP Team. (2025, August 28). Mapping Gender-Based Violence in India: Trends, determinants, and institutional frameworks. CJP. <https://cjp.org.in/mapping-gender-based-violence-in-india-trends-determinants-and-institutional-frameworks/#:~:text=Giri%20and%20Parveen%20report%20in,acording%20to%20the%20NFHS%20Report>

- Closson, K., Boyce, S. C., Johns, N., Inwards-Breland, D. J., Thomas, E. E., & Raj, A. (2024). Physical, sexual, and intimate partner violence among transgender and gender-diverse individuals. *JAMA Network Open*, 7(6), e2419137.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.19137>
- COFEM Secretariat. (2022, August 15). Sexual and gender-based violence against Dalit women and girls in India. Coalition of Feminists for Social Change. <https://cofemsocialchange.org/sexual-gbv-dalit-women-girls-india/>
- Dagras, M. (2021). Victimization of LGBT community in India. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3866184>
- DC Web Desk. (2025, May 6). NCRB: Domestic Violence Tops Crimes Against Women in India. *DeccanChronicle.com*; *Deccan Chronicle*. <https://www.deccanchronicle.com/nation/crime/ncrb-domestic-violence-tops-crimes-against-women-in-india-1877291>
- Department of Justice and Constitutional Development, Republic of South Africa. (2022). South Africa against Gender-Based Violence & Femicide. *Justice.gov.za*. <https://www.justice.gov.za/vg/GBV.html>
- Devgan, R. (2022). IPC Section 376 - Punishment for rape. *A Lawyers Reference*. <https://devgan.in/ipc/section/376/>
- Dhal, S. (2018). Situating tribal women in gender discourse: A study of the socio-economic roots of gender violence in Odisha. *Indian Journal of Public Administration*, 64(1), 87–102.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0019556117735459>
- Equal Measure 2030. (2024). Fast track or backtrack ? The prospectus for Gender Equality by 2049. In *Equal Measures 2030* (pp. 11–20). <https://equalmeasures2030.org/fast-track-or-backtrack/>
- European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE). (2021). Costs of gender-based violence in the European Union. *European Institute for Gender Equality*. https://eige.europa.eu/gender-based-violence/costs-of-gender-based-violence?language_content_entity=en
- European Institute For Gender Equality. (2023, June 9). Sweden. *European Institute for Gender Equality*. https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/legislative-policy-backgrounds/sweden?language_content_entity=en
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. (2024, June 20). LGBTIQ equality at a crossroads—progress and challenges. <https://fra.europa.eu/en/news/2024/harassment-and-violence-against-lgbtqi-people-rise>

- Fernandez, B., & Gomathy, N. B. (2016). The nature of violence faced by lesbian women in India. [ideas.repec.org](https://ideas.repec.org/p/ess/wpaper/id8228.html).
<https://ideas.repec.org/p/ess/wpaper/id8228.html>
- Funes, S. (2017, December 13). The Birth of Femicides in Argentina: a Recognition of Gender Violence | Heinrich Böll Stiftung | Brussels office - European Union. Heinrich-Böll-Stiftung.
<https://eu.boell.org/en/2017/12/13/birth-femicides-argentina-recognition-gender-violence>
- Government of India, Ministry of Women and Child Development. (2024). Rajya Sabha unstarred question No. 1907 | Human trafficking and women's safety. Digital Sansad.
https://sansad.in/getFile/annex/265/AU1907_1UDjyR.pdf?source=pqars
- Goyal, S. (2024). Understanding the Challenges for Implementation of the New Criminal Procedural Law: A Critical Appraisal of Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023. *NALSAR Law Review*, 9(1), 225-241.
<https://nalsar.ac.in/images/Final-NLR-Vol9.pdf>
- Halder, P. (2021, September 22). India's tribal women left behind in progress toward gender equality. Landesa. <https://www.landesa.org/indias-tribal-women-left-behind-in-progress-toward-gender-equality/#:~:text=While%20India's%20national%20constitution%20delineates,in%20which%20women%20cannot%20participate.>
- Hashemi, L., Fanslow, J., Gulliver, P., & McIntosh, T. (2022). Intergenerational impact of violence exposure: Emotional-behavioural and school difficulties in children aged 5-17. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 12.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2021.771834>
- Henry, R. S., Perrin, P. B., Coston, B. M., & Calton, J. M. (2018). Intimate partner violence and mental health among transgender/gender nonconforming adults. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 36(7-8), 3374-399. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260518775148>
- Immigration and Refugee Board of Canada. (2019). Responses to Information Requests - Immigration and Refugee Board of Canada. [Irb-Cisr.gc.ca](https://www.irb-cisr.gc.ca/en/country-information/rir/Pages/index.aspx?doc=458886&pls=1).
<https://www.irb-cisr.gc.ca/en/country-information/rir/Pages/index.aspx?doc=458886&pls=1>
- Independent Advisory Group on Country Information (IAGCI). (2024, January 8). Country policy and information note: women fearing gender-based violence, Bangladesh. GOV.UK.
<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/bangladesh-country-policy-and-information-notes/country-policy-and-information-note-women-fearing-gender-based-violence-bangladesh-january-2024-accessible>

- Instituto Maria Da Penha (IMP). (2006). Summary of the law: Lei Maria da Penha. www.institutomariadapenha.org.br.
<https://www.institutomariadapenha.org.br/lei-11340/resumo-da-lei-maria-da-penha.html>
- International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and ICF. 2021. National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019-21: India: Volume II. Mumbai: IIPS.
- Inter-Parliamentary Union. (2016). Sexism, harassment and violence against women parliamentarians.
<https://www.ipu.org/resources/publications/issue-briefs/2016-10/sexism-harassment-and-violence-against-women-parliamentarians>
- Iricibar, V. (2024, June 3). Argentina marks ninth Ni Una Menos anniversary: "It's not freedom, it's patriarchal violence." *Buenos Aires Herald*.
<https://buenosairesherald.com/society/argentina-marks-ninth-ni-una-menos-anniversary-its-not-freedom-its-patriarchal-violence>
- Iyer, S. R., & Radha, N. (2016). Women trafficking in India—A critical analysis. Studocu. <https://www.studocu.com/in/document/university-of-mumbai/bms/ash-v4-n2-017-bsjsjs/36472662>
- Jain, D. (2023). Supreme Court of India Judgement on Abortion as a Fundamental Right: Breaking New Ground. *Sexual and Reproductive Health Matters*, 31(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/26410397.2023.2225264>
- Kalumbi, M. (2025, June 20). Mobile courts bring justice closer - Oxfam, CAVWOC. Malawi Broadcasting Corporation.
<https://mbc.mw/mobile-courts-bring-justice-closer-oxfam-cavwoc/>
- Kotiswaran, P. (2018, July 18). How Did We Get Here? Or A Short History of the 2018 Trafficking Bill. *Economic and Political Weekly*.
<https://www.epw.in/engage/article/how-did-we-get-here-or-short-history>
- Krishnan, M. (2022). Caste-ing Gender Violence. *Times of India*, 1970-2020. University of Chicago. <https://doi.org/10.6082/uchicago.3699>
- Latin America Advisor: A Daily Publication of the Dialogue. (2022, October 6). How Well Is Brazil Addressing Violence Against Women? – Inter-American Dialogue. [TheDialogue.org](http://thedialogue.org); *The Dialogue: Leadership for the Americans*. <https://thedialogue.org/analysis/how-well-is-brazil-addressing-violence-against-women>
- Lok Sabha Un-Starred Question No 2151 to be Answered on 29.07.2016, (2016) (testimony of Shrimati Krishana Raj, Minister of the State in the Ministry of Women and Child Development).
<https://sansad.in/getFile/loksabhaquestions/annex/9/AU2151.pdf?source=pqals>

- Madan, M., & Nalla, M. K. (2016). Sexual harassment in public spaces. *International Criminal Justice Review*, 26(2), 80–97. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1057567716639093>
- Mann, C. (2024, November 26). Girls share how gender-based violence impacts their learning. Malala Fund. <https://malala.org/news-and-voices/girls-share-how-gender-based-violence-impacts-their-learning>
- Marokoane, A. (2025, September 4). Digital shadows, deadly realities: Technology-facilitated femicide in South Africa. News.nwu.ac.za; North West University, South Africa. <https://news.nwu.ac.za/digital-shadows-deadly-realities-technology-facilitated-femicide-south-africa>
- Mehra, D., Srivastava, S., Chandra, M., Srivastava, N., Laaksonen, M., Saarinen, H. E., & Mehra, S. (2023). Effect of physical mobility, decision making and economic empowerment on gender-based violence among married youth in India-SAWERA project. *BMC Public Health*, 23(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-15421-4>
- Men Against Violence and Abuse (MAVA). (1993). MAVA India. [http://www.mavaindia.org/](http://www.mavaindia.org)
- Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, Government of India. (2021). The Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021 . <https://www.meity.gov.in/static/uploads/2024/02/Information-Technology-Intermediary-Guidelines-and-Digital-Media-Ethics-Code-Rules-2021-updated-06.04.2023-.pdf>
- Ministry of Employment, Government Offices of Sweden. (2024, February 7). Government invests SEK 600 million to combat intimate partner and honour-based violence. Regeringskansliet. <https://www.government.se/articles/2024/02/government-invests-sek-600-million-to-combat-intimate-partner-and-honour-based-violence/>
- Ministry of Finance, Government of India. (2025). Statement 13: Gender Budget. <https://www.indiabudget.gov.in/doc/eb/stat13.pdf>
- Ministry of Gender and Family Promotion, Government of the Republic of Rwanda, & Kigali. (2021, December 10). The fight against GBV concerns every Rwandan. www.migeprof.gov.rw. <https://www.migeprof.gov.rw/news-detail/the-fight-against-gbv-concerns-every-rwandan>
- Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India. (2025). Lok Sabha unstarred question no. 1954 to be answered on the 11th March 2025/Phalguna 20, 1946 (Saka) murder cases. <https://www.mha.gov.in/MHA1/Par2017/pdfs/par2025-pdfs/LS11032025/1954.pdf>

- Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India, & PIB Delhi. (2025, March 29). India's Commitment to Women's Safety. Pib.gov.in. <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2116557>
- Mishra, S. K., Pradhan, G., Pradhan, S. K., & Choubey, G. (2024). Prevalence and predictors of domestic violence in India: Complex sample analysis of a nationally representative study conducted between 2019 and 2021. *Cureus*. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.66113>
- Montesanti, S. R., & Thurston, W. E. (2015). Mapping the role of structural and interpersonal violence in the lives of women: Implications for public health interventions and policy. *BMC Women's Health*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-015-0256-4>
- National Commission for Women, Government of India. (2025, March 27). Laws Related to Women - National Commission for Women. National Commission for Women. <https://www.ncw.gov.in/important-links/laws-related-to-women/>
- Niaz, U. (2003). Violence against women in South Asian countries. *Archives of Women's Mental Health*, 6(3), 173–84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00737-003-0171-9>
- Nisha, S., Kumar, U., Ambasth, A., Ranjan, P., Sharma, A., Mahadeva, R., Gupta, V., Kampani, S., & Dixit, S. (2024). Assessing the issues of honour and violence against women: A human rights discourse framework for the detection of violence against women. *BIO Web of Conferences*, 86, 01114. <https://doi.org/10.1051/bioconf/20248601114>
- OECD (2023). Breaking the cycle of gender-based violence: Translating evidence into action for victim/survivor-centred governance. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/b133e75c-en>
- One Stop Centre Scheme Implementation Guidelines for State Governments/UT Administrations, (2017). <https://socialwelfare.tripura.gov.in/sites/default/files/GUIDELINES%20FOR%20ONE%20STOP%20CENTER%20SCHEME.pdf>
- Ouedraogo, R., & Stenzel, D. (2021). The heavy economic toll of gender-based violence: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa. *IMF Working Paper*, 2021(277), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781557754073.001>
- Paliwal, D. (2024). Punishment for rape in India (Section 375 and 376 IPC). *Ipleaders*. <https://blog.ipleaders.in/punishment-for-rape-in-india/>
- Pandey, G. (2024, October 19). Sati: Why India widow-burning case is back in news after 37 years. *BBC*. <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/cn8ykmn2p1go>
- Patel, A. R., Prabhu, S., Sciarrino, N. A., Pousseau, C., Smith, N. B., & Rozek, D. C. (2021). Gender-based violence and suicidal ideation among Indian women from slums: An examination of direct and indirect effects of depression, anxiety, and PTSD symptoms. *Psychological Trauma*

Theory Research Practice and Policy, 13(6), 694–702.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/tra0000998>

Phuc, H., DO, Baker, P. R. A., Van Vo, T., Murray, A., Murray, L., Valdebenito, S., Eisner, M., Tran, B. X., & Dunne, M. P. (2021). Intergenerational effects of violence on women's perinatal wellbeing and infant health outcomes: Evidence from a birth cohort study in Central Vietnam. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 21(1).

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-021-04097-6>

PRS Legislative Research. (2018). The Trafficking of Persons (Prevention, Protection and Rehabilitation) Bill, 2018. PRS Legislative Research. <https://prsindia.org/billtrack/the-trafficking-of-persons-prevention-protection-and-rehabilitation-bill-2018>

PRS Legislative Research. (2023). Demand for Grants 2023-24 Analysis Women and Child Development. https://prsindia.org/files/budget/budget_parliament/2023/DFG-Women_and_Child_Development_2023-24.pdf

PRS Legislative Research. (2025a, March 20). Demand for Grants 2024-25 Analysis : Women and Child Development. PRS Legislative Research. <https://prsindia.org/budgets/parliament/demand-for-grants-2024-25-analysis-women-and-child-development>

PRS Legislative Research. (2025b, September 29). Demand for Grants 2025-26 Analysis : Women and Child Development. PRS Legislative Research. <https://prsindia.org/budgets/parliament/demand-for-grants-2025-26-analysis-women-and-child-development>

PTI. (2024, February 25). 275 cases of custodial rape registered from 2017-2022; Offenders range from police to armed forces: NCRB. Deccan Herald. <https://www.deccanherald.com/india/275-cases-of-custodial-rape-registered-from-2017-22-offenders-range-from-police-to-armed-forces-ncrb-2909295>

Public Administration Institute. (2024). Understanding gender-based violence: Definition, causes, and impact. Public Administration Institute. https://pubadmin.institute/gender-sensitization/understanding-gender-based-violence-causes-impact?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Puri, Lakshmi. (2016). "The economic costs of violence against women." Remarks made at the high-level discussion on the "Economic Cost of Violence against Women." United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women (UN Women). New York, September 21. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/news/stories/2016/9/speech-by-lakshmi-puri-on-economic-costs-of-violence-against-women>

Rights CoLAB. (2023, September 28). Umunthu Plus Initiative. Rights CoLab. https://rightscolab.org/case_study/umunthu-plus-initiative/

- Saathi. (2022). PROGRAMMES – Saathi. Saathi.org.np.
<https://saathi.org.np/programmes/>
- Sabrang. (2024, May 21). National Commission for Women: An instrument of social justice or a mere political mouthpiece? | SabrangIndia. SabrangIndia. <https://sabrangindia.in/national-commission-for-women-an-instrument-of-social-justice-or-a-mere-political-mouthpiece/>
- Salter, M., Woodlock, D., Dragiewicz, M., Conroy, E., Ussher, J., Burke, J., & Middleton, W. (2025). "I see it running through my family": The intergenerational and collective trauma of gender-based violence. *Journal of Family Trauma Child Custody & Child Development*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26904586.2024.2443843>
- Sarac, E., & Odabas, D. (2025). Gender-based economic violence and the exploitation of women: A deep dive. *World Journal of Psychiatry*, 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.5498/wjp.v15.i3.103725>
- Seshasayee, H. (2021, December 7). Addressing the historical roots of gender-based violence in twenty-first century India. Wilson Center. <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/addressing-historical-roots-gender-based-violence-twenty-first-century-india>
- Sikri, K., Thakur, A., Tadele, B. A., & Cowen, D. (2021, February 21). Why women's police stations in India fail to mitigate violence against women—The Reach Alliance. The Reach Alliance. <https://reachalliance.org/case-study/why-womens-police-stations-in-india-fail-to-mitigate-violence-against-women/>
- Smallens, Y. (2025). "They're ruining people's lives." Human Rights Watch. <https://www.hrw.org/report/2025/06/03/theyre-ruining-peoples-lives/bans-on-gender-affirming-care-for-transgender-youth>
- Soci, G. (2024, February 20). Protecting victims of GBVF | South African Government. *Www.gov.za*. <https://www.gov.za/blog/protecting-victims-gbvf>
- Sultan, M., & Mahpara, P. (2024, March). "It's a Family Matter": Inaction and Denial of Domestic Violence*. *Ids.ac.uk; IDS Bulletin*. <https://bulletin.ids.ac.uk/index.php/idsbo/article/view/3243/3334>
- Suri, S., Mona, & Sarkar, D. (2022, April 6). Domestic violence and women's health in India: Insights from NFHS-4. *orfonline.org*. <https://www.orfonline.org/research/domestic-violence-and-women-s-health-in-india-insights-from-nfhs-4>
- Temple, J. R., Shorey, R. C., Tortolero, S. R., Wolfe, D. A., & Stuart, G. L. (2013). Importance of gender and attitudes about violence in the relationship between exposure to interparental violence and the perpetration of teen dating violence. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 37(5), 343–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2013.02.001>

- The Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, (2023).
https://www.mha.gov.in/sites/default/files/2024-04/250884_2_english_01042024.pdf
- The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, (2013).
<https://www.iitk.ac.in/wc/data/TheCriminalLaw.pdf>
- The Guardian. (2025, June 9). Domestic violence can affect victims' brain health for life, study suggests. The Guardian.
https://www.theguardian.com/society/2025/jun/09/domestic-violence-can-affect-victims-brain-health-for-life-study-suggests?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- The Indian Penal Code, (1860).
<https://www.indiacode.nic.in/repealedfileopen?rfilename=A1860-45.pdf>
- The Information Technology Act, (2000).
https://www.indiacode.nic.in/bitstream/123456789/13116/1/it_act_2000_updated.pdf
- The Medical Termination of Pregnancy (Amendment) Act, (2021).
<https://mohfw.gov.in/sites/default/files/MTP%20Amendment%20Act%202021.pdf>
- The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act , Pib.gov.in (2005).
<https://wcd.gov.in/documents/uploaded/1710219616.pdf>
- The Times of India. (2025, August 31). Honour killing: Karnataka teen strangled, burnt over intercaste relationship; Kin absconding after crime. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/hubballi/honour-killing-in-kburagi-teen-strangled-and-burnt-over-intercaste-relationship/articleshow/123605332.cms>
- Therese , R. M. (2018, April 23). Gender-based violence in Rwanda: Getting everyone on board. World Bank Blogs.
<https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/nasikiliza/gender-based-violence-in-rwanda-getting-everyone-on-board>
- Thomas, A. (2015). INCIDENTS OF SEXUAL HARASSMENT AT EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN INDIA: PREVENTIVE MEASURES AND GRIEVANCE HANDLING. *International Journal of Recent Advances in Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(3), 0317–0322.
<https://doi.org/10.64485/ijramr>
- Tsapalas, D., Parker, M., Ferrer, L., & Bernales, M. (2020). Gender-based violence, Perspectives in Latin America and the Caribbean. *Hispanic Health Care International*, 19(1), 23–37.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1540415320924768>
- UNESCO. (2020). *UNESCO's Global Survey on Online Violence against Women Journalists*. https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/unescos-global-survey-online-violence-against-women-journalists#_ftn1

- UN Women – Africa. (n.d.). Frequently asked questions: Types of violence against women and girls. [https://africa.unwomen.org/en/what-we-do/ending-violence-against-women/faqs/types-of-violence-1#:~:text=Gender%2Dbased%20violence%20\(GBV\),of%20power%20and%20harmful%20norms](https://africa.unwomen.org/en/what-we-do/ending-violence-against-women/faqs/types-of-violence-1#:~:text=Gender%2Dbased%20violence%20(GBV),of%20power%20and%20harmful%20norms).
- UN Women Africa. (2024, March 10). Justice Amplified: Mobile Courts Empower Malawi. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=32MfzVtHzHM>
- UN Women. (2025, February 10). FAQs: Digital abuse, trolling, stalking, and other forms of technology-facilitated violence against women | UN Women – Headquarters. UN Women – Headquarters. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/articles/faqs/digital-abuse-trolling-stalking-and-other-forms-of-technology-facilitated-violence-against-women>
- UN Women–Headquarters. (2024, November 25). Facts and figures: Ending violence against women | UN Women—Headquarters. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/articles/facts-and-figures/facts-and-figures-ending-violence-against-women>
- UNDP & UN Women. (2017). Preventing violence against women in elections: A programming guide. <https://www.undp.org/publications/preventing-violence-against-women-elections-programming-guide>
- United Nations. (2000). Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons Especially Women and Children, Supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime. OHCHR; United Nations. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/protocol-prevent-suppress-and-punish-trafficking-persons>
- United Nations. (n.d.). LGBTIQ+ | United Nations. <https://www.un.org/en/fight-racism/vulnerable-groups/lgbtqi-plus>
- Verge, T. (2021). Legislative reform in Europe to fight violence against women in politics. *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, 4(3), 459–61. <https://doi.org/10.1332/251510821x16149579296781>
- Vijayalaxmi, B. (2019). Cyber crime against women in India - A critical analysis. In *International Journal of Law*. <https://www.lawjournals.org/assets/archives/2019/vol5issue2/11163.pdf>

- Vital Strategies. (2025, January 2). Women victims of violence alter their pattern of visits to healthcare units around 90 days before escalation of cases - Vital Strategies. Vital Strategies. <https://www.vitalstrategies.org/women-victims-of-violence-alter-their-pattern-of-visits-to-healthcare-units-around-90-days-before-escalation-of-cases/>
- Ward, S., & McLoughlin, L. (2020). Turds, traitors and tossers: The abuse of UK MPs via Twitter. *Journal of Legislative Studies*, 26(1), 47–73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13572334.2020.1730502>
- WHO. (2021, November 25). Gender based violence is a public health issue: Using a health systems approach. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/news/item/25-11-2021-gender-based-violence-is-a-public-health-issue-using-a-health-systems-approach>
- Wilson, B. D. M., Jordan, S. P., Meyer, I. H., Flores, A. R., Stemple, L., & Herman, J. L. (2017). Disproportionality and disparities among sexual minority youth in custody. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 46(7), 1547–61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-017-0632-5>
- Women Against Abuse. (n.d.). The language we use. <https://www.womenagainstabuse.org/education-resources/the-language-we-use>
- World Bank Group. (n.d.). EnGENDER IMPACT: Addressing gender-based violence. World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/gender/publication/engender-impact-addressing-gender-based-violence>
- World Health Organization. (2021, March 9). Devastatingly pervasive: 1 in 3 women globally experience violence. World Health Organisation News. <https://www.who.int/news/item/09-03-2021-devastatingly-pervasive-1-in-3-women-globally-experience-violence>
- World Justice Project. (n.d.). Rights in Action: Access to Justice for Women in Argentina. World Justice Project. <https://worldjusticeproject.org/our-work/programmes/rights-access-justice-women-argentina>
- Yan, E., Lo, I. P. Y., Sun, R., Chan, A. S. W., Ng, H. K. L., & Wu, A. (2024). Intimate partner violence among lesbian, gay, and bisexual adults: A cross-sectional survey in Hong Kong. *LGBT Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1089/lgbt.2023.0294>

About CDPP

The Centre for Development Policy and Practice is an independent research institution working on economic and public policy issues with a focus on the development of marginalised populations. Our work spans research and outreach, aimed at disseminating valuable research insights. We conduct rigorous internal and partnership-centric research, emphasising empirical evidence to bridge knowledge gaps and offer innovative solutions to societal issues.

A primary focus of our institution is to narrow the knowledge divide between the government and the public regarding inclusive policies. We aim to inform and raise public awareness about existing policy frameworks, engaging people and valuing their input in the policy formulation. We achieve this through working with a team of research professionals and expert consultants, under the guidance of eminent public intellectuals and conduct various events like seminars, workshops, roundtables, talks, and regular publications. These platforms bring together experts, government officials, and the public for multifaceted discussions and debates on crucial societal concerns.

Governing Council

G. Sudhir is a former IAS officer. He was Chairman of the Commission of Inquiry to study the Socioeconomic and Educational conditions of Muslims in Telangana.

Amitabh Kundu is a Professor Emeritus at L. J. University, Ahmedabad, a Visiting Professor at MANUU, Hyderabad, and a Trustee of Development Alternatives, Delhi. Formerly a Professor and Dean at JNU, he chaired key committees, including the Post-Sachar Evaluation, Diversity Index (Ministry of Minority Affairs), Housing Shortage Estimation (Urban Development), and Housing Start-Up (RBI).

Aalok Wadhwa is a management professional with over three decades of experience working in FMCG, online and social media content, publishing, and retail businesses.

Saleema Razvi is a Research Economist at the Copenhagen Consensus Center. She has previously served in organisations like Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations, the Population Foundation of India, and UNICEF.

Abdul Shaban is a Professor at the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai. He has been a member of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee, Chief Minister's High-Powered Committee on Muslims, Government of Maharashtra, and Sudhir Commission, Telangana.

Syed Adeeluddin serves as the Director of CDPP. In addition to his leadership role, he is a philanthropist and social worker, balancing his professional commitments with the responsibilities of his family's construction business. An engineering graduate from Osmania University, he also holds an MBA in Finance.

Neelima Khetan is a CSR and social sector professional with nearly four decades of experience. She is the Managing Partner at Nous Consultants and was a Visiting Fellow at the Centre for Social and Economic Progress. She has held leadership roles in Vedanta, Hindustan Zinc, and Coca-Cola India. With grassroots experience at PRADAN, Seva Mandir, and AIF, she also served as Acting Director at IRMA. An author and board member of several non-profits, she holds degrees from IRMA and SRCC.

Jeemol Unni is a Professor at Ahmedabad University and a former Director and RBI Chair Professor of Economics at the Institute of Rural Management, Anand. A specialist in labour economics, she serves on the Editorial Boards of the Indian Journal of Labour Economics and the Journal of Development Policy and Practice.

Sumaira Naser is a philanthropist, educationist, and environmentalist. She is a patron of the Telangana Science Fair Academy, which fosters scientific temperament among youth, and serves as an advisor at the International Women's Startup Corridor (IWSC), with a focus on promoting women's health.

Rathin Roy is a Visiting Senior Fellow at ODI, where he previously served as Managing Director. His research focuses on fiscal and macroeconomic issues in developing economies. He was the Director and CEO of NIPFP in New Delhi and has held key roles at the UNDP and the Thirteenth Finance Commission. Rathin holds a Ph.D and M.Phil in Economics from the University of Cambridge, an M.A. from Jawaharlal Nehru University, and a B.A. from St. Stephen's College, University of Delhi. He has also taught at the Universities of Manchester and London.

Research Team

Amitabh Kundu is a Professor Emeritus at L. J. University, Ahmedabad, a Visiting Professor at MANUU, Hyderabad, and a Trustee of Development Alternatives, Delhi. Formerly a Professor and Dean at JNU, he chaired key committees, including the Post-Sachar Evaluation, Diversity Index (Ministry of Minority Affairs), Housing Shortage Estimation (Urban Development), and Housing Start-Up (RBI). Min

Soma Wadhwa is a development studies researcher, with extensive experience as a media professional.

Nahia Hussain is Vice President (Policy Affairs) at CDPP with a Master's degree from National Law School of India, Bangalore.

Anjana Divakar is the Executive Director of Public Policy Research and Operations at the CDPP. She has a Master's degree in Public Policy from the Jindal School of Government and Public Policy.

Laldinmoi Pangamte is the Copy Editor, Publications, at CDPP. She has a PhD degree from the School of International Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi.

Moumita Barman is a Senior Research Associate at CDPP. She has a Master's degree in Public Policy and Governance from the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Hyderabad.

Sejal Gupta is a Senior Research Fellow at CDPP, working on the Regulation Project across Emerging, Infrastructure, and Consumer sectors. She holds a Master's in Urban Planning (SPA, New Delhi), where she won the Prof. N.S. Saini Gold Medal, and a Bachelor's in Architecture (RV College, Bengaluru).

Manisha Dhulipala is a Senior Research Fellow at CDPP with 15+ years of experience in research and policy advocacy in public health, environment, and development. She holds an M.Sc. in Science and Technology for Sustainability (SPRU, University of Sussex), an M.Sc. in Environmental Sciences (Marathwada University), and a B.Sc. in Microbiology (Osmania University).

Lubna Ludheen is a Research Associate at CDPP. She has a Master's Degree in Public Policy from Mount Carmel College, Bengaluru.

Mohammed Ahmed is a Graphic and UI Designer with 20+ years of experience across industries. He has a bachelor's degree in Commerce from Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Open University, Telangana.

Mohammed Rahmath Ali is the Manager, Operations & Finance at CDPP. He has a degree in Commerce from Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana.

Iqra Ahmed is a Communications and Copyediting Associate at CDPP. She has a Master's degree in Journalism and Mass Communication from Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh, Assam.

Arnav Panwar is a Research Fellow at CDPP. He has an undergraduate degree from FLAME University in Public Policy. He has previously worked as a research intern at TIDE, Bangalore.

Areeb Barr Abdullah is a Research Intern at CDPP. He holds a Bachelor's degree from Jamia Millia Islamia and a Master's degree in Geography from Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia Avadh University.

About CLES

The Centre for Law, Economics and Society is a CDPP initiative that seeks to research on the legal landscape in India. Research areas will include the challenges people face to access legal justice and identify areas of improvement to provide quality legal aid services.

Access to justice means that individuals can have their legal rights and grievances addressed through the legal system. However, in India, access to justice faces many barriers like the high cost of legal services, lack of legal representation in certain areas of the country, and a high number of pending cases discouraging people from seeking legal justice. Additionally, it is recognised that access to justice can be particularly challenging for marginalized groups in India, such as Muslims, Dalits, Indigenous people and women. These groups may face discrimination and social barriers that make it harder for them to access legal remedies and justice.

The Constitution of India has provisions for legal aid services to ensure that everyone has access to justice regardless of their financial circumstances. However, legal service institutions are not able to provide quality services due to a lack of infrastructure, uneven human distribution, and inefficient utilisation of funds. Through research, we aim to provide insights into the lacunae in the legal process with a focus on the marginalised sections of the society.

CLES Advisory Board

M. N. Rao, Former Chief Justice, of Himachal High Court and Former Judge of the Andhra Pradesh High Court

Faizan Mustafa, Former Vice Chancellor, NALSAR

Shafeeq Mahajir, Senior Counsel

Sanjay Chadha, Senior Counsel, Supreme Court of India

Aman Wadud, Lawyer, Guwahati High Court

Qudsia Tabassum, Advocate

Afsar Jahan, Government pleader, High Court of Telangana

Mohammed Faud Mirza, Philanthropist

Dushyant, Lawyer, Andha Kanoon, Andha Samaaj

Sumaira R. Khan, Advocate and Educationist

Mani Chander, Lawyer

Aleem Khan, Trustee at GBKT

Azam Khan, Director at SDIF

Hyder Khan, M.D., Ph.D Board President and Trustee of USIPI

Organising Partners

Centre for Development Policy and Practice (CDPP): CDPP is a research group that focuses on development concerns and public policy challenges in the world today. Working with a team of research professionals and expert consultants under the guidance of eminent public intellectuals, CDPP conducts research studies, develops policy papers, publishes a peer-reviewed quarterly Journal, and hosts conferences in addition to regular seminars and workshops.

Digital Empowerment Foundation (DEF): DEF is a Delhi-based nonprofit organisation working towards empowering people to gain access to better healthcare, education, skills, and livelihood opportunities through digital literacy and digital tools. The organisation's main focus is to make technology easily accessible to the masses, and to empower women, youth, persons with disabilities, and the elderly through providing functional digital literacy, media literacy, and digital up-skilling across agriculture, micro and nano-business, health, education, livelihood, and entrepreneurial skills.

Centre for Women Studies, Maulana Azad National Urdu University (MANUU): Since its inception, the centre has been actively engaged in teaching, training, research, and extension activities. The centre aims to promote gender equality through education. Through these activities, the centre focusses on empowerment of urdu speaking women and on critical issues pertaining to gender equality at the community level.

Kautilya School of Public Policy, GITAM (KSPP): KSPP is a part of GITAM (Deemed to be University), Hyderabad, established in 1980. The school is dedicated to advancing the study and practice of public policy. Since its inception, the school has been actively engaged in offering academic programmes, research, and outreach activities aimed at fostering the development of competent policy leaders at international levels.

The Education Group (London) Ltd. (TEG): TEG is a leading recruitment partner and full-service consultancy specialising in the tertiary education sector. Since 2020, TEG has been the exclusive service partner of the University of the West of Scotland, London Campus, offering solutions in facilities management, global marketing, student recruitment, admissions, and enhancing the overall student experience through TEG Club.

Associate Partners

Jahangirabad Institute of Technology (JIT): JIT is a private engineering and management institute located in Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India. Established with the aim of providing quality technical and professional education, JIT offers undergraduate and postgraduate programs in engineering, management, and computer applications.

The Council on Energy, Environment and Water (CEEW): CEEW is one of South Asia's leading not-for-profit policy research institutions. Based in India, CEEW works at the intersection of energy, environment, and sustainable development. It is renowned for producing high-quality, evidence-based research and for supporting decision-making at the local, national, and global levels.

International Institute of Information Technology, Hyderabad (IIITH): IIIT-His an autonomous university, founded as a not-for-profit public private partnership (N-PPP) in 1998, and is the first IIIT in India under this model. Over the years, the institute has evolved strong research programmes in various areas, with an emphasis on technology and applied research for industry and society. The institute facilitates interdisciplinary research and a seamless flow of knowledge.

Road to People & Platforms: Let's Talk Accountability

DCS25 WEEKLY WEBINAR SERIES

Starting from October 08, 2025

- Theme I : **Governing Data, Governing Rights**
- Theme II : **Digital Justice and Citizenship**
- Theme III : **Truth in the Age of Disinformation**
- Theme IV : **Technology for Local Futures**
- Theme V : **Digital Artisans and Cultural Innovation**
- Theme VI : **Ethical AI for Social Good**

SCAN QR FOR DCS25 REGISTRATION

Organisers

Principal Partners

Associate Partners

Inclusion and Equity Partner

Knowledge Partners

Media Partner
MEDIANAMA

14-15 November | T-HUB, Hyderabad

For more information, visit the CDPP website: www.cdpp.co.in

OUR PREVIOUS WORKING PAPERS

SERIES-2025

- Understanding the Regulatory Landscape in India: A Comprehensive Look at Consumer Sectors (Food Safety and Healthcare)
 - Creating Institutional Excellence in India's Secondary, Higher Secondary, and Tertiary Education: A Case Study of MS Education Academy
 - Understanding the Regulatory Landscape of Emerging and Infrastructure Sectors
-

SERIES-2024

- Understanding Communal Clashes During Religious Processions
 - Unveiling Stigma: Addressing Menstrual Hygiene and Health in the Indian Context
 - Workforce Participation in India: Where Are the Women?
 - Diversity and Disparities: A Study on Caste, Religion, Gender, and Disability in Higher Education in India
-

SERIES-2023

- From Speech to Action—Exploring Hate Speech Origins, Impact, and Interventions from Multidisciplinary Perspectives
 - The World's Biggest Country: India's Demographic Trajectory and Its Impact on Muslims, the Parliament and the Labour Market
 - Agriculture in Telangana: From Plight to Pride
 - Internet Control and the Rise of Discrimination in India
-

SERIES-2022

- Muslim Women: Tackling Vulnerability and Marginalisation
 - How Healthy is our Young Population
 - Educating Challenges: Quality and Inclusion
 - Situating Development of Muslims in Uttar Pradesh
-

SERIES-2021

- The IT Industry in Telangana
 - Why Do Young Urban Indians Vote the Way They Do
 - Situating Development of Muslims in Telangana
 - Tracing the Evolution of Citizenship
 - Philanthropy in India
 - Education Quality
 - Tracking Discrimination
 - COVID-19 and India
 - Study on The IT Industry of Hyderabad
 - India's Agritech Sector
 - India's Healthcare Market
 - Technology Aided Models
-

The Centre for Development Policy and Practice (CDPP) brings out quarterly working papers based on the research work being carried out here. These are published on our website www.cdpp.co.in and sent to a select group for review, comments, and critique.

CENTRE FOR
DEVELOPMENT
POLICY AND
PRACTICE

CENTRE FOR DEVELOPMENT POLICY AND PRACTICE

10-3-303, 3rd Floor, Serene Heights, Masab Tank, Hyderabad - 500 028, T.S., India
info@cdpp.co.in | www.cdpp.co.in | 040 - 3516 4255 | +91 93915 81698